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Results of the user studies and requirements on “Individual Reflection at Work”

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List of Abbreviations

App	Application; small self-contained software with specific purpose
CRM	Customer Relationship Management
RGN	Registered General Nurse (used in context of staff at RNHA)
SU	Stroke Unit (at NBN); intensive care unit whose staff is the central target user group for MIRROR at NBN

Executive Summary

WP4’s overarching goal is to support learning by reflection at work, with a focus on individual learning, individual reflection and learning by observation. A specific sub-goal is to gain an improved understanding of triggers for reflection, i.e. what makes people actually reflect. Within this deliverable, we (i) show evidence that supports the assumption that people at selected MIRROR testbeds do learn by reflection and by observing others, (ii) identify and categorise concrete situations in which people reflect, what they reflect upon, and what they learn from reflection, (iii) identify categories of triggers for reflection, (iv) collect existing work tools and data as well as reflective practices at selected MIRROR testbeds as connecting points into which future reflection Apps can hook into, and (v) discuss potential technological support for reflection.

Objective

This deliverable shows our achievement of “**Objective 4.1: Deepen understanding of individual reflective learning at work.**” Insights gained from the user studies from WP4’s perspective will naturally feed into the overall continued development of theory on reflection within MIRROR.

In particular, we investigated the following assumptions and research question based on data collected at MIRROR testbeds:

- **Assumption 1:** People reflect upon their work
- **Assumption 2:** People learn by observing others at work
- **Research Question 1a:** When and how does individual reflection about work and learning practices occur at work?
- **Research Question 1b:** Are there any typical triggers for reflection?
- **Research Question 2:** Is individual reflection currently aided by tools?
- **Research Question 3:** Which kind of technological support could be used to support reflective learning at work?

Method

In order to verify the above assumptions and answer the research questions, we designed research instruments that would help us elicit answers from the target users in the MIRROR testbeds. Tools that we used were a **reflection diary, a reflection questionnaire, a job description questionnaire and a focus group on “Technology Support for Learning by Reflection at Work”**. Tool design here means that we formulated the precise questions, and prepared mock-ups and discussion inputs. These tools can of course also be used in the future to investigate other workplaces with regard to reflection.

All five MIRROR testbeds, RNHA, NBN, Regola, BT, Infoman, responded with reflection questionnaires. Within this work, we used this data for a descriptive analysis with which we support Assumptions 1 and 2. From RNHA, NBN and Infoman we have additional data in the form of reflection diaries, interviews and focus groups. Within this work, we used this data for a qualitative analysis through which we support Assumptions 1 and 2, and answer Research Questions 1-3.

Analysis and Results

We support **Assumptions 1 and 2** with a descriptive analysis of the returned reflection questionnaires, i.e. we find that on average employees of NBN agree with the statement that they reflect upon their work to a degree of 3.7 (where 1 denotes no agreement and 5 strong

agreement). We also support Assumptions 1 and 2 with reflection stories, i.e. real concrete stories about everyday work situations of user study participants in which reflection happens and direct quotes from user study participants that indicate that learning. An exemplary reflection story, taken from the testbed NBN, illustrates both the format of a reflection story, and reflection at NBN:

The participants did a simulation of reanimation. This was video-recorded from three perspectives. “*We have observed others and then ourselves. Also in order to compare how I felt with how it looks. I had thought during the reanimation that I was very slow, and then I realized that I was nearly too fast. [...] The perception was very different, this has confirmed me in not needing to become even faster.*” (Interview)

In order to answer **Research Question 1a** systematically, we developed the following classification scheme. This scheme was developed based on the existing theory of reflection, ongoing theoretical work within the MIRROR project, as well as existing user study data.

Characteristics of a Reflection Situation

- **At Work, Outside Work** (Where, when)
- **Individual, Supervised, Collaborative** (With whom).

Content Characteristics

- **Single Experience, Set of Experiences**
- **Activity, Interaction with Colleagues, Interaction with Patient or Client, Own Reaction** (Topics of Reflection and Observation)
- **Individual Experience, Vicarious Experience, Shared Experience.** (Ownership of Experience)

Outcome Characteristics

- **Individual Learning, Organisational Learning** (Who learns).
- **Individual, Team, Organisational Scope** (Scope of Reflection)

We clustered evidence for learning by reflection that we found in user study data from Infoman, NBN and RNHA into the above classification scheme, and can thus provide a good impression of the diversity of reflection in these three real workplaces.

The result of our analysis of the given data according to **Research Question 1b** is the following categorisation of triggers for reflection:

- **Different from Baseline**
- **Emotion**
- **Information Input**
- **Feedback from / Reaction of Stakeholders**

Note that from a theoretical viewpoint, we assume that what triggers reflection is a “discrepancy between expectations and the current experience” (see Sect. 2.1.1). However, for practical purposes, we wanted to be able to differentiate between different kinds of triggers. We expect that an understanding of concrete triggers will constitute a significant contribution to the advancement of theory on reflective learning. Additionally, we expect insights into triggers to be a first step towards intelligent prompting for reflection, or “reflection recommenders” that recommend people to reflect.

In order to answer **Research Question 2**, we looked for tools that already support reflection, as well as data or data sets, which are created during work, and tools, which are used during work, as well as reflective practices.

We found hardly any direct technical support for reflection at Infoman, NBN and RNHA. The closest support we found was the lysis protocol at NBN, where the protocol requires a reasoning both where the lysis (a treatment for stroke) was applied and where it was not applied. On the other hand, we found a rich amount of data and data sets, as well as technical support for work and mature reflective practices in place. All these can serve as starting point for the development of further reflection apps of MIRROR.

Research Question 3 was most deeply explored together with NBN through the focus groups. For Infoman and RNHA, we excerpted various statements concerning wishes for technological support from other research instruments. We explored how (i) data that captures externally observable data, (ii) physiological data, (iii) mood data can support learning by reflection, and whether target users have a strategic approach to learning. Additionally, we identified barriers and constraints for technology support, and collected explicit App ideas.

Overall we found that users clearly see video or audio trails of their work as a good potential basis for reflection, as well as their “usual” work data. Target users are more sceptical about physiological and mood data, but mostly in connection with the explanation that “we cannot do anything about it anyway”, i.e. users seem to see little possibility to act on knowledge about their physiological or emotional state. Except for physicians in specialist training, we did not find much resonance with users concerning a strategic approach to learning.

Implications and Outlook

A major constraint of target users is that they have little time to do something “in addition” during their working hours. We conclude from this that future reflection Apps must be integrated into existing work practices. Additionally, we will strive to use existing data, and to “insert reflection” unobtrusively into everyday work.

Concerning the content of reflection, the user study results indicate that the development of domain-specific knowledge and self-organisation capabilities, as well as the communication with clients, patients or residents is more important to target users than the communication with colleagues or reflection on one’s own reaction. This result aligns well with the above discussed constraint on time. We therefore plan to develop reflection Apps that are testbed-specific in the immediate future. This focus will give us the possibility to well integrate Apps into existing work environments.

In the upcoming Year 2 of the MIRROR project, WP4 will start **progressing towards**

- “**Objective 4.2:** Design a user profile which contains an adequate summary of an individual’s work history”
- “**Objective 4.3:** Create individual reflection Apps that convert the user profile into a “usable” representation that supports individual reflection”
- “**Objective 4.4:** Create a platform where work practices and experiences can be shared within a community of practice”.

We will do so by developing first reflection Apps together with MIRROR testbed partners. We see the inclusion of sharing functionalities not as crucial in the upcoming year, but will include them if they are at the core of specified reflection Apps, e.g. if they are necessary to trigger reflection by using shared data as baseline against which experiences are compared.

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1 Introduction

WP4’s overarching goal is to support (individual) learning by reflection at work. We primarily focus on **individual reflection** and **individual learning**. By individual reflection we mean individual reflection on one’s own, at work or elsewhere, informal individual reflection with colleagues, boss, or friends/family, and institutionalized individual reflection supported by a supervisor, peer-groups. By individual learning we understand improving existing competencies or acquiring new competencies. We expect that observation of and comparison others provides an important basis for individual reflection. Observation enables learners to improve without having to make every experience themselves, or every mistake. Observed work practices can both provide learners with data to learn from, and a baseline on which to assess own work. Within MIRROR, we consider learning by observation in the sense of observing work practices of others, and relating them to own work practices. The relation to own work is a necessary prerequisite so that individual learning can take place. A major research interest within WP4 is to understand **what triggers the internal reflection process** within learners. Understanding of concrete triggers will constitute a significant contribution to the advancement of theory on reflective learning. Additionally, we expect insights into triggers to be a first step towards intelligent prompting for reflection, or “reflection recommenders” that recommend people to reflect.

Within this deliverable, we analyse empirical data collected at MIRROR testbeds, mostly at Infoman, NBN and RNHA although to a small extent we include results from Regola as well. With this analysis, we **specifically address**

- **“Objective 4.1:** Deepen understanding of individual reflective learning at work”.

In the discussion section, we summarise the user study results and **look onwards** specifically to

- **“Objective 4.2:** Design a user profile which contains an adequate summary of an individual’s work history”
- **“Objective 4.3:** Create individual reflection Apps that convert the user profile into a “usable” representation that supports individual reflection”

and address how the findings of the user studies will influence the design research work in the years to come, specifically of course in the upcoming year.

Section 2 contains the theoretical background of this deliverable. The first part, Sect. 2.1, is shared with the Deliverables 3.1, 4.1, 5.1, 6.1, 7.1, 8.1 and describes MIRROR’s underlying understanding of reflective learning. The second part, Sect. 2.2 adds WP4-specific further theoretical background. In Sect. 3, we highlight the research questions that we primarily address within this deliverable. In Sect. 4, we list the testbeds and empirical data that were collected from them. In Sect. 4, we list the research methods. The main part of this deliverable is Sect. 6, in which we describe how we analysed the empirical data and present the results of our analysis. Section 7 concludes this deliverable with (i) an overall summary of the contribution this deliverable makes towards reflection theory (ii) a discussion of implications for the development of reflection Apps, and (iii) an outlook on our future work with specific focus on Year 2 of MIRROR.

2 Theoretical Background

2.1 MIRROR’s Understanding of the Role of Reflective Learning at Work

The purpose of this section is to summarize our current understanding of reflection in MIRROR and to provide a common set of basic concepts to apply across the deliverables **D3.1, D4.1, D5.1, D6.1, D7.1 and D8.1**. This section is included in all these deliverables.

The document is based on continuous work in the first year of MIRROR to identify and agree on a shared set of concepts. This section does **not** include emerging theory based on the empirical work in MIRROR. The set of shared concepts will be refined over the course of the project.

The document starts with an outline of concepts related to the individual process of reflection, followed by a section on reflective learning on individual, collaborative and organizational levels. Next the concept of reflection session is elaborated, providing a link to the MIRROR requirements process and the storyboards with test bed specific requirements (to be documented in **D1.3**). Finally there is a section on the roles of tools in reflection, pointing towards the MIRROR design space.

2.1.1 The Reflection Process

Reflective learning refers to “those intellectual and affective activities in which individuals engage to explore their experiences in order to lead to new understandings and appreciations” (Boud 1985). In MIRROR we base our understanding of the process of reflective learning on the model of (Boud 1985), in which the learner re-evaluates past experience by attending to its various aspects, thereby producing outcomes (Figure 1). This process is a core element in collaborative reflection and in organizational learning

Figure 1: The process of reflective learning (Boud 1985)

In everyday as well as academic language ‘**experience**’ refers both to single experiences (of specific events or situations) and general experience in the form of knowledge/skills/attitudes collected and developed over time. Also, experience can be seen as a continuous “flow” of which people can be more or less conscious.

In the reflective learning process (Figure 1) we can consider the experience returned to as a single experience or as a set of such single experiences. A **single experience** is defined as **the total response of a person to a situation**, including behaviour, ideas and feelings. Given the differences between individuals, the experience of one and the same event will be different in different persons.

In the reflective process, the re-evaluation of experience requires generalization and abstraction from the concrete experiences as well as attention to their emotional aspects. The learners’ knowledge serves as a resource for – and outcome of - the re-evaluation.

The outcome of reflective learning can be cognitive, affective, and/or behavioural. A reflective process, through its outcome, always results in some “resolution”, even if the outcome does not necessarily have an immediate and/or measurable impact on the work practice in question. **For our purposes (in MIRROR) we consider reflection and reflective learning to be the same thing.**

A key aspect in making a reflective process happen is the presence of **triggers**. Triggers are unexpected situations (e.g. disturbances and perception of uncertainty, or positive situations like surprising success) creating awareness of discrepancy between expectations and the current experience. Reflection might be triggered by an external event or agent (external trigger/incident) or might develop from one’s own thinking (internal trigger/inner need to reflect).

2.1.2 Reflective Learning on Individual, Collaborative and Organizational Levels

Reflection can take place **individually** and **collaboratively**. For reflection to be collaborative, the participants need to share experiences and relate to others’ experiences in their own reflection, resulting in a spiral-like interaction between individual and collaborative reflection. Collaborative reflection may be based on experiences of shared events and situations of collaboration between the participants, but also on individual experiences that are not related to the same events but are comparable through a **shared context** (e.g. experiences from similar, individual work tasks taking place at different times and/or different locations). Individual and collaborative reflection has different advantages and can complement each other in workplace learning.

Reflective learning can also be viewed on the level of the organization. **Organizational learning**, an organization’s improvement of its task performance over time (Argyris 1996), can be seen as a consequence of the learning taking place in individuals and teams in the organization in the context of their work, e.g. through a **bottom-up** learning process. Learning in an organization is also framed by the organization’s **top-down** management of its processes, which may be more or less explicit about the role of informal learning and employees’ reflection on work experience. Management in an organization may reflect on their own performance (and that of the organization) on the basis of data from the organization; this data may originate in processes of work but also in processes of reflection through which the employees share their ideas and views.

In workplace learning, reflection and **problem solving** can be seen as closely related and feeding into each other (Schön 1983).

2.1.3 The Reflection Session

By **reflection session** we refer to a time-limited activity framing and supporting processes of reflection. Reflection sessions range from the small, individual, spontaneous pause in between work tasks to the scheduled, elaborately organized and facilitated workshop in a team. Key **dimensions that can be used to characterize reflection sessions** are Objectives, Content, Process, Outcomes, Support, and Timing. These dimensions, to be elaborated below, are not completely independent.

Objectives

The objective(s) of a reflection session link the reflection to work processes. The objectives may be more or less explicit. Objectives can be characterized in more detail outlining whether they are on **individual, team and/or organization/management level**, in which **specific work/business processes** and the objective(s) originate (e.g. day-to-day needs of individual work practice, plan for individual competence development,..), to which **roles** they relate, and what are the **more specific goals** (e.g. related to sense making, problem solving, improvement or performance)

Content

By content we refer to ‘the thing reflected upon’. The content can be characterized in more detail by outlining whether the reflection is addressing **individual experience and/or shared experience** (e.g. among the members of a work team), whether the reflection is addressing a **single experience** and/or a **set of experiences**, whether the reflection is concerned with **one work process** or issues that **span several work processes**, which work process(es) are in focus, and whether **other representations** of the relevant work practice (e.g. best practices, standards, simulations such as in a serious game) are being used in the re-evaluation of the experience

Process

This refers to how the activities in the reflection session are being conducted. These processes can be **individual and/or collaborative**.

Outcomes

This refers to the results of the reflection session, e.g. what is being produced, some of which may be planned and some unplanned. In characterizing the outcomes of a reflection session, the following should be considered: Which **articulated knowledge** is developed/constructed (e.g. lessons learned, creative solutions, proposed changes to certain work processes, and refined/annotated/aggregated data from a work process), which **artifacts** are produced (e.g. reports and personal notes), to which **roles** and **processes** the outcomes are relevant, which knowledge and artifacts are intended to be **shared** (and with whom), and what are the actual **changes in work practices**

Support

This refers to support or **scaffolding** for reflection, which can be provided by a human coach/ facilitator and/or by tools. Support can be characterized by the way **access to data** from the work process is being provided (subject to numerous considerations regarding availability, privacy, representation/presentation, sharing etc.) by the **roles in the reflection session** (e.g. is there a facilitator), by the **procedural support** (e.g. guidance through certain steps), by the support for **articulating and sharing knowledge** within the reflection session and in the creation of its outcomes, and by the specific techniques/approaches used (such as creativity techniques and **serious games**).

Timing

This refers to when the reflection session takes place, in particular how it is scheduled with respect to work processes. It also refers to the duration of the session. The timing can be characterized by outlining to what extent the reflection session is **separate from, or intertwined/concurrent with, the work process** (If reflection happens in frequent, small steps, e.g. in between work tasks, it may be convenient to consider these steps together as one reflection session), whether the session is a **pre-scheduled activity or initiated upon**

need or convenience, and what are the **criteria and conditions for starting and terminating the session**. The start of a session may for instance be based on the learners’ initiative (e.g. on the occurrence of a trigger for a reflective process) and/or on some form of prompting. The termination of the session may be based on time allocated/elapsed, the occurrence of certain events in the work process, the completion of certain outcomes, etc.

2.1.4 The Roles of Tools in Reflection at Work

Tools may have different roles in supporting reflection at work (Krogstie 2009). Two key categories of tool use are **gathering data from the work process** and **providing support for the reflection session**.

Tool support for a reflection session includes providing **access to data** from the work process. Some of this data may serve to trigger reflection, other data may be used to make sense of (recall, reconstruct) the experience(s) in question. Tool support for the reflection session may also take the form of **process guidance**, e.g. guide its steps. Further, tools may support the **articulation and sharing of knowledge** in a reflection session and in producing outcomes of value to the surrounding work and business processes.

Finally, in considering support for reflection we need to consider **tools that support the work process** more broadly, since tool use in day-to-day work and reflection may be closely intertwined and one may impact on the other.

2.2 WP4’s perspective on learning and reflection

The objective of WP 4 is to support individuals to learn by reflecting on their own work practices, and to learn from the observation of others’ practices by reflecting on the similarities and differences between them (see MIRROR 2010a, p20). Related to the reflection sessions as described above, this means that we define our scope along the following dimensions.

First, we focus on reflection sessions where the **content of reflection** is the learner’s own experience. We therefore also consider settings in which the learner is aided by a person in a supervisory role or by a peer group. This provides the first interface to collaborative reflection, in the sense that articulation of own experiences and insights, as well as social interaction is required. Additionally, we see reflection on own experiences as natural starting point for seeking collaborative reflection, or reflection with an organisational scope (bottom-up process of organisational learning). Second, we focus on reflection sessions where the **scope** is individual, and the **outcome** is individual learning. Here, we see a second interface to collaborative reflection, since we naturally expect individual insights and individual learning to happen in parallel to collaborative reflection.

Below we clarify the concepts of learning by observation and “work and learning practices” as understood within WP4, as these are central to our work.

2.2.1 Learning by observation

People **learn** not only from their own experiences, but also **from others’ experiences** by directly or indirectly (e.g., reading about) observing (Bandura 1996). For our ongoing work, we are not concerned with learning by imitating others, but with learning that occurs when **observing and reflecting on others’ experiences**. By this we mean, that the learner puts the experience of someone else in relation with her own experiences, with her own behaviour / cognitive or affective actions in similar situations, and with future experiences. We therefore include **vicarious experiences** as possible object of

reflection. By vicarious experiences we understand experiences made by others. These can become accessible to the learner directly, such as when watching in real-life, or through a medium, such as when reading a case description or watching a video, etc. A shared context between the observed vicarious experience and the learner’s own experience allows the learner to gain insights useful for own future work practice. Learning by observation, from vicarious experiences, allows learners to learn more efficiently than by trying out every alternative themselves, or coming up with every solution by themselves. We see reflecting on vicarious experiences, in contrast to observing and just imitating, as the key to successfully learning complex lessons from observing others.

2.2.2 Work and learning practices

We consider working as intertwined with learning, in line with Eraut (2004) and Lindstaedt (2010). Where useful, we emphasize this by talking about “work and learning practices”. By this we mean learning practices that are embedded in work practices, and even necessary to successfully carry out the assigned work. Thus we investigate in our research at work experiences in which learning must occur, or naturally occurs because the nature of the work requires learning to happen. We see this concept of integrated work and learning also as helpful to approach motivational issues. Many employees and especially most organisations have as first interest that “the work is done well” and see continuous learning only as secondary goal. Where the understanding exists that learning is necessary to perform successfully, we hence expect a higher motivation to learn during work.

3 Research Interests

The research instruments that we employed in the user studies were designed to allow answering the following research questions. Also our analysis of the empirical data that was collected, target these research questions. In addition to the research questions 1-3, which are also stated in MIRROR (2010a, Part B, p23), we were interested in verifying the basic assumptions of MIRROR (Assumptions 1 and 2).

Assumption 1: People reflect upon their work

This is an assumption about the AS IS situation in the investigated testbeds. If it holds, this also indicates that learning by reflection is important for target users.

Assumption 2: People learn by observing others at work

This is also an assumption about the AS IS situation in the investigated testbeds. If it holds, this also indicates that learning by observation is important for target users.

Research Question 1a: When and how does individual reflection about work and learning practices occur at work?

This research question is aimed at the AS IS situation of individual reflection in the investigated testbeds. We describe our corresponding research in Sects. 6.1.3 and 6.2.3.

Research Question 1b: Are there any typical triggers for reflection?

This research question also targets the AS IS situation of individual reflection. We describe our corresponding research in Sects. 6.1.4 and 6.2.4. We believe that this research is highly significant for the future advancement of theory on reflective learning at work. Little concrete knowledge about what actually makes knowledge workers reflect is currently available both in literature and in practice, while at the same time this knowledge will be very helpful in devising technological support for learning by reflection.

Research Question 2: Is individual reflection currently aided by tools?

This research question also targets the AS IS situation of individual reflection. Anticipating the results of our studies already, namely that there is no explicit technological support for reflection in the targeted testbeds, we extended the scope of this research question. In our analysis of empirical data regarding this research question we therefore included existing tools and data about work, as well as existing reflective practices. Such existing tools, data and reflective practices are natural points of connection for future reflection Apps. In the discussion section, we will link results regarding this research question with the theory on roles of tools for reflection described above (Sect. 2.1.4).

Research Question 3: Which kind of technological support could be used to support reflective learning at work?

This research question targets the future practice of individual reflection at work, supported technologically by reflection Apps. We explored four kinds of entry points for reflection: (i) observable data about work experience, (ii) physiological reaction to work experience, (iii) emotional reaction to work experience and (iv) strategic approach to work-related learning). We also include in our analysis barriers or constraints for reflection Apps, and collected explicit App ideas. Results of our research regarding this research question will very directly flow into the overall design process within the project.

4 Methods/Research Instruments

In order to answer the above stated research questions, we have used different research instruments in our user studies, as outlined already in MIRROR (2010b), p31. Below we shortly list those that were actually used.

4.1.1 Reflection Questionnaire

The reflection questionnaire is used to detect the occurrence of reflection within the test-beds (see MIRROR 2010b, p56; MIRROR 2010b Part B p44-46).

Due to the specific nature of the RNHA testbed -- mainly a lower level of education and concerns about the level of literacy -- a shortened version of the reflection questionnaire with easier language was used (see Appendix E, p3). The modifications were well received by the testbed and likely lead to an increase response rate. While the level of detail and accuracy in which the key aspects can be captured is lower, these aspects can still be compared to the other testbeds.

Note that the questionnaires were distributed in different languages, i.e. NBN and Infoman received them in German, Regola in Italian, and BT and RNHA in English.

4.1.2 Job Description and Reflection Interview

The job description interview is used to capture various kind of information about a job at a test bed partner (see MIRROR 2010b, p52). The reflection interview allows the structured assessment of reflection with regard to multiple aspects (see MIRROR 2010b, p56).

Note that as is typical for interviews, the interviewers tried to create an interesting flow of conversation for the user study participant. Additionally, different interviewers at different testbeds prioritised topics differently. Hence, the topics covered in interviews vary between testbeds, and between single interviews.

4.1.3 Reflection Diary

The purpose of reflective diaries is to find specific instances where reflection has occurred in various situations at the workplace (see MIRROR 2010b, p55).

4.1.4 Focus Group on “Technology Support for Learning by Reflection at Work”

In order to specifically explore user interests regarding technology support for learning by reflection, we added focus groups as a research instrument. The rationale of adding such a research instrument was to discuss emerging ideas for reflection Apps with target users before the start of App-specific development activities. We use the results from these focus groups as direct input to the design and development of reflection Apps. Additionally, the focus groups give also insights into what kind of image of learning by reflection target users share as a group.

A description of the focus group as a research instrument (in English), as well as the moderation field manual for the “Technology Support for Learning by Reflection at Work” focus groups (in German) is attached to this deliverable as Appendix A.

5 Testbeds and Sample

Testbed descriptions are available in MIRROR (2010b, p21ff) for all testbed partners. For Infoman, NBN and RNHA additional, very extensive workplace descriptions have emerged from the on-site user studies (Appendices B, C, D). Hence, testbed partners are only very shortly described below. Additionally, we describe what kind of user study data we analyse for each testbed, and describe the sample in terms of demographic characteristics such as occupation, age and gender.

Note that KNOW as workpackage leader has led the design of research tools from a WP4 perspective, as well as performed the analysis of user study data that is contained in this deliverable. However, below we point out that we use a lot of data that was collected by other MIRROR research partners.

5.1 Registered Nursing Homes Association (RNHA)

Short Description

RNHA is a group of registered nursing homes. The residents are elderly people, many of them suffering from dementia. The target group of MIRROR are the carers and nurses working at RNHA. (see Appendix D). The used data was collected at Kinton Manor Nursing Home, at Marillac Carehome, at Wren Hall Nursing Home and at Palm Court Nursing Home.

User Study Sample

Reflection Diary:

- The organisation of keeping reflection diaries was conducted by KMRC.
- 5 persons kept a Reflection Diary at RNHA. Of these, two are RGNs (registered general nurses) and three are carers. The participants' ages are between 26 and 59 years. Four participants work at Kinton Manor Nursing Home, and one participant at Marillac Carehome.

Job Description and Reflection Interview:

- The Job Description and Reflection Interview was conducted by RUB. This interview consisted of questions covering both job description and reflection at work, as well as a description of documentation methods within the care home.
- 3 persons at RNHA were interviewed, all three were carers. The age of the interviewees ranges between 39 and 49.

Reflection Questionnaire:

- The organisation of the staff survey questionnaire was conducted by KMRC.
- 50 people at RNHA filled in the questionnaire. The age ranges from 21 to 63, 7 male and 43 female persons participated. The participants consisted of 28 carers, 5 nurses, 15 housekeeping staff (e.g. cooks, kitchen assistants), and 2 managers. 28 participants are working in the Kinton Manor Nursing Home, 22 are working at Wren Hall Nursing Home.

5.2 Neurological Clinic Bad Neustadt (NBN)

Short Description

The Stroke Unit (SU) at the Neurologische Clinic Bad Neustadt deals with neurological emergencies especially with the treatment of strokes. The target group of MIRROR are physicians, nurses and therapists working at the SU. (see Appendix C).

User Study Sample

Reflection Diary:

- The organisation of keeping reflection diaries was conducted by KMRC.
- Three different staff members of the SU filled in 3 diaries. There is no further demographical data about the participant, because the study participants were concerned about their privacy given the small sample of users that participated.

Reflection Interview:

- The reflection interview was conducted by KMRC. Reflection Interviews contain aspects of individual and collaborative reflection, knowledge management and knowledge exchange with colleagues, experiential learning in general, and data available for reflection.
- 7 people were interviewed at NBN, 3 physicians and 4 nurses. The age of the interviewees ranges between 27 and 50.

Reflection Questionnaire:

- The organisation of the staff survey questionnaire was conducted by KMRC.
- At NBN 39 staff members filled in the questionnaire. The age ranges from 22 to 51, 8 males and 28 females (3 provided no gender information). The participants consisted of 7 physicians, 12 nurses, 10 carers, 4 therapists and 6 without further information about their position.

“Potential Tools for Individual Reflection” Focus Groups:

- The focus groups were conducted by KC supported by KMRC.
- Three different focus groups were conducted, one group with 3 physicians, one group with 4 nurses and one group with 4 therapists. The participant’s ages range from 20-59; 8 females and 3 males.

5.3 Regola

Short Description

Regola provides IT solutions for the health and emergency management sector. The originally intended target group for MIRROR are workers in this sector, e.g. volunteers at the Civil Protection in Turin. However, access to this target user group proved to be very difficult. In the meantime, Regola has offered their own company and employees as testbed and target user group respectively. In this deliverable, we can therefore provide insight into the occurrence of learning by reflection and observation at Regola directly.

User Study Sample

Reflection Questionnaire:

- The organisation of the staff survey questionnaire was conducted by KMRC.
- At Regola, 17 staff members returned the reflection questionnaire, 12 male and 5 female. The age ranges from 25 to 45. The participants consist of 1 graphic designer, 1 programmer, 1 senior programmer, 1 administrative secretary, 1 system administrator, 4 software developer, 1 student, 1 volunteer, 1 entrepreneur, 1 commercial employee, 1 research and development member, 3 employees with no further description

5.4 British Telecom (BT)

Short Description

BT has 1500 contracts that are managed by contract teams. These are large, customized contracts. The target group for MIRROR are the members of these contract teams.

User Study Sample

Reflection Questionnaire:

- The organisation of the staff survey questionnaire was conducted by KMRC.
- 4 staff members of BT returned the reflection questionnaire, three male and one female. The age ranges from 27 to 35. The participants consist of one director and three strategy specialists.

Note that **because of the small number of participants from BT, we did not use the results of this questionnaire for analysis** (Sects. 6.2.1 and 6.2.2).

5.5 Infoman

Short Description

The main strategic objective of Infoman AG is to analyse and optimise the marketing, sales and service processes of companies. The target group of MIRROR are consultant and sales persons working at Infoman. (see Appendix B).

User Study Sample

Reflection Diary:

- The organisation of keeping reflective diaries was conducted by KMRC.
- 1 Tele Account Manager and 1 Business Consultant filled in the reflection diary, both male. The age ranges between 29 to 51. The Tele Account Manager kept the diary for two times, the first when he started working and the second after being about six months at Infoman.

Reflection Interview:

- The reflection interview was conducted by KMRC. Reflection Interviews contain aspects of individual and collaborative reflection, knowledge management and knowledge exchange with colleagues, experiential learning in general, and data available for reflection.
- 5 reflection interviews were conducted, 2 Business Consultants, 2 IT / Presales and 1 Tele Account Manager. The age ranged from 29 to 50.

Reflection Questionnaire:

- The organisation of the staff survey questionnaire was conducted by KMRC.
- 3 members of Infoman filled in the reflection questionnaire, two male and one female. The age ranges from 28 to 50. The participants consist of 1 Tele Account Manager, 1 Senior Business Consultant and 1 Marketing and Communication person.

Note that **because of the small number of participants from Infoman, we did not use the results of this questionnaire for analysis** (Sects. 6.2.1 and 6.2.2).

6 Data Analysis and Results

In this chapter, we first describe the method of analysing the empirical data at hand (Sect. 6.1) and then present the results of our analysis (Sect. 6.2). In the results section, we also provide short summaries and discussions at a detailed level. An overall summary of the work presented in this deliverable is given in Sect. 7.1.

6.1 Data Analysis and Development of Categories

We analysed the qualitative data (reflection diaries, interviews and focus groups) for all below-described analyses. The quantitative data (reflection questionnaires) were used only to test the underlying assumptions (Sects. 6.1.1 and 6.1.2, results in Sects. 6.2.1 and 6.2.2).

6.1.1 Assumption: People reflect upon their work.

The MIRROR proposal and research direction of this workpackage (WP4) on learning by reflection is heavily based on the assumption, that people reflect upon their work and learn from such reflections. We look for supportive evidence for this assumption.

We give this evidence in the form of reflection stories, i.e. real concrete stories about everyday work situations of user study participants in which reflection happens, and direct quotes from user study participants.

Furthermore, we also support this assumption with a descriptive analysis of the reflection questionnaires. We analysed the questionnaire results per testbed, i.e. can give indications of whether target users at NBN, Regola and RNHA consider learning by reflection as part of their work. The assumption that people reflect upon their work, individually, is targeted in the reflection questionnaire in the first fourteen questions (MIRROR 2010b, Part B, p45). For RNHA, we considered the first five and last three questions in RNHA's version of the reflection questionnaire (see Appendix E, p.3). These questions specifically concern individual reflection. They measure to which degree target users agree that they reflect, individually, upon their work. Inverse scaled items were reversed for the analysis so that higher values correspond to higher individual reflection. For each testbed we confirmed that all questions measure the same underlying concept by using Cronbach's Alpha to test for internal consistency among the answers.

6.1.2 Assumption: People learn by observing others at work

The MIRROR proposal and research direction of this workpackage (WP4) on learning by observation is also based on the assumption, that learn by observation. We look for supportive evidence for this assumption.

We give this evidence in the form of reflection stories, i.e. real concrete stories about everyday work situations of user study participants in which reflection happens, and direct quotes from user study participants.

Furthermore, we also support this assumption with a descriptive analysis of the reflection questionnaires. We analysed the questionnaire results per testbed, i.e. can give indications of whether target users at NBN, Regola and RNHA consider learning by observation as part of their work. The assumption that target users in testbeds learn by observation, is targeted in the reflection questionnaire in question 25 (MIRROR 2010b, Part B, p46). In RNHA's version of the reflection questionnaire, no question concerning learning by observation was included, as an effort was made to keep this questionnaire very short and questions of general interest for different workpackages had to be included.

6.1.3 When and How Does Individual Reflection Occur at Work? – Reflection Sessions

Categories

We identified characteristics of reflection sessions, where by “reflection session” we understand an occurrence of user study participants having learned from their own experiences (as defined in Sect. 2.1.3)

Based on our data, we organized characteristics into sets of characteristics and developed identifiable categories for characteristics. To clarify the **terminology**:

- **Sets of characteristics:** “Characteristics of a Reflection Situation” is a set of characteristics. In this set, we collect all characteristics of the reflection situation, as opposed to characteristics of the content of reflection or the outcome of reflection.
- **Characteristics:** “Where, when” or “With whom” are characteristics. The first pulls together the time and location dimension, the second describes the social dimension. Both these characteristics belong to the set that describes the reflection situation itself.
- **Category:** We have defined categories, i.e. prescribed values, for each characteristic. For the “Where, when” characteristic, we have decided to differentiate only between “At Work” and “Outside Work” (and not, for instance, between exact times and places).

Characteristics of a Reflection Situation

- **At Work, Outside Work** (Where, when)
- **Individual, Supervised, Collaborative** (With whom).

Content Characteristics

- **Single Experience, Set of Experiences**
- **Activity, Interaction with Colleagues, Interaction with Patient or Client, Own Reaction** (Topics of Reflection and Observation)
These categories provide us with a non-domain-specific way to categorise the topics of (reflective) learning. The category “Activity” captures all topics that concern domain knowledge and self-organisation skills. The category “Interaction with Colleagues” captures all topics that concern social skills among colleagues. The category “Interaction with Patient or Client” captures all topics that concern both social skill and domain knowledge. For instance, when interacting with residents at a care home, or patients at a stroke unit, their behaviour is sometimes due to their medical situation (dementia, difficult personal situation). The category “Own Reaction” captures where the learner reflects on her own, for instance emotional or cognitive, reaction.
- **Individual Experience, Vicarious Experience, Shared Experience.** (Ownership of Experience)

Outcome Characteristics

- **Individual Learning, Organisational Learning** (Who learns).
While we originally intended to differentiate between more informal learning on a team level (where members of a team learn in a collaborative way and similar things), and the more formal learning on an organisational level (where the organisation learns in the sense that the actually prescribed processes change), we found that the empirical data we had did not let us clearly differentiate between these two cases. At Infoman and RNHA the borders between “team” and “management” seem to be very fuzzy at times, and at NBN significant portions of work processes are prescribed, and if a work process does not work, then the prescribed workflow needs to / is changed.

- Individual, Team, Organisational Scope** (Scope of Reflection)
 The categories describing the scope of reflection differentiate between which actors must ideally learn and change to take effect in the real world. If the learner herself needs to change her work processes / improve her competencies, then the scope is “Individual”. If a team needs to change its way of interaction or everyone in the team needs to change their work processes for the change to be effective, etc., then the scope is “Team”. If the organisation should change the prescribed work processes, then the scope is “Organisational”. Note that the scope is not equivalent to “who learns”. For instance, a learner may gain insights why something systematically goes wrong in her organisation, but does not share this.

Note that we included categories that do not directly concern individual learning and reflection in our categorisation scheme above. However, this allows us first to distinguish reflection sessions that we are not concerned with in WP4, and second to make visible transitions and interrelations between individual learning and reflection, and collaborative reflection and organisational learning.

Process of Developing the Categories

The above **sets of characteristics were developed iteratively** based on empirical data and on existing theory. From the **empirical data**, we collected short statements that describe reflection situations. From **Boud’s model** (see Figure 1) we re-used the notion that relevant elements to describe an occurrence of learning by reflection are the experience on which is reflected (captured in “Content Characteristics” categories), the reflective process, and the outcome (captured in “Outcome Characteristics” categories). The reflective process however is an internal cognitive process, and we hesitate to overinterpret single statements in our empirical data basis. We therefore replaced the category of “Reflective Process” with “Reflection Situation” (captured in “Characteristics of the Reflection Situation”).

In a second step, we identified the **categories** that let us cluster specific examples. Again, we used the **empirical data** on the one hand, and theoretical considerations on the other, this time based on the **characteristics of Reflection Sessions** that has emerged within the project (see Sect. 2.1.3 above).

Relation to Reflection Sessions as defined in Sect. 2.1.3

Dimension of Reflection Session as defined in Sect. 2.1.3	Set of characteristics / Characteristic / Category used in analysis in this deliverable	Explanation
Objective	Scope of Reflection	We preferred to call it scope instead of objective, since the evident reflection situations in the empirical data do not always point to a consciously set goal.
Content	Content Characteristics	
Process	With whom [reflection is done]	
Outcomes	Who learns	

Support	Not included	This is analysed in a separate section (see Sects. 6.1.5 and 6.2.5 below) when looking for answers to “Research Question 2 – Is individual reflection currently aided by tools?”
Timing	Where/when [reflection occurs]	Additionally, we use a separate section (see Sects. 6.1.4 and 6.2.4) to investigate triggers for reflection

6.1.4 Triggers for Reflection

Little concrete knowledge about what actually makes knowledge workers reflect is currently available both in literature and in practice, while at the same time this knowledge is crucial in devising technological support for learning by reflection.

To clarify the terminology, we point out that by trigger we mean what actually puts in motion the internal reflective process. This is different from differentiating between “small, individual, spontaneous” and “scheduled, elaborately organized and facilitated” reflection sessions (quotes are taken from the Sect. 2.1.3 about reflection sessions). A reflection session can be consciously started, and within such a session the occurrence of actual reflection by the participants can be facilitated. The internal reflection process is triggered by “something” that puts the mind to work, and one of our research goals is to understand what precisely it is.

From a theoretical viewpoint, we assume that what triggers reflection is a “discrepancy between expectations and the current experience” (see Sect. 2.1.1). For practical purposes, we would like to be able to differentiate between different kinds of triggers. We therefore developed the following categories, based on the given empirical data:

- **Different from Baseline:** A single experience (or a set of experiences) deviates from what the learner has explicitly expected, or deviates from a given norm or best practice.
- **Emotion** (Surprise, Hurt, etc.): A single experience (or a set of experiences) causes an emotional reaction in the learner.
- **Information Input:** Some information is received by the learner that is not easy to integrate with past or future experiences.
- **Feedback from / Reaction of Stakeholders:** Stakeholders may be customers, patients, colleagues, superiors, other professionals with which the learner interacts at work. The feedback may be very direct, such as feedback on a sales conversation from a present team member, or the reaction of the stakeholder may not conform to the learner’s goal, such as to make the resident of a care home happy and content.

Note that the above categories are not necessarily mutually exclusive, for instance when the learner is disappointed because an expectation has not been met, or hurt by feedback from a stakeholder.

6.1.5 Existing Support for Reflection

In this analysis, our aim is to find answers to “Research Question 2 – Is individual reflection currently aided by tools?”

During the analysis of all available data of the user studies conducted at Infoman, NBN and RNHA, we found that tools that directly support reflection currently do not exist. On the other hand, we do find **data** or **data sets**, which are created during work, and **IT tools**, which are

used during work, as well as **reflective practices**. Note that we were lax in interpreting “IT tools”, and included also all tools such as paper-based notes, that could equally well be digitalised. All these can serve as starting point for the development of further reflection apps of MIRROR.

Due to the close interrelationship between tools and the data they access, display and manipulate, we decided not to differentiate between tools and data at this stage. Thus, we look at tools and data on the one hand, and reflective practices on the other.

Tools and data can be divided into:

- **IT Tools keeping customer/patient information** (e.g. patients curve, general customer information including project information)
- **IT Tools for knowledge sharing with colleagues** (e.g. sharing experiences of patient handling, sharing of best practices with customers)
- **IT Tools keeping personal/individual information** (e.g. personal notes for preparing meetings with customers)

The reflective practices are categorized as follows:

- **Scheduled reflective practices** (e.g. regular meetings)
- **Unscheduled reflective practices** (e.g. spontaneous team meetings after a customer meeting)
- **Individual reflective practices:** (e.g. keeping individual notes about)

Reflective practices and the corresponding categorization can also be found in the section about Reflection Sessions (Sect. 6.2.3).

6.1.6 Potential Support for Reflection

In this analysis, our aim is to find answers to “Research Question 3 – Which kind of technological support could be used to support reflective learning at work?”

We summarize our findings along the structure of the “Technology Support for Learning by Reflection at Work” focus groups (see Sect. 4.1.4 and Appendix A). Additionally, we identified general **barriers or constraints** that should be considered when designing reflection Apps, and **explicit App ideas** that came up from the user study participants.

- **Photos, videos and other data that capture the externally observable experience:** Which kind of data e.g. photos, videos or other objective data could be helpful to remind people of past situations or experiences? Which content should be available within the data?
- **Physiological data:** How could own physiological information support the learner? Which kind of physiological data would be helpful for learners to trigger reflection?
- **Mood:** Could the tracking of mood help learners reflect about their work? Could the consciousness of mood help learners to reflect about their work and to learn from this?
- **Strategic development:** Do learners have a strategy for their professional development? Could a sophisticated presentation of personal status in terms of strategy further individual reflection on progress?
- **Barriers or constraints:** Which barriers or constraints have to be considered within the different application partners? What are the barriers or constraints, which have to be overcome, before a reflection app or tool would be used?

- **Explicit App ideas:** What are prerequisites that target users would use reflection Apps? Which Apps would target users like to support them at work and with work-related reflection?

6.2 Results

This section is organised along the assumptions and research questions that we target in this deliverable. In each sub-section, we then proceed with a per-testbed analysis.

6.2.1 Assumption: People reflect upon their work.

Infoman

At Infoman, we find the following selected reflection stories as examples of how people reflect at work:

“At an internal showcase presentation, I noticed that the presentation was very complex in that there were a lot of windows, a lot of steps to do things, etc. In preparation for the CeBit, I asked myself what would happen if one reduced such presentations significantly when embedding them in the sales process. At the CeBit I plan to pay attention in particular to whether potential customers prefer being shown a system or being listened to when talking about their requirements and needs.”
(Summary of entry in Reflection Diary)

“The approach initially chosen for a research project, one and a half year before the project starts, is not necessarily helpful once the project starts. If we notice that this doesn’t make sense for us or our partners, then we have to do something else.”
(Interview)

“One day I sat down – independent from any concrete trigger – and looked at the projects I had done. I mapped them onto our process map and tried to see which parts I have covered with my projects, where have I collected experience? What is missing? Doing this, I have learned again a lot, realized what I had achieved so far [...] and then I could say concretely that on the following three issues I really want to work on”
(Interview)

NBN

At NBN, we find the following selected reflection stories as examples of how people reflect at work:

“We had a patient coming in with a light stroke, but who developed towards a bad one, there we consider every day why this is so, have we overlooked something, every day: why did he come here, what is the most probable cause, what is the right therapy. There we re-consider the therapy each day, daily during the ward round.” (Interview)

“We had a patient who was cerebrally dead. His cardiovascular system was stable, and so we could keep him alive. Therefore organ donation could be talked about with his relatives. The patient donated two organs. The situation was wearing, because this is of course emotionally stressful, also talking with the relatives. [...] Between the talks and afterwards I read a lot about diagnosis of cerebral death.” (Interview, slightly summarized)

The participants did a simulation of reanimation. This was video-recorded from three perspectives. *“We have observed others and then ourselves. Also in order to compare how I felt with how it looks. I had thought during the reanimation that I was very slow,*

and then I realized that I was nearly too fast. [...] The perception was very different, this has confirmed me in not needing to become even faster." (Interview)

"In the morning, I told a physician that the plan we were following was wrong. By lunchtime, I still had not gotten feedback. I was very annoyed, because this was in his responsibility and it made me lose time in my duties. Nevertheless, I pointed this out to the physician once more, in a friendly way. The physician apologized for forgetting about this, and changed the plan. [...] I have learned that every person reacts individually, and sometimes the simple solution to a problem is baffling." (Reflection Diary)

Some years ago, a therapist had many patients with the same diagnosis. *"I noticed that they were doing well while being in the therapy session, but this success was not sustained outside the therapy sessions. Therefore I organized to go to a training seminar on that topic. There I did not learn anything in particular, but was confirmed that therapy success is very difficult to achieve in such cases, and I felt less under pressure for not achieving great advances with these patients."* (Focus group)

The evidence from qualitative data that learning by reflection happens is supported by the results of the reflection questionnaire.

At NBN, answers to questions regarding individual reflection show a good internal consistency (Cronbach's Alpha = .854), which is high enough to aggregate these questions. The resulting value represents the agreement of the participants about the value and the performance of individual reflection at work. The ratings go from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree):

Figure 2: Distribution of agreement with the statement "I reflect upon my work, individually" at NBN.

The person with the smallest agreement had a mean value of 2.43 of agreement, and the person with the strongest agreement had a mean value of 5 of agreement with the statement "I reflect upon my work, individually".

Regola

At Regola, we also find that learning by reflection happens at work, although here we can give only the answers to the reflection questionnaire as support.

At Regola, answers to questions regarding individual reflection show a good internal consistency (Cronbach's Alpha = .673), which is high enough to aggregate these questions. The resulting value represents the agreement of the participants about the value and the performance of individual reflection at work. The ratings go from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree):

Figure 3: Distribution of agreement with the statement "I reflect upon my work, individually" at Regola.

The person with the smallest agreement had a mean value of 2.86 of agreement, and the person with the strongest agreement had a mean value of 4.29 of agreement with the statement "I reflect upon my work, individually".

RNHA

At RNHA, we find the following selected reflection stories as examples of how people reflect at work:

"On a certain day during handover in the staff there was an issue brought up by the housekeeping staff to please tidy up the rooms & empty the commodes & flush the toilets when all care is given to the resident and when they walk out of the rooms. [...] Another staff then asked that should they always go behind every resident to check they have used the toilet. This made a bit of issue, the thing was simple, 'just flush the toilet'. But things went bad, the way the staff grasped the message was wrong. Anyway the issue was solved later. [...] I think that communication] should be very effective so as everyone understands one thing and takes it serious rather than being negative and making a joke out of it." (Reflection Diary)

"An elderly patient was at end stage of life but did not want to go to hospital for his chest infection. The family disagreed. [I learned/decided] to get the written consent from the service user in advance to demonstrate they did not want to go to hospital."
(Reflection Diary)

"I still remember very clearly how shocked I was when I started working as a care assistant. All of a sudden I was surrounded by people who were disabled one way or the other, who were totally or almost totally dependent on others. A situation like that must shock anyone who faces it. I realized how fragile human life is, how precious it is and how fortunate I am to be able to help them instead of being one of them."
(Reflection Diary)

"[...] when one resident was sort of bending down with the carpets, because the carpets are quite patchy they look like something is on the floor and one was bending down, and the other resident she thought that that maybe he was trying to take her shoes of or something and she was telling him to get away and being quite verbal with him. [... afterwards ...] I thought maybe if they'd done something with the carpets then it wouldn't, the situation wouldn't happen. If they changed like the colors instead of making it look like there is toys or whatever on the floor." (Interview)

The evidence from qualitative data that learning by reflection happens is supported by the results of the reflection questionnaire.

At RNHA, answers to questions regarding individual reflection show a good internal consistency (Cronbach's Alpha = .772), which is high enough to aggregate these questions. The resulting value represents the agreement of the participants about the value and the performance of individual reflection at work. The ratings go from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree):

Figure 4: Distribution of agreement with the statement "I reflect upon my work, individually" at RNHA.

The person with the smallest agreement had a mean value of 3 of agreement, and the person with the strongest agreement had a mean value of 5 of agreement with the statement "I reflect upon my work, individually".

6.2.2 Assumption: People learn by observing others at work

Infoman

At Infoman we find the following evidence for learning by observation of others:

“At the new company, colleagues show a significantly calmer and less aggressive demeanour. [...Consequently I adapt my behaviour consciously], politeness alone demands that.” (Reflection Diary)

I watched an on-demand webcast of Microsoft. I was astonished how simple their argumentation was. [...] Personally, I will try to reduce such complexity in communication in the future. (Summary of entry in Reflection Diary)

“When we act as a team, we should act on the same approach. Hence there is this idea ‘What is this guy doing better than I am?’ which is not a comparison between people.” (Interview)

“Currently I often work along senior colleagues, such that I think I can learn more from them than vice versa, but feedback is also going in both directions.” (Interview)

“[I learn] from colleagues who have been here longer: style of speech, how to demo functionalities. From other sales people, the style of presentation. [...] It’s a continuous give and take.” (Interview)

NBN

At NBN we find the following evidence for learning by observation of others:

“The self-conception of medical practice in other hospitals” [is a topic for reflection]. (Interview)

“I am often scheduled to work with new nurses, they have a period of three to four weeks for vocational adjustment. When they are with me, they know they learn [...]” (Interview)

“I am often asked by younger colleagues, can you help me for a second, how should I lay this patient.” (Interview)

The above evidence is supported by the following answers to the observation question in the reflection question. The ratings go from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree):

Figure 5: Agreement with the statement "I often learn by observing others at work who do things differently from how I do them." at NBN

Regola

At Regola, we also find that learning by observation happens at work, although here we can give only the answers to the reflection questionnaire as support. These answers, however, indicate very strongly that learning by observation does occur. The ratings go from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree):

Figure 6: Agreement with the statement "I often learn by observing others at work who do things differently from how I do them." at Regola

RNHA

At RNHA we find the following evidence for learning by observation of others:

“As I am not trained to give care to her colostomy bag under UK law, I called the attention of my registered nurse. She showed me the proper way of care to stoma and colostomy bag.” (Reflection Diary)

“[...] when we had a new resident come in and I wasn't sure sort of how to like approach, so I asked like a senior just to go with me just for the first time just so I could get to know them.” (Interview)

“When you start as a care assistant you usually shadow somebody so you usually follow somebody around [...]” (Interview)

“Carer X forced client to dress in clothes he did not want to wear. The client retaliated, was resistive. [...]I felt guilty, reassured him and dressed him in the appropriate clothes. [...later on] I encouraged staff to listen to clients.” (Reflection Diary)

“Yeah I sometimes compare sort of my strengths and weaknesses to other members.”
The interviewed person continued to say that such a comparison was something done individually, and would be talked about only if it would directly benefit a client (e.g., if one carer gets along better with a particular client than another carer). (Interview)

6.2.3 When and How Does Individual Reflection Occur at Work? – Reflection Sessions

We provide evidence for the variety of reflection situations by filling the identified categories with specific instances. We proceed per testbed, with a list of examples for different categories and a short summary and discussion section.

6.2.3.1 Infoman

Characteristics of a Reflection Situation

At Work/Outside Work:

- Customer contact: Customer acquisition, sales calls, initial contact with potential customers, emails to customers, customers don't react, holding a training course, consulting meetings at customer site (At Work)
- Internal meetings: Regularly scheduled meetings like team meetings, a yearly kick-off or appraisal interviews, on-demand meetings, internal presentation of CRM, informal conversations among colleagues (At Work)
- Searching for information (At Work)
- Receiving information (At Work)
- Preparing for future work (At Work)
- Informal conversations among colleagues, e.g. in hotel after work, business travel (Outside Work)

Individual, Supervised, Collaborative

Since the examples for individual, supervised and collaborative reflection we found in the empirical data follows common sense, we do not provide a bullet point list here. By common sense, we mean that reflection happens individually when work is done alone, supervised between new employees and their mentor, and collaboratively together with the team in team activities such as meetings, conversations among colleagues. Occasionally, also individual reflection happens in such team activities, when learners reflect on the current situation but do not communicate their thoughts to the team.

Content Characteristics

Single Experience, Set of Experiences

- Extraordinary (difficult, or very successful) conversations with clients and potential clients, e.g. a telephone call where conversation partner was particularly impolite, extraordinary events during a training course, particularly good or bad reactions of customers (Single Experience)
- Reoccurring difficulties in conversations with (potential) clients, e.g., due to unfamiliarity with the topic, difficulties with argumentation, content is not understood by the client (Set of Experiences)
- Ongoing activities and interaction with clients (Single Experience, Set of Experiences).
- Overall strategy for customer acquisition / interaction with customers (Set of Experiences)
- Repeatedly similar own work experiences that are unsatisfactory, e.g. searching for information (Set of Experiences)

Activity, Interaction with Colleagues, Interaction with Patient or Client, Own Reaction

- Usage of Microsoft’s CRM system, Outlook Search, Microsoft Partner Portal (Activity)
- Searching for information (Activity)
- Receiving information (Activity)
- Preparing for future work (Activity)
- Difficult conversations with (potential) clients, e.g. due to unfamiliarity with topic, difficulties with argumentation, content is not understood by the client (Interaction with Client)
- Ongoing activities and interaction with customers (Interaction with Client).
- Overall strategy for customer acquisition (Interaction with Client)
- Conflict situation with colleagues, e.g. difficult assignment/distribution of responsibilities, discussions, conversations with superiors (Interaction with Colleague)

Individual Experience, Vicarious Experience, Shared Experience

- Usage of Microsoft’s CRM system, Outlook Search, Microsoft Partner Portal (Individual Experience, Shared Experience)
- Searching for information (Individual Experience)
- Receiving information (Individual Experience)
- Preparing for future work (Individual Experience , Shared Experience)
- Interaction with customers, e.g. by telephone or email, reading and writing emails, holding a training course (Individual Experience)
- On-site activities at customer (Vicarious Experience, Shared Experience)
- Internal meetings and conversations (Shared Experience)

Outcome Characteristics

Individual Learning, Organisational Learning

- Plan to prepare and write down often needed pieces of text and argumentation, e.g. for emails, for sales calls, etc. (Individual Learning)
- Plan to improve, or successful improvement of, communication, e.g. more proactively address colleagues, style of communication, e.g. use a simpler language (Individual Learning)
- Plan to pay particular attention to identified issue in the future, plan to collect more data and do further analysis on issue, e.g. whether customers prefer being shown features or being listened to (Individual Learning)

- Plan to organise own work differently, and to optimise own work, e.g., focus on specific goals, actively ask for feedback from management. (Individual Learning)
- Strategy for interaction with customer (Individual Learning, Organisational Learning)
- Systematically sharing presentation material (Organisational Learning)
- Developing new solutions/new approaches, e.g. in research-oriented projects (Individual Learning, Organisational Learning)
- Optimising strategies and processes of the company (Organisational Learning)

Individual, Team, Organisational Scope

We find that the scope of reflection is mostly individual, since the interviewed persons seem to have much freedom of choosing the way to work. Consequently, a solution can mostly be found by changing the own way of work, and organizational learning is mostly an added benefit, e.g., if best practices would be shared within the whole of Infoman this would be better, but if not, the single salesperson could still act according to his own insights. However, there are some topics like information exchange between colleagues that are reflected on at a team level, and very few that really concern the overall strategy and vision of Infoman that are reflected on an organizational level.

Summary / Discussion

Staff at Infoman mostly sees reflection as inherent part of their work. Individual and collaborative reflection seems to be very balanced, while supervised reflection seems to play a less important role.

Learning from observation is regarded as natural and integrated into work, as Infoman's employees very often work in teams. Although interview partners sometimes pointed out that they learn from more experienced colleagues, most of them stressed that learning from others is very much reciprocal. Interview partners also stressed that they did not compare themselves to their colleagues in a competitive manner, but in order to improve their own work practices.

Our empirical data mostly contains reflection situations at work, with the exception of business travel where staff reflects collaboratively with colleagues

We often find individual learning as the result of reflection, and organisational learning often seems to be connected to sharing individual knowledge, such as insights into better practice. This may be due to the fact that staff at Infoman has a lot of freedom to choose their way of working, and there seem to be very few prescribed practices. Organisational knowledge seems to reside in shared information.

6.2.3.2 NBN

Characteristics of a Reflection Situation

At Work/Outside Work:

- Meeting among colleagues: Regularly scheduled meetings like shift handover, appraisal interviews, ward rounds or case conferences, on-demand meetings like information meeting of worker's council, informal conversation among colleagues (At Work)
- Ongoing interaction with patients at work, e.g. during care, therapy or medical diagnosis/treatment, on the way between patients (At Work)
- Preparing for audit / external certification (At Work)
- Further education (At Work)

- Break (Outside Work)
- Keeping up to date with new (compliance) guidelines (Outside Work)
- Informal learning groups (physicians) (Outside Work)

Individual, Supervised, Collaborative

In the empirical data we studied, the differentiation between individual, supervised, and collaborative reflection seems to depend mostly on the content of reflection.

Where communication with colleagues, patients or relatives is concerned, reflection seems to happen individually. An exception is communication difficulties between different professional groups, or departments at NBN. Such difficulties seem to be reflected on both individually and collaboratively.

Where the content of reflection concerns the care for patients, we mostly find collaborative reflection with physicians, individual reflection for therapists up to the point where they feel they need advice of colleagues, and mostly collaborative reflection for nurses.

Content Characteristics

Single Experience, Set of Experiences

- Emotionally stressed by patient(s) situation / by demanding work (Single Experience, Set of Experiences)
- Unsatisfactory communication with colleague(s), e.g. Disagreement , conflict-solving conversation, bad atmosphere in conversation (Single Experience)
- Critical incident with patient, e.g. patient accidentally hurt himself, critical condition of patient (Single Experience)
- Care / treatment of patient, e.g. bedding, therapy, medical diagnosis and intervention (Single Experience, Set of Experiences)
- Communication with patients / relatives (Single Experience, Set of Experiences)
- Watching a work process implemented unsatisfactorily by someone else, e.g. by junior colleagues (Set of Experiences)
- Unsatisfactory work process, e.g. sheets for patient's schedule are changed daily, stressful work (Set of Experiences)

Activity, Interaction with Colleagues, Interaction with Patient or Client, Own Reaction

- Care / treatment of patients, e.g. bedding, fixating patients, therapy, medical intervention (Activity, Interaction with Patient)
- Unsatisfactory work process, e.g. sheets for patient's schedule are changed daily instead of less frequently (Activity)
- Organisation / style of own work (Activity)
- Watching a work process implemented unsatisfactorily by someone else, e.g. by junior colleagues (Activity)
- Communication with colleague(s), e.g. interdisciplinary communication, disagreements, conflicts, conflict-solving conversations or unresolved issues (Interaction with Colleagues)
- Communication with patients / relatives (Interaction with Patients or Clients)
- Emotionally stressed by patient(s) situation / by demanding work (Own Reaction)

Individual Experience, Vicarious Experience, Shared Experience

- Emotionally stressed by patient(s) situation / by demanding work (Individual Experience)
- Unsatisfactory communication with colleague(s) (Individual Experience, Vicarious Experience, Shared Experience)

- Watching a work process implemented unsatisfactorily by someone else, e.g. by junior colleagues (Vicarious Experience)
- Unsatisfactory work process, e.g. sheets for patient’s schedule are changed daily (Shared Experience)
- Unsatisfactory communication with colleague(s) (Individual Experience)
- Watching a work process implemented unsatisfactorily by someone else, e.g. by junior colleagues (Single Experience, Vicarious Experience)
- Unsatisfactory work process, e.g. sheets for patient’s schedule are changed daily (Shared Experience)

Outcome Characteristics

Individual Learning, Organisational Learning

- Continue work in similar style as up to now, e.g. after confirmation of its quality (Individual Learning)
- New perspective on own behaviour (Individual Learning)
- New perspective / insight on communication with colleagues (Individual Learning)
- Change care / treatment for patient (Individual Learning)
- Plan to separate work and private time more strictly (Individual Learning)
- Plan to improve organisation of own work, e.g. make sure to know everything before colleague has gone somewhere else (Individual Learning)
- Plan to improve on communication / style of communication, e.g. stay more professional and take statements less personally (Individual Learning)
- Try to give constructive feedback / instruction (Individual Learning)
- Plan to share newly gained knowledge (Individual Learning)
- Plan to try organisational changes, e.g. coordination of therapy and nursing at stroke unit (Individual Learning, Potential for Organisational Learning)
- Plan to change care / treatment systematically, e.g. fixating patients – but in areas where no work process/compliance with organisational guidelines exist / are necessary (Individual Learning, Potential for Organisational Learning)
- Unsatisfactory work process was successfully changed, or attempted to or planned to be changed, e.g. sheets for patient’s schedule are now changed weekly instead of daily (Individual Learning, Organisational Learning)
- Severe incidents (Organisational Learning)

Individual, Team, Organisational Scope

Where organizational learning occurred, we find the following typical process: The learning process starts with an individual knowledge worker identifying an unsatisfactory work process, and sometimes can identify possible solutions already. (Organisational Scope during Individual Reflection) In a second stage this is sometimes discussed in the team, e.g. to confirm that the work process is unsatisfactory for more than one person, to find solutions collectively (Organisational Scope in Collaborative Reflection). In a third stage, the responsible management level for implementing a change of work procedure is addressed. In some instances we only found evidence for potential organisational learning, which means that individuals did consider content of organisational scope, and plan to make organisational learning happen.

Summary / Discussion

Staff at NBN is strongly focused on reflection regarding care, therapy and medical diagnosis and treatment of patients. Regarding these topics, staff at NBN see reflection as inherent

part of their work, and therapists for instance mentioned explicitly being taught critical reasoning during education. Apart from medical knowledge concerning care, therapy and medical diagnosis and treatment, we also find examples for reflection on communication among colleagues, and communication with patients and often also their relatives. We find a lot of evidence for individual learning, both concerning medical know-how and communication.

Learning by observation seems to be closely associated with training or an initial period of work for a new colleague. Otherwise, staff at NBN seems to prefer directly asking for advice or feedback.

We find that whether reflection is done individually or collaboratively seems to fall together with the topic of reflection. We find many cases of collaborative reflection on medical know-how, and many cases of individual reflection on communication issues, except where these are linked to systematic, work-flow problems like interdisciplinary or inter-department communication.

Reflection seems to happen mostly at work, and we find indications that staff at NBN does not regard reflection outside work as desirable, even though we find some examples for that. On the other hand, especially physicians noted that they dedicate part of their spare time systematically to continued education.

We also find that where individual reflection targets an organisational scope, there seems to be a well-working process that starts at individual reflection, sometimes moves via collaborative reflection to confirm or discuss individual insights, and results in involving the management level which may lead to organisational learning. Indeed, we find several examples for successful organisational learning that has happened through this bottom-up process in the empirical data.

6.2.3.3 RNHA

Characteristics of a Reflection Situation

At Work/Outside Work:

- Conversations with colleagues or outside professionals such as social workers: At scheduled meetings like shift handovers, senior staff meetings; or lectures about (dementia) care; In supervision/with a mentor; Informal conversations with colleagues (At Work)
- Care of patients, e.g. serving food, transporting patients (At Work)
- Writing reports / documenting work (At Work)
- On the way to/from work (Outside Work)
- During breaks with colleagues (Outside Work)
- In the evening, alone or with family member (Outside Work)

Individual, Supervised, Collaborative

Like at NBN, the examples for individual, supervised and collaborative reflection we found in the empirical data follows common sense. Hence we do not provide a bullet point list here.

Content Characteristics

Single Experience, Conglomeration of Experience

- Conversations with colleagues: Conflict / conflict-solving conversations among colleagues (Single Experience)

- Difficult conversation with resident’s relatives, e.g., whether or not to take him to hospital at the end-of-life-stage (Single Experience)
- Resident’s condition, critical incident with resident such as patients getting bruised by a fall or (Single Experience)
- Difficult interaction with residents, mostly due to dementia/Alzheimer, e.g. aggressive behaviour, bad mood, strange actions (Single Experience, Conglomeration of Experience)

Activity, Interaction with Colleagues, Interaction with Patient or Client, Own Reaction

- Organization of work, work processes, e.g. who orders medication when (Activity)
- Care of Patient, e.g. making residents comfortable/happy, preventing / dealing with bed sore, regular hygiene, maintaining respectful relationship with residents, diet of resident (Activity, Interaction with Patient)
- Difficult interaction with residents, mostly due to dementia/Alzheimer, e.g. aggressive behaviour, bad mood, strange actions (Interaction with Patient)
- Style of communication among colleagues, e.g. gossiping, style of communication in / organisation of meetings (Interaction with Colleagues)
- Conflict among colleagues, disagreement about care/treatment (Interaction with Colleagues)

Individual Experience, Vicarious Experience, Shared Experience

- Difficult interaction with residents, mostly due to dementia/Alzheimer, e.g. aggressive behaviour, bad mood, strange actions (Individual Experience, Shared Experience)
- Watching an unsatisfactory implementation of work (Vicarious Experience)
- Conversations with / among colleagues: Conflict / conflict-solving conversations among colleagues, style of communication among colleagues (Vicarious Experience, Shared Experience)

Outcome Characteristics

Individual Learning, Organisational Learning

- Change of attitude / new perspective towards own life, e.g. vulnerability, ageing
- Change of own attitude to / style of work, e.g. react immediately to resident’s discomfort / needs, deal with own emotions / empathy with residents, attentive care, double-check some aspects of work (Individual Learning)
- New insight into informal learning, e.g. try different things (Individual Learning)
- Continue successful / good quality work, e.g. spend more time with a specific, or talk a lot with residents (Individual Learning)
- Plan to come to work better rested, e.g. not going out on days before workdays (Individual Learning)
- Plan to improve (style of) communication with colleagues, e.g. how to say no and mean it, conduct difficult conversations in a private space (Individual Learning, Team Learning)
- Change care of / style of interaction with residents, e.g. by involving a nurse or general practitioner in case medical problems are suspected, let residents rest (Individual Learning)
- New perspective / understanding of existing work processes and compliance guidelines, e.g. fire drill, necessity to document (Individual Learning)
- Plan to look for specific information (Individual Learning)
- New insight on systematic problems for residents, e.g. pattern of carpet (Individual Learning, Potential for Organisational Learning)

- Implement change of work organisation, e.g. breaks (Organisational Learning)

Individual, Team, Organisational Scope

In the empirical data we mostly find an individual scope of reflection. In those instances where organisational learning occurred, we found as process again (as with NBN) the way from individual insights (into what should change) during individual reflection with an organisational scope, through collaborative reflection with an organisational scope to an actual change. The process of changing an organisational process seems to be very informal.

Summary / Discussion

At RNHA, we do find evidence for reflection at work, but we do not find in the qualitative data (diaries, interviews) that reflection is part of the self-conception that staff at RNHA has of themselves and their work. Rather, staff often seems to take a pragmatic view of their work insofar as they do their work, and if they find something that they would like to change they either try it or leave it. This counters to some extent the result from the reflection questionnaire, where staff agreed to a large majority with the statement “I reflect upon my work”.

We find little explicit evidence for learning by observation, except for the training of new employees who seem typically to be paired with senior carers. However, as staff at RNHA often works together, especially in difficult situations with residents, and additionally seem very comfortable concerning asking senior colleagues for help, we can assume that learning by observation does play a significant role at RNHA.

We find evidence both for reflection at work, as well as outside work, e.g., on the way to or from work, in the evening, or during breaks with colleagues. We did not find a strong aversion towards thinking of work outside work.

Staff at RNHA seems to reflect a lot on single experiences, such as extraordinarily difficult interaction with residents (“challenging behaviour”), critical incidents with residents, or difficult conversations with colleagues or with residents’ relatives. We find that a lot of reflection circles around the care of residents, interaction with residents especially regarding challenging behaviour, and organisation of own or the team’s work processes. Hence, very often, reflection results in individual learning in the sense that each situation that has been dealt with adds to the experience of the single carer or nurse.

There seems to be quite an informal process from individual reflection on an organisational scope via collaborative reflection to the change of a work process, or change of environment. The reason could be that the care homes from which we have empirical data are rather small (and this is a typical setting for care homes within RNHA).

6.2.4 Triggers for Reflection

The following triggers work both in scheduled and un-scheduled reflection. We consider a scheduled reflection, such as supervision, a planned meeting etc. not as trigger for reflection, but as giving opportunity for reflection. In such a scheduled reflection situation, the internal reflective process in each person’s mind still needs to be set in motion.

Infoman

Different from baseline (expectation, norm, best practice, etc.):

- Trouble using software tools, e.g. CRM, MS Office, MS Partner Portal

- Usage of software tool differently than intended
- A work activity, e.g. finding information, writing emails, ... takes longer than necessary
- Norm of behaviour in new company is different than in old company
- Change of work style or setting company
- Colleagues change their behaviour
- Unexpected behaviour of colleague, such as work practice / style of communication etc. of respected colleague
- Unexpected reaction of customer, e.g. a customer that was expected to be difficult was very easy-going
- Own behaviour differs from a known rule of thumb, e.g. "always accept 'no' from a customer"
- Personal and company goals differ

Emotion (Surprise, Hurt, etc.)

- Surprisingly simple argumentation for complex content
- Surprisingly simple work process at new company
- Surprise at a decision
- Surprise / insecurity over a manager's assessment of a colleague
- Surprise / hurt at change of colleague's opinion / standing on a subject of discussion
- Perplexity, astonishment at behaviour of colleague
- Intuition, gut instinct

Information Input

- Sales argumentation of Microsoft is hard to understand/integrate with own understanding
- Interesting new information that is not integrated in own/company's work practice
- Too much information in too little time
- Not understanding presentation of "own" products
- New strategy of company, new information from management
- New information from customer that must be integrated with prior strategy/line of argumentation

Feedback from / Reaction of Stakeholders

- Customers are not interested in / don't understand products that are being promoted for sale or explained in a training
- No response from potential customers
- Customer reacts badly (emotionally) during interaction, e.g. seems frustrated, is impolite.
- Customers frequently put forward the same counter-argumentation
- Feedback from customers
- Feedback from colleagues

NBN

Different from baseline (expectation, norm, best practice, etc.):

- Colleagues don't interact with patients/relatives of patients as they should
- Feedback, given e.g. by colleagues, by video, that differs from self-image.
- Critical incident involving patient
 - Patient is hurt

- Diagnosis / treatment is especially difficult, treatment is not working as expected, treatment is working especially well, complications, rapid deterioration of patient's condition
- Compliance guidelines are unsatisfactory, i.e. deviant practices work better
- Change in work practices
- Own work practice has deviated from compliance guideline / best practice
- Atypical cases, extraordinary cases

Emotion (Surprise, Hurt, etc.)

- Dissatisfaction / irritation / anger about unsatisfactory work practice, meeting, conversation
- Stressed by / anger / frustration / hurt in conversation with patients/relatives of patients
- Irritation about having to take work to home
- Feel let down by colleague, irritated with colleague
- Empathy with patients / relatives' difficult situation
- Perplexity / astonishment about completely new and unexpected (difficult) situation

Information Input

- Cases that are new with respect to learner's experience
- New colleagues (nurses) come into team and bring in new knowledge

Feedback from / Reaction of Stakeholders

- Positive feedback / appreciation from colleagues
- Colleagues are disappointed about a decision
- Colleague is in very bad mood
- Reaction of / Feedback from patients, in forms of mood, of improving condition, direct feedback

RNHA

Different from baseline (expectation, norm, best practice, etc.):

- Poor condition of resident
- Problem amongst staff
- Critical incident involving patient, e.g., patient gets hurt
- Patient is unwell
- Work practice different to prior experience
- Dilemmas and trade-offs related to the ideals of care

Emotion (Surprise, Hurt, etc.)

- Frustration / anger about / stressed by / dissatisfaction about conversation with colleagues
- Anger about / dissatisfaction with work process, e.g. having to do other people's work, or with impractical arrangement of facility
- Dissatisfaction with a decision taken on resident's behalf
- Bad atmosphere in team / amongst staff
- Feel humiliated by behaviour of people present at residence
- Satisfaction with atmosphere in team
- Satisfaction / happiness with work
- Empathy with residents

- Challenged by situation / Insecurity about how to deal with a situation, e.g. don't know how to react to resident

Information Input

- New information about fire regulations, about resident safety measures

Feedback from / Reaction of Stakeholders

- Mood of residents, e.g. they are very happy, they feel isolated, they are impolite and in a bad mood, their mood changes abruptly
- Challenged by situation / Insecurity about how to deal with a situation, e.g. don't know how to react to resident
- Residents are dissatisfied with a work practice
- Input / requests from residents
- Feedback from colleagues

6.2.5 Existing Support for Reflection

When analysing the data collected during the user studies at various application partners, namely Infoman, NBN and RHNA, we found no existing software tools that directly support learning by reflection at work. On the other hand, we found a rich variety of data and data sets that are created during work, as well as IT tools that support work, and reflective practices. All of these are natural starting points for MIRROR Apps that will support learning by reflection and observation.

Existing data and data sets, work tools and reflective practices that we found at the testbeds have been integrated in the extended descriptions of Infoman. NBN and RNHA (Appendices B, C, D), to which we also refer below for a description of tools, data and practices.

6.2.5.1 Infoman

At Infoman there exist a lot of tools with corresponding data, which could be useful to support reflection. A detailed description of all these tools can be found in Appendix B, Sect. 5.

Tools keeping customer information:

- **Documentation of projects**

Tools for knowledge sharing with colleagues:

- **Documentation of experiences about customers**
- **Best practice range**
- **Exchange of information between employees**
- **SharePoint library for presentations in sales**
- **Staff user profile**

Tools keeping personal/individual information:

- **Individual documentation of customer questions**
- **Client acquisition via telephone**

The following reflective practices were found at Infoman:

Scheduled reflective practices

- **Full year target appointment:** for the preparation of the full year target appointments the full year target appointment sheets are used. Further input is provided during the

interview. The main goal of these meetings is to find out in which direction the employee wants to develop herself and what is necessary to reach this development. The appointment could also result in a rough development plan.

- **Team meetings:** there exist official protocols to transmit official information from the leader meetings or information about the development of Infoman to the employees. Information read between the lines has to be documented by the employees themselves.

Unscheduled reflective practices:

- **Spontaneous team-meetings:** team-meetings after visiting possible customers e.g. at dinner in the hotel or on the way home lead to a team-reflection about the day. Such discussions could lead (a) to individual reflection about one's own presentations but also (b) to thoughts of how the team should go on, modify or change its approach with the customer. Positive as well as negative customer meetings can be re-experienced together, to find solutions for problems or to find out, why the meeting was that good.

Individual reflective practices:

- **Sales presentations:** sales presentations are used as object of individual reflection.
- **Individual personal notes:** one interviewee mentioned his individual practice: he makes personal notes to summarize interesting topics, to question them and to get more information about the topic for himself.

6.2.5.2 NBN

At NBN there exist a lot of tools with corresponding data, which could be useful to support reflection.

Tools keeping patients information:

- **Medical record, i.e. the curve:** Medical records of patients keep all data about who did what and when with the patient. (see Appendix C, Sect.1.5).

Tools for knowledge sharing with colleagues:

- **Lysis protocol:** for each stroke patient, the assistant physician has to fill in this protocol, including reasoning, why or why not the patient was medicated with lysis. We actually consider this as one of the most direct examples of support for reflection that we found in the studied testbeds, since the protocol form requires physicians to reason, in hindsight, on their procedure (see Appendix C, Sect.1.5).
- **Protocols:** there exist a lot of protocols of different team meetings e.g. nurses ward meetings, therapists weekly “further training” meetings, ward meetings,... (see Appendix C, Sect. 1.4.2, 1.4.3)
- **Case presentations during physicians meeting:** once a week one assistant physician has to present an interesting, peculiar or rare case to the colleagues. (see Appendix C, Sect.1.5)
- **Protocols of conversations with relatives:** Conversations with relatives about the patients or about the treatment of patients are documented as well (see Appendix C, Sect.1.5)

Tools keeping personal/individual information:

- **Medical specialist training documentation:** assistant physicians document their patient cases themselves within a paper-based book to control their training (see Appendix C, Sect.1.5)

- **Evaluation sheet:** for an appraisal interview the interviewee has to fill in the evaluation sheet. Feedback and further information about their work is given during the interview (see Appendix C, Sect.1.5)

The following reflective practices were found at NBN:

Scheduled reflective practices:

- **Appraisal interviews:** in preparation of an appraisal interview, a nurse has to fill in an assessment questionnaire. This sheet will be discussed with the supervisor during the appraisal interview. In general these interviews cover further development and education, rotations between the wards, problems etc.
- **Feedback from the supervisor:** feedback from the supervisor has to be demanded by the assistant physicians themselves. Feedback covers current status of one's own specialist medical training or the executions of specific treatments etc.
- **Lysis protocol:** for each stroke patient there has to be written a lysis protocol: within this protocol an assistant physician has to argument, why or why not a patient got the lysis treatment.

Unscheduled reflective practices:

- **Support through experiences:** Support through experiences is based on interpersonal relations. An experienced person provides tips and tricks to newcomers and colleagues e.g. work-flows

6.2.5.3 RHNA

At RHNA there exist a lot of tools with corresponding data, which could be useful to support reflection. A detailed description of all these tools can be found in Appendix D Section D.3.2.1.

Tools keeping patients information:

- **Resident's documentation:** documentation of residents about their behaviour

Tools for knowledge sharing with colleagues:

- **Resident's notes:** notes made about residents, typically exists both on paper and on computer, also be called personal care records
- **Hand over notes:** notes about residents to give over to the next shift.
- **Daily Workplan**

Tools keeping personal/individual information:

- **Personal Diary or Personal Cards**

The following reflective practices were found at RNHA:

Scheduled reflective practices:

- **Supervision:** nurses and carers reflect with a supervisor about their job

Individual reflective practices:

- **Personal diary entries:** nurse goes back and looks at what she has written to see her improvement over time

6.2.6 Potential Support for Reflection

Within this section we describe which technical support target users could imagine using for learning by reflection and observation. We summarise target user statements per testbeds, along the topical clusters defined above (Sect. 6.1.6).

Note that only at NBN focus groups on “Technology Support for Learning by Reflection at Work” were carried out. These focus groups are specifically targeted towards potential support for reflection. Three such focus groups, one each for nurses, therapists and physicians, were carried out. For Infoman and RNHA, we only had the diaries and interviews from which to extract fitting information. These research tools, however, were not specifically designed to elicit such more creative, design-oriented information, and information below is therefore more scarce for Infoman and RNHA than for NBN.

In all three testbeds, time is a major constraint. All participants of the user studies mentioned that time is critical, and that they could not do something additional at work. All tools have to be practical, easy to use, easy integrable into the current work practices and must not be time-consuming.

6.2.6.1 Infoman

Photos, videos and other data that capture the externally observable experience

User study participants could imagine using video recordings of customer meetings as a data basis for reflection. Such video-recorded meetings could then be re-evaluated within a workshop, e.g., when and why the work was constructive, when and why a situation became too emotional (positive as well as negative), or when and how a relation to a customer was built up. This could help to find out how dealing with customers could be more successful. Additionally, this would be an opportunity to observe colleagues when doing their work, and learn from them.

Barriers and Constraints

One major concern for user study participants was how relevant data would get into a Mirror reflection App. Target users did not want to insert the same information into multiple systems, and there is already one system at Infoman, the Microsoft CRM tool, that contains a lot of information relevant for staff at Infoman. Additionally, it is important that the data is constantly used, in the sense of being kept up to date, which again is only possible in one “main” system.

Explicit App Ideas

Sales and consultants of Infoman stated that tools, which support reflection during work, should encompass the following characteristics:

- Tools should capture and integrate data automatically in the system or app, because there is no time left to fill in necessary information or data manually.

Tools, which are useful to support reflective learning at Infoman are:

- **Customer-trend-analyses:** it is interesting to capture information of topics in which customers are interested in. Reflecting such information over time could lead to the recognition of customer trends and then be used by sales.

- **Multi-modal idea capture:** Automatic capturing of discussions and collecting notes after a meeting on e.g. the way home by car. It is interesting to reflect on these notes or to search these notes again.
- **Project progress tool:** Sales mention that is important to have a tool which presents the process and development of a project over time. The information about the project covers information of:
 - How did ratings over the project evolve?
 - How did personal moods change concerning the project?
 - How was the teamwork during the project?
- **Project and staff relations:** a tool which visualizes which colleague is involved in which project, what kind of tasks she has and which topics she is interested in.
- **„All-in-one“ information system:** it would be very useful to have one integrated IT system which stores information like project information, colleagues information, organizational information, etc. Such a system could also integrate data captured via voice recording or videos for example on the way home in a car. All content should be easily modifiable, searchable and can be positioned easily into the Infoman’s new portal. Due to the distributed workplaces of colleagues, community building tools should also be integrated within the system.
- **Sales support tool:** An App that supports the core job of a sales person. The major task is supported “on demand, mobile and flexible”. Automatically triggered questions or hints to support reflection are provided similar to “Could you have been more polite to the customer?”, “Could you have been more convincing about your product?”

6.2.6.2 NBN

Photos, videos and other data that capture the externally observable experience

The physicians participating at the user studies were of the opinion that learning by doing is very important to learn work processes where manual competencies are required, e.g. surgery. Simulation or repetition of such processes in a training setting would be very effective to train such competencies. Additionally, work flows, e.g. what to do when a helicopter arrives, are remembered better if repeated regularly. Thus photos would probably not be very helpful. However, videos taken from different perspectives about e.g. a patient’s treatment, about unusual cases, could be useful for physicians to (a) reflect on one’s own working processes and (b) to reflect together with a colleague or supervisor to get new input and to learn from past situations. To some degree, interesting videos are already available at YouTube, and seem to be watched by the physicians. One idea that came up during discussion was to combine such videos with multiple-choice questions. The questions in this instance would serve to trigger reflection about the content of the video, e.g., was the correct work flow implemented, what was missing, what were the mistakes in the video, etc. Additional relevant information for a situation is medical information about the patient.

Nurses could imagine that one photo with all necessary information, such about the situation, such as time, participating persons etc. serves as trigger for reflection. It would be important that the faces of the people are recognizable on the photo, and that the situation is in some way extraordinary and not a routine situation. Nurses stated that the capturing of “all-in-one” photos or videos within special situations is very difficult. Nurses also considered videos relevant, e.g. about discussions within the team, criticism meetings or unusual situations. Depending on the content, interaction within the team, own behaviour or general work processes would be analysed.

Therapists regarded photos as less useful than videos, since only videos capture workflows. Therapists think that photos of specific situations are not useful for their work at all. Furthermore they stated that they have not time to watch videos during work. For them videos can only help to learn general work-flows, but videos could not adapt on the fly to the patient's need, which is a major challenge of a therapist. However, therapists pointed out very strongly that they have to keep their work as flexible as possible and if necessary have to adapt their work at the patient on the fly. According to therapists, hand-written, short and precise notes still would work best for information exchange among colleagues, either other therapists or other professions like nurses and physicians.

Both physicians and nurses indicated that the installation of a fixed video recording system could lead to the feeling of being monitored. All user study participants fear that that taking photos or videos from patients is very time consuming. Additionally all patients captured on a photo or recorded by video would have to sign a consent form, which is more or less impossible at the stroke unit since this unit deals with emergencies.

Physiological data

Physicians were very sceptical of measuring their own physiological data, especially since it seemed unclear how they could/should act on the knowledge, e.g., that they were stressed. Physicians were very clear in their opinion that their tiredness or stress level is not allowed to interfere with, or even influence, their work. If patients are waiting for a treatment, the physicians have to treat them.

Nurses were more interested in physiological data. Data that was mentioned as interesting were stress levels, sleep habits, blood pressure, blood sugar, data from pedometers, calorie consumption and data about the cardiovascular system. Nurses could imagine using this to find out which situations they find stressful and how stress influences their bodies (e.g., sleep). They would see this in the spirit of “practice what you preach”, since they often give advice to stroke patients on how to lead a well-balanced life, e.g., eating, sleeping, stress habits.

Therapists could imagine capturing physiological data to find out one's own stress level at work. On the one hand they could try to learn from other colleagues who seem to deal better with stress situations. On the other hand, such data could be used to prove to management levels that their work is stressful, and to what degree. Therapists would not want to always capture physiological data, but would do this for a given time period, e.g., two weeks, and then analyse the data. Such data capture could be repeated, e.g., annually. However, one therapist completely disagreed and did not see the relevancy of capturing physiological data for learning purposes.

Mood

Physicians very clearly see that mood is not allowed to influence how they treat patients. It is important for their professionalism that they treat all patients in the same way: with professional distance, friendly, neutral and fair. From this they concluded, that reflecting on captured moods is not useful to them.

Nurses would be interested in the mood of a common, which could be the basis for a team reflection. Nurses could imagine that reflecting on (recordings of) their own mood could help them detect triggers for bad mood, like for instance criticism meetings, too much work and problems with the supervisor.

Therapists stated that they are always aware of their current mood. Therapists were very sceptical about capturing their mood; on the basis that mood gives a very direct feedback on

the work. For instance, if a therapist is exhausted at the end of the week, it was a hard week. If the workload was easier, they feel better when leaving for the week end.

All participants have the tendency to be sceptical regarding mood as a trigger for reflection, or as an entry point to more data about a situation. A general feeling seems to be (explicitly voiced by nurses and therapists) is, that people know their own mood anyway and don't need to record it.

Strategic Development

Physicians were very interested in support for strategic approach to learning. They could imagine for instance a strategic game in which the learner captures to what extent one has already completed the requirements for becoming a medical specialist. Depending on which requirements are fulfilled, the learner enters new levels in the game. However, they also felt that a checklist that captured own progress in the formal training program would do as well. Ideally, such an App could be used during work, such that physicians could quickly put a checkmark in the App on some procedure that they have just completed. Ideally, such an App is connected to knowledge resource to research in-depth details about a medical procedure, treatment, etc.

Nurses were less interested in the idea of strategically approaching continued learning at work, although they could imagine that such a strategic approach, maybe embedded in a game, could be useful during nurse training. However, they could well imagine using quiz games for learning / reinforcing know-how, e.g. about anatomy, about relevant legislation. Nurses could also imagine games for simulating work processes.

Therapists again were less interested in the idea of strategically approaching their continued learning at work. However, they could imagine to use games to (a) support therapists that are only frequently at the SU to get up to speed with SU-specific work-flows and (b) to train time management issues, such as who to treat first, and with which therapy if several acute patients are in the SU.

Barriers and Constraints

Furthermore we found that (i) there is no Internet access available at the stroke unit because currently the stroke unit is shielded as a whole (a WLAN project at the SU is in progress) and (ii) the availability of technical devices is not enough: e.g. there is only one PC for 5 nurses. Additionally the reliability of technical devices should be guaranteed.

Explicit App Ideas

Physicians, therapists and nurses at NBN stated that tools at NBN, which support reflection during work, have to encompass the following characteristics:

- tools help to find optimal solutions by providing relevant literature
- tools provide the possibility to reflect alone or within a team
- tools remember nurses about positive situations and events
- tools avoid negative stress

Electronic medical record:

- **Mobile devices for physicians:** Physicians stated that one iPad for each physician is useful to have all information about patients available anytime and anywhere in the SU.
- **Mobile devices for patients:** Physicians, nurses and therapists mentioned that having an iPhone or iPad at each patient's bed to insert all information on the fly is very

supportive. This reduces the workload of the nurses and is also be very practical for therapists and physicians to have all relevant data available at the patient.

- **Medical training planner:** Physicians want a specialist medical training planner like a checklist

Games and simulations:

- **Dialog training game:** Nurses mentioned computer games for educating relatives about the conditions of the patients, especially if a patient is fatally ill (e.g. metastases in a brain).
- **Work-flow training game:** Nurses stated that the training of work-flows can be done with a game similar to “Wer wird Millionär” including several levels.
- **Neurological Simulator:** Physicians suggested a simulator for neurological cases.
- **Patient’ treatment training:** There are two rooms separated by a mirror. Within one the simulation of a treatment of a neurological patient takes place, from the other room everything is captured with a video camera. During the debriefing all participants can reflect and discuss about the past treatment.

Information platforms:

- **Research information database:** Physicians stated that they need a tool or app, where (a) information about the current research topic could be inserted and (b) additional information belonging to the current research topic could be presented automatically (kind of recommender system)
- **Information exchange platform:** An information-platform to exchange data between physicians, nurses and therapists has to provide the following features:
 - **Information exchange:** Short concise notes about the patient’s assessment, short concise information about the current status of the patient, what is allowed to do (from the physicians) and what was already done with the patient (from the therapists and nurses).
 - **Interdisciplinary language of all participants** (physicians, nurses and therapists) has to be the same.
 - **Patient information platform:** Platform should cover all general information about the patient in short
 - **Work-flow plans:** For new colleagues, visualization and descriptions of work-flows short and concise, and the working-flexibility must be maintained.
- **Brainstorming rooms:** Physicians need small meeting rooms with flat screens to develop or discuss in teams of two or three people new ideas or thoughts
- **Best practices:** Best practices are hand-written notes, short, concise and reduced to the most important information. Preliminary information of therapists and nurses help to save time. Visualization of information about the patients from physicians to nurses or therapists would also save time. Additionally no questions have to be posed twice to the patient and the therapist could concentrate on the patient and on questions interesting for the physicians.

6.2.6.3 RNHA

Barriers and Constraints

We found no further constraints in the empirical data that we analysed. However, some additional constraints are described in Appendix D.

Explicit App Ideas

Nurses and carers at RNHA stated that tools especially have to support the exchange of information about residents among.

Tools which are useful to support reflective learning at RHNA are:

- **Mobile texting device:** a mobile device or phone for “texting” (easily inserting text), which can then be easily transferred onto the computers; instead of writing paper-based notes and then inserting them into the computer manually.
- **Resident event tool:** Tools help to record, remember and reconcile events about residents.
- **Magical Tool:** *“Something [...] that sees what I see maybe or something that can hear me or see what I'm doing all the time [...] use the data to just re-run it really, to see how I handled a situation. Then I could decide if and what I could do better next time maybe.”*
- **Knowledge Transfer Tool:** a senior nurse *“would like a tool to transfer her knowledge into the head of other staff”*.

7 Discussion

In this section, we first summarise the results of this deliverable from a theoretical viewpoint (Sect. 7.1), then discuss the implications of these results for the development of reflection Apps (Sect. 7.2), and describe our next steps in the upcoming Year 2 of the MIRROR project (Sect. 7.3).

7.1 Summary

As the per-testbed summaries in Sect. 6.2.3 are quite detailed, we focus in the summary here on validity and generalizability of results, and on our results concerning triggers for reflection. The per-testbed summaries in Sect. 6.2.3 and this section thus constitute the contribution that this deliverable makes to the advancement of theory on reflective learning.

Validity and Generalizability of Results

Most of the results in this deliverable concern target users at Infoman, NBN and RNHA. To a small degree we have delivered results on Regola based on a quantitative analysis of questionnaires.

For all testbeds, we must consider that it was probably the most motivated employees who participated in the user studies, as participation was voluntary. Although this may skew the results, we point out here that also learning by reflection must happen voluntarily, and we expect that also future reflection Apps will be first, and mostly, used by motivated employees in all testbeds. Thus we think it is justified to base the development of such Apps on the existing data.

Note that we do not necessarily seek generalizability with our concrete examples of reflection situations, but rather provide positive examples for reflection and learning by observation. Additionally, we seek to widen the circle of users in the following years in our design-research approach, such that the more mature the reflection Apps become, the more users will use it and give feedback on it. On the other hand, our categorisation schemes for reflection sessions (Sect. 6.1.3) and for triggers can of course be applied to other workplace settings (Sect. 6.1.4).

Learning by Reflection

We have given evidence that learning by reflection does occur in all investigated testbeds (Sect. 6.2.1). Furthermore, we have provided a plethora of examples where and when reflection can occur (Sect. 6.2.3), as well as a clear categorisation scheme with identifiable categories (Sect. 6.1.3) and a categorisation of concrete triggers for reflection (Sect. 6.1.4)

Learning by Observation

We have given evidence that learning by observation does occur in all investigated testbeds (Sect. 6.2.2). Learning by observation is sometimes associated with training or an initial period of work, and replaced with directly asking colleagues.

Triggers

One of the major result of this user study with respect to ongoing and future advancement of reflection theory, is the development of categories for such triggers based on empirical data that we provide within this deliverable.

In the category “**Different from Baseline**” we find examples where the learner has expectations towards own work and behaviour and realises these are not met, where a

significant change in the work environment takes place, where other people act in an unexpected manner, where there is a discrepancy between some norm or best practice and the actual practice. We also count critical incidents, where in the case of NBN and RNHA the life / welfare of patients and residents is at stake, and atypical medical cases at NBN in this category.

Emotions range from sheer perplexity and surprise, towards dissatisfaction, anger or frustration with an experienced situation. On the more positive side we also find satisfaction and relief as triggers for reflection, and in the health care testbeds NBN and RNHA also empathy with patients and residents as triggers. Note that we also find stronger emotions at NBN and RNHA than at Infoman.

Information Input as trigger is prevalent at Infoman, where staff seeks to integrate new knowledge with sales or consulting strategies, own or shared work practices, and company strategies for own business development. A few examples of new information triggering reflection are also found at NBN and RNHA. At NBN, we suspect that evolving medical knowledge frequently triggers reflection, but do not find this in the empirical data. However, we find that physicians in medical specialist training do start reflection and research when in contact with cases that challenge their current medical knowledge.

In the category “**Feedback from / Reaction of Stakeholders**”, we find examples for direct feedback from stakeholders to the learner, as well as examples where the reaction of the stakeholder clearly indicates that something went well or wrong. The latter case is very strongly seen in all testbeds. At Infoman, customers that don’t react or are not interested usually lead to reflection. At NBN, patients that do not get better during therapy, or don’t react to medical treatment trigger reflection, as well as patients or relatives who are dissatisfied. At RNHA, residents in a bad mood typically trigger reflection.

7.2 Implications

In this section, we focus on implications of the above described insights on the development of future reflection Apps. This is in line with a technical focus in the WP4 objectives in Year 2.

7.2.1 Constraints

For all participants in the user studies, time is critical. Reflection Apps should be easy and quick to use, and be well-integrated into the existing work-environment. We also interpret specifically the results of the focus groups at NBN (Sect. 6.2.6) as requirements on reflection Apps to give an immediate and clear benefit to the target users.

It will be a challenge to trade-off these constraints with what we see as one of the inherent properties of learning by reflection, namely that it takes time. We conclude from this, that **future reflection Apps must be integrated into the existing work practices**, for which the collected reflective practices (Sect. 6.2.5) will be a good starting point.

7.2.2 Emerging Ideas for Apps

Here, we sum up shortly the explicit ideas for Apps that we elicited from the empirical data, and direct feedback on App ideas that were presented to target users in the focus groups at NBN (see also Sect. 6.2.6).

In all testbeds we find the wish for tools (i) that support information collection, with a focus on capturing more data and integrating more data sources than current IT does and (ii) that provide data analytics functionality. Specific data analytics were mentioned at NBN and RNHA where the wish was to aggregate data per patient, and at RNHA additionally an

aggregation per staff person was desired. At Infoman, one of the three user study participants wished for explicit reflection support, e.g., by prompting users with questions that foster reflection. At NBN, user study participants additionally were interested in (i) learning material for work-flows such as work-flow training games or (interactive) visualisations of work-flows, (ii) training games or full-scale simulation trainings, e.g., for treatment, for conversation, (iii) tools that support strategic development during specialist medical training, potentially game-based, and (iv) tools that support collaborative discussions of cases.

7.2.3 The Roles of Tools in Reflection at Work

Relating back to Sect. 2.1.4, we find we will strongly need to “**consider tools that support the work process more broadly**, since tool use in day-to-day work and reflection may be closely intertwined and one may impact on the other” (citation from Sect. 2.1.4). This will give us the opportunity to use data that is already being collected, and the potential to “insert reflection” unobtrusively into everyday work tools, and maybe also sneak in reflective practices where so far none existed.

7.2.4 Content of reflection

In the analysis of the empirical data, we broadly categorised the topics of reflection into (i) activities, i.e. domain-specific know-how as well as self-organisation capabilities, (ii) interaction with colleagues, which requires mostly interpersonal skills, (iii) interaction with clients, patients or residents, which requires both interpersonal skills as well as domain knowledge and (iv) own reaction, which concerns intrapersonal skills.

The results of our study indicate that the development of **domain-specific knowledge and self-organisation capabilities**, as well as the **communication with clients, patients or residents** is more important to target users than the other two. We base this conclusion on the strong focus on interaction with clients we find at Infoman, and on the aggregated results from NBN and RNHA where the welfare of patients and residents is in the foreground. Following up on the indications of priorities for target users, as well as the above discussed constraints, we therefore plan to first **develop reflection Apps that are testbed-specific**, and hence domain-specific, instead of targeting generic reflection Apps for usage across all testbeds. This focus will give us the possibility to well integrate Apps into existing work environments, and to investigate closely, in a user-centered iterative design and development process, what target users need and actually use at work.

In the focus groups at NBN, physiological data and mood are regarded as not central by users. We interpret these results also from the aspect that learning by reflection only makes sense if the learner has the capability to act on the newly gained insights. At NBN, target users indicated that they don't feel able act upon the knowledge that their work causes them stress, emotional distress, impairs sleep quality etc. We plan, first, to relate these results closely with the results of an experiment involving physiological sensors at NBN (D3.1, Sect. 5). Second, we plan to further investigate, together with WP3, the open questions regarding the usage of physiological and mood data, which, from a WP4 perspective revolve around what can be learned from reflecting on such data, and identifying possible courses of actions on the gained insights.

7.3 Outlook

In the upcoming Year 2 of the MIRROR project, WP4 will start **progressing towards**

- “**Objective 4.2:** Design a user profile which contains an adequate summary of an individual’s work history”
- “**Objective 4.3:** Create individual reflection Apps that convert the user profile into a “usable” representation that supports individual reflection”
- “**Objective 4.4:** Create a platform where work practices and experiences can be shared within a community of practice”.

Initially, we will put a focus on specifying, together with selected MIRROR testbeds, testbed-specific Apps, as also indicated above. For these Apps, we will identify which experiences need to be captured in a user profile, and try to include knowledge about typical triggers to prompt users to reflect intelligently based on the content of experiences. We see the inclusion of sharing functionalities not as crucial in the upcoming year, and will include them only if they are at the core of specified reflection Apps, or necessary to trigger reflection (e.g., if shared data provides the baseline against which specific experiences are compared).

Technical research challenges will include

- Embedding support for reflection within the (technical and social) work environment of the target users
- Automatically identifying triggers for reflection

The latter is necessary in order to satisfy user requirements, as well as profit from the data that is already being collected at testbeds during work.

As a first step towards this goal, we will integrate our findings based on empirical data with the storyboards which are results from a user-centered design process. In particular, we plan to collaborate with WP7 on strategic, game-inspired Apps that cover the strategic approach to self-directed learning by reflection and observation, which seem suitable for physicians in specialist medical training at NBN. We also plan to collaborate with WP5 on dealing with challenging behaviour, at the interface of reflection and creative problem solving. Finally, we plan to collaborate closely with WP3 on the usage of physiological and mood data for reflection purposes, as already discussed above.

The direction of these objectives is more technical than WP4’s objective in Year 1, to gain a deeper understanding of reflection as it currently happens at work. Nevertheless, we will follow up on several **theoretical research questions** as well. We plan to collaborate in particular with WP6 and WP8 to investigate

- The co-dependencies between individual and collaborative reflection
- The bottom-up process which leads from individual and/or collaborative reflection to organisational learning

Where applicable, insights will flow into the development of reflection Apps that cater to learning needs at all levels, individual, team and organisational.

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Focus Group on “Technology Support for Learning by Reflection at Work”

This moderation field manual was developed in the scope of the MIRROR project. The below high-level description is in English and in line with the research instruments descriptions in MIRROR (2010b, Sect. 7). The rest of the moderation field manual is in German.

Description of Focus Groups on “Technology Support for Learning by Reflection at Work”

Purpose: The aim of focus groups is to discuss in groups the potential of technology for reflective support at work.

Research questions to be answered:

- Which kind of support (e.g., data visualization, modelling, scripting, prompting) could be used to support reflective learning at work?

Target group: MIRROR target group

Description: Focus groups are a research method, where different information triggers concerning a specific topic are put together, and a moderator guides the discussion group through the predefined content. The focus group is initiated to discuss with the participants the potential of technological support of reflection. The following four aspects are discussed in the “Technology Support for Learning by Reflection at Work” Focus Groups:

- Photos, videos and other data that capture the externally observable experience.
- Physiological data that capture the learner’s physiological response to an experience.
- Captured mood as an entry point for navigating through / analysing experiences.
- Strategic development of own competencies, inspired by games.

The discussed technologies follow emerging ideas within the MIRROR project. Additionally, they follow theory in that they consider which data could be captured about work experiences (first three items) and explore the potential of strategic serious games in addition to simulation and role playing games (which are explored in D7.1).

The moderation field manual for the “Technology Support for Learning by Reflection at Work” focus groups below is in German.

A. Leitfaden “Technologische Unterstützung für Lernen durch Reflexion im Arbeitsumfeld“

A.1 Dauer

Diskussionszeitraum: ca. 3 Stunden inkl. Pause

A.2 Begrüßung

Herzlich willkommen bei der Fokusgruppe, also einer Gruppendiskussion, zum Thema „Technologische Unterstützung für Lernen durch Reflexion im Arbeitsumfeld“.

A.2.1 Einverständniserklärung

MIRROR ist ein 4jähriges EU-Projekt das am 1. Juli 2010 begonnen hat. Wir wollen Technologie (Anwendungen am PC, auf mobilen Geräten, auf Hardware Sensoren) entwickeln um **Sie** beim Arbeiten und Lernen zu unterstützen. Speziell möchten wir Sie dabei unterstützen aus eigenen Erfahrungen, und aus den Erfahrungen anderer, zu lernen.

Vor Beginn der tatsächlichen Arbeit als Fokusgruppe möchten wir Sie um Ihr Einverständnis bitten, Zusammenfassungen dieser Diskussion sowie Artefakte die wir in der Gruppe erstellen Dritten in anonymisierter Form zugänglich zu machen. Artefakte sind z.B. Aufzeichnungen auf Flipcharts (wichtige Punkte in der Diskussion) oder verschiedene Skizzen und Diagramme.

Zusätzlich werden Fotos von der laufenden Gruppendiskussion und –interaktion gemacht, zu diesen Fotos werden wir im Anschluss an die Gruppendiskussion die Zustimmung der sichtbaren Personen einholen, und anderenfalls die Fotos sofort löschen. Fotos die wir behalten werden zu oben genanntem Zweck verwendet und können Dritten zur Verfügung gestellt werden.

InterviewConsent-NBN-deutsch austeilten

A.1.2 TeilnehmerInnenformular

Wir bitten Sie, dass jeder Teilnehmer und jede Teilnehmerin uns grundsätzliche persönliche Daten zur Verfügung stellt, die Alter, Stellenbeschreibung, Ausbildung und Arbeitserfahrung betreffen. Als Namen bitten wir Sie folgenden Code zu erstellen: erste Buchstabe des Geburtsorts, erster Buchstabe des eigenen Vornamens, erster Buchstabe des Vornamens der Mutter und der Geburtstag (also eine zweistellige Zahl). Es geht uns dabei darum, dass wir einzelne Aussagen zu einem späteren Zeitpunkt einzelnen Personen zuordnen können, über die wir ein grundlegendes demographisches Hintergrundwissen haben.

TeilnehmerInnen-Formular austeilten

A.3 Einstieg

A.3.1 Bekanntschaft mit Projekt

Uns würde zuerst einmal interessieren, wer von Ihnen schon Kontakt mit unserem laufenden Projekt gehabt hat, zum Beispiel an den Storyboards mitgearbeitet hat? An der Sensorstudie teilgenommen hat?

- Hat Ihnen das Spaß gemacht?
- Würden Sie sagen, dass Ihnen schon alleine "das" neue Einsichten vermittelt hat?

A.3.2 Bekanntschaft mit Technologie

Wir werden Ihnen im Lauf der Diskussion einige Anwendungen für Handys und Computer vorstellen.

- Wer von Ihnen besitzt eigentlich ein internet-fähiges Handy? Wer von Ihnen hat einen PC / Laptop daheim?
 - Ist das ein Mittel zum Zweck, oder macht das Benutzen Spaß?
 - Tun Sie sich schwer damit, wenn sich "dauernd" die Handys ändern?
 - Fragen Sie Ihre Kinder um Rat, oder andere „Experten“, oder macht es Ihnen Spaß das selber herauszufinden?

Reflexion

Mit Reflexion meinen wir "Über eigene Erfahrungen und Handlungen, und die von KollegInnen, nachzudenken und daraus zu lernen".

- Fallen Ihnen dazu Beispiele ein?
 - Wenn zu negativ: Gibt es etwas worauf Sie stolz sind? Man kann auch am Erfolg lernen.

Wenn Beispiele sich mit unseren Apps / Mock-Ups decken -> aufgreifen und ev. Reihenfolge ändern

A.4 Foto-App

„Reflexion basiert auf Erfahrungen. An die muss man sich natürlich erinnern können. Wir haben uns überlegt, dass man Erfahrungen zum Beispiel anhand von Fotos dokumentieren kann.“

- Können Sie sich vorstellen dass Ihnen Fotos von Arbeitssituationen helfen würden sich an interessante Situationen zu erinnern, damit Sie später dann über die Situation nachdenken und daraus lernen können?
 - Was müsste auf so einem Foto drauf sein?

2er bzw. 3er Gruppen bilden: Moderatorin verteilt Ausdrucke vom Foto-App Mock-Up

MIRROR Foto App

Notizen:

Patient war ruhig und ansprechbar aber trotzdem war er nicht bei vollem Bewusstsein.
Wichtig: Immer Puls und Blutdruckwerte messen...

Bild 1: Foto App

„Bitte schauen Sie zu zweit / zu dritt zusammen“.

„Wir haben uns einmal folgendes überlegt. Stellen Sie sich vor, Sie wären im Besitz von so einer Bilder-Geschichte aus Ihrem Arbeitsalltag. Lassen wir einmal außer Acht, wie Sie zu so einer Bilder-Geschichte gekommen sind. Diese Bilder-Geschichte ist technologisch so aufbereitet, dass Sie zu einzelnen Bildern zum Beispiel Notizen machen können, oder andere Daten anfügen können. Sie können der Zeit entlang nach vorwärts und rückwärts „blättern“.“

- Überlegen Sie bitte zu zweit/zu dritt, ob Ihnen eine solche Dokumentation einer interessanten Arbeitssituation helfen würde, sich an die Situation zu erinnern, und daraus zu lernen (z.B. Was sollte ich beim nächsten Mal anders machen, was sollte ich beim nächsten Mal wieder so machen?)
- Wie müsste diese App anders ausschauen, um hilfreich zu sein? Sie können gerne auf dem Papier herumzeichnen! Sie können auch überlegen ob Sie andere Daten anstatt Fotos lieber hätten!
- Wann (in Pausen, am Abend nach der Arbeit, vor der Arbeit, ...) und wo (daheim, im Stationszimmer) könnten Sie sich vorstellen so eine App zu verwenden?

Im Plenum

„Bitte erzählen Sie uns und sich gegenseitig kurz was Sie so diskutiert haben“

- Welche anderen Daten wären zu so einer "Bilder-Geschichte" interessant?
 - Audio? CT? Fieberkurve? Ihre eigenen Gefühle? Video?
- Was müsste auf solche Fotos drauf sein?

„Wir haben ja vorher die Frage außer Acht gelassen wie Sie zu so einer Bilder-Geschichte kommen. Wir hätten uns überlegt, dass Sie mit einem Fotohandy in der Tasche, z.B. Brusttasche, herumlaufen und ganz normal Ihre Arbeit machen. Das Fotohandy würde immer fotografieren, und wenn Sie finden, dass eine Situation interessant ist, drücken Sie einen Knopf. Das Handy würde dann die letzten, sagen wir 20Minuten, speichern. Alles andere wird immer verworfen.“

- Könnte das funktionieren? Würden Sie mit so einem Handy herumlaufen, und bei Bedarf auf den „Speichern“-Knopf drücken?

Wenn Bedenken zur Privacy kommen:

- Fallen Ihnen Möglichkeiten ein, was man machen könnte, um Fotos zu machen und trotzdem die Privatheit der beteiligten Personen zu wahren?
- Wäre es eine Möglichkeit, die Gesichter zu verwischen? Oder stilisierte Figuren daraus zu machen?

A.5 FitBit

Ich möchte die Diskussion an dieser Stelle nun in die Richtung von physiologischen Daten als Auslöser von Lernen von Erfahrungen lenken. Bis jetzt haben wir darüber diskutiert, Bilder als Anker zur Erinnerung und Ausgangspunkt zum Lernen aus Erfahrungen zu verwenden. Ebenfalls könnte man aber eigene körperliche Befindlichkeit, bzw. körperliche Aktivitäten als Auslöser verwenden um sich eigener Aktivitäten bewußt zu werden und im Anschluß Lernmöglichkeiten zu identifizieren.

Großes Bild von FitBit an Board hängen

Das FitBit ist ein kleines Gerät das man in der Brusttasche, am Handgelenk, am Gürtel, etc. tragen kann. Es kann dazu verwendet werden um am Tag Schritte zu zählen, verbrauchte Kalorien zu zählen, und in der Nacht zu messen wie oft man aufwacht aus dem Schlaf, und wie lange man schläft. Damit kann man die eigenen Fitness überwachen und herausfinden wie „gesund“ der eigene Schlaf ist.

<https://www.fitbit.com>

Bild 2: FitBit

Bild 3: Schlaf-Analyse

Bild 4: Aktivitäts-Analyse

- Wofür können Sie sich vorstellen das Fitbit zu verwenden?
 - Können Sie sich auch vorstellen, dass die Daten interessant sind wenn Sie das Fitbit während der Arbeit tragen?
- Könnten Sie sich vorstellen das Fitbit täglich bei Ihrer Arbeit zu tragen?

- Unter welchen Umständen würden Sie das Fitbit täglich bei Ihrer Arbeit tragen?

A.6 Pause

Nach dieser angeregten Diskussion schlage ich vor, wir machen eine kurze Pause.

A.7 Spiel / Strategie

Es geht in der heutigen Diskussion ja um Lernen aus Erfahrungen. Das kann durchaus auch strategisch angelegt sein, ähnlich wie bei Strategiespielen bei denen man alle möglichen „Erfahrungen“ sammeln, und Aufgaben lösen muss um im Spiel weiterzukommen.

- Wer von Ihnen spielt denn eigentlich hin und wieder Spiele?
 - Und am Handy / am Computer? (falls nur „normale“ Spiele kommen)

Es gibt einen Haufen verschiedene Spiele für Handys und Computer. Das Spiel das ich Ihnen jetzt zeige, gibt es für das iPhone und heißt Hospital Havoc. Man arbeitet da in einem Krankenhaus, und bekommt Punkte dafür dass man seine Arbeit tut.

Bitte probieren Sie das vielleicht einmal aus.

iPhone und iPad durchreichen, **Hospital Havoc** ausprobieren lassen.

- Finden Sie das als Spiel gut? Mögen Sie das?
- Können Sie sich vorstellen, dass so ein ähnliches Spiel (angepasst an Ihr Arbeitsumfeld – also man würde zum Beispiel Besprechungen haben, Abgaben, Telefonate, Publikationen probieren, Reviews machen, etc.) Sie an konkrete Arbeitssituationen erinnert, und Sie dazu anregt darüber nachzudenken?
 - Wie müsste das Spiel anders sein um das zu ermöglichen?
- Könnten Sie sich vorstellen, dass Sie Ihre Arbeitserfahrungen wie in so einem Spiel organisieren. Mit Levels, und „Punkten“ die Sie dafür bekommen?
 - Welche Erfahrungen würden sich dafür anbieten?

Bild 5: Hospital Havoc

<http://www.bitwisedesign.com/hospitalhavoc/purchase/ipsaf>

YouTube: <http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=uAH0LZxHxrQ&feature=related>

A.8 Moodmap-App

„Reflexion wird zum Beispiel durch Gefühle, positive und negative Stimmungen, ausgelöst. Darum ist eine Idee von uns, Stimmungen als Ausgangspunkte zu nehmen um sich an

Situationen zu erinnern, darüber nachzudenken und zu lernen. Ähnlich wie bei der App wo Fotos als Erinnerungsstütze verwendet werden um sich an bestimmte Situationen zu erinnern, könnte man das auch mit Stimmungen machen.“

- Sind Sie sich Ihrer Stimmungen meistens bewusst?
- Nützen Sie dieses Wissen bewusst?

„Wir haben uns überlegt, dass man Stimmungen auf folgende Art dokumentieren könnte. Ohne einer Stimmung ein bestimmtes Wort wie „fröhlich, beschwingt, enthusiastisch, bedrückt, ruhig“ zuzuteilen, kann man auf der Moodmap seine Stimmung zwischen hoher und niedriger Energie, und positiv und negativ, ausdrücken.“

iPeeper/KnowSe: iPhone App, iPad App, Web-App zum Aufzeichnen von Stimmungen herzeigen.

A3 Zettel mit erster Moodmap aufhängen.

Bild 6: MoodMap

Bild 7: iPeeper App mit MoodMap

- In welchen Situationen könnten Sie sich vorstellen, Ihre Stimmung so zu dokumentieren?
- Glauben Sie, dass Sie sich leicht tun, Ihre Stimmung in dieser MoodMap „auszudrücken“?
 - Stellen Sie sich Ihre jetzige Stimmung vor, und überlegen Sie, wo Sie sie in der MoodMap einordnen würden.

„Wie Fotos auch, könnte man Stimmungen dazu verwenden, um sich im Nachhinein, beim Zurück-Erinnern an eine Situation, leichter wieder in die Situation zurückzusetzen. Eine mögliche Visualisierung ist die folgende.“

2er bzw 3er Gruppen bilden: Moderatorin verteilt Ausdrucke von der MoodMap (Seite 2)

Bild 8: Alternative Darstellung der MoodMap

- Überlegen Sie bitte zu zweit/zu dritt, ob Ihnen eine solche Dokumentation einer interessanten Arbeitssituation helfen würde, sich an die Situation zu erinnern, und daraus zu lernen (was sollte ich beim nächsten Mal anders machen, was sollte ich beim nächsten Mal wieder so machen)?
- Wie müsste diese App anders ausschauen, um hilfreich zu sein? Sie können gerne auf dem Papier herumzeichnen! Sie können auch überlegen ob Sie andere Daten anstatt Fotos lieber hätten!
- Wann (in Pausen, am Abend nach der Arbeit, vor der Arbeit, ...) und wo (daheim, im Stationszimmer) könnten Sie sich vorstellen so eine App zu verwenden?
 - Würde Ihnen so eine Visualisierung dabei helfen, sich in eine Situation zurückzusetzen?
 - Würden Ihnen die Notizen dabei helfen?
 - Welche anderen Daten wären eventuell brauchbar?
 - Wie müsste die App anders ausschauen um hilfreicher zu sein?

Im Plenum

„Bitte erzählen Sie uns und sich gegenseitig kurz was Sie so diskutiert haben. Haben Sie die App „umdesignt“?“

- Welche anderen Daten würdet Ihr gerne an so einen „Stimmungseintrag“ anhängen?
 - Audio? Video? Notizen, Twitter, Blogs, Dokumente, Emails, Facebook, Xing, LinkedIn, physiologische Daten wie Puls, Körpertemperatur, etc?

„Eine unserer Ideen ist eine Art „Mood-Tag-Cloud“. Man würde also sehen in welchen Stimmungen man sich befunden hat, wie oft (je größer das Quadrat desto öfter), und man hätte beim Klicken auf ein Quadrat Zugriff auf Daten die man zu dem Zeitpunkt noch zur Verfügung gehabt hat. Diese Daten würden wenn möglich automatisch angehängt.“

A3 Zettel mit Mood-Tag-Cloud aufhängen

Bild 9: Mood-Tag-Cloud

- Könnten Sie sich vorstellen, so durch Ihre Daten (Notizen, Dokumente, Personen, etc.) zu navigieren?
 - Durch welche Daten vielleicht besonders?
- Könnten Sie sich vorstellen, dass Sie diese Darstellung alleine zum Nachdenken anregt? Zum Beispiel wenn das gelbe „fröhliche“ Eck besonders groß ist (oder klein)?

Falls noch Zeit ist, und es thematisch hereinpasst: A3-Zettel mit folgender Darstellung diskutieren

Bild 10: Activities und MoodMap

„In einer existierenden App, Moody Me, ist nun alles zusammen folgendermaßen gelöst“

iPhone App, iPad App, mit **Moody Me** herumgeben

Bild 11: Moody Me App

- Wenn Sie die Mock-Ups die wir vorher gemeinsam besprochen und weiterentwickelt haben mit dieser App vergleicht - was sind Unterschiede?
 - Liegt Ihnen diese Apps vielleicht eher? Warum?
 - Was würden Sie noch gerne in die Mock-Ups übernehmen?

A.9 Abschluß

Wenn Sie wählen könnten, und es alle diese Apps schon gäbe - welche würden Sie gerne ausprobieren wollen?

A.9.1 Organisatorisches

Damit sind wir am Ende dieser Gruppendiskussion. Wir bedanken uns sehr herzlich für Ihre Teilnahme, und hoffen dass wir in Zukunft Technologien entwickeln / anpassen können, so dass Sie sie auch verwenden wollen.

Wir hoffen, dass diese Diskussion auch für Sie interessant war, und würden Sie darum noch um Feedback bitten.

Abschlussfragebogen austellen

B. Description of work at Infoman

This document is meant to be a description of the work AS IS done at the Infoman AG (INFOMAN). The document is the result of joint work done by MIRROR partners active in user studies at INFOMAN (DFKI, RUB).

Version	Editor(s)	Affiliation	Content
1	Martin Degeling, Dennis Liedtke	RUB	Initial Structure and Content based on observation and interview study done by RUB
2	Angela Fessl	KC	Insights from KMRC Interviews

B.1 Infoman

The Infoman AG is a consulting company based in Stuttgart, Germany. Their key field of action is consulting small and medium enterprises (SME) of the manufacturing sector in using Customer Relationship Management (CRM) Software they adjust to the needs of the customer. Research was carried out at the INFOMAN site in Stuttgart, Germany and focused on the group of sales consultant which where, at this point, the planned target group of the MIRROR tools. Since the observations took place on two days an overview of a 'usual' workday was gathered but as a project based organization requires flexible adjustments of work to the demands of the customer's generalizations may be problematic. Also, several tasks that are not carried out on a regular basis, like a visit at a customer site or a business fair, could not be observed but were described by the staff.

B.1.1 Partners at the testbed

Partner	Research Step	Time	Methods applied
All	Initial workshop	September 2010	
RUB	Work analysis	March 2011	Observation: Ethnographic notes, observation scheme
RUB	Work description and collaborative reflection analysis	March 2011	Interview: Guidelines for job description, (collaborative) reflection
KMRC	Current situation of individual reflection	March 2011	Reflection Diary
KMRC	Current situation of individual and collaborative reflection	March 2011	Reflection Interview

B.2 Work environment and routines

There are five sales consultants working in Stuttgart, several more have offices overall the country and a smaller district office with consultants of other groups is based in Luzern.

The office in Stuttgart is spread over one complete floor of a shared office building. The floor has offices along a U-formed hallway where the entrance with the reception is in the middle. The sales consultants' offices are at one wing of the hallway next to marketing and human resource departments.

B.2.1 Sales Consultants

The aim of the work of the sales consultants is to acquire contracts with customers to buy services around the Customer Relation Management (CRM) Software. INFOMAN then adjusts and introduces it into the customers' organizations.

The sales consultants have assigned different regions to each consultant where they are responsible for interested customers. There are consultants that live at different larger cities around the country and work remote. Besides this, each consultant has an individual focus and advanced knowledge about different parts of their product, for example, if organizational changes or specific technical details or possibilities of the product are needed. It is known to the other consultants who has expert knowledge about what, so a regional active consultant may ask an expert of a specific field to join the acquiring process if his or her knowledge is needed.

Interaction with customers can be very time consuming. To get a better understanding of the customer and their organization the sales consultants communicate a lot preferably via telephone and in on-site visits. In addition, they send information and files via e-mail to customers. Every contact is afterwards documented in the internal INFOMAN CRM system.

The workday of a consultant at the headquarters is highly dependent on the status of the acquiring project he or she is working on. 2-3 days a week a sales consultant is at on-site visits at customers to present the products of INFOMAN. On the other days, the work at the headquarters is carried out during office hours 9 a.m. to 6 p.m., but the participants reported that they usually do work in the evening too, which does not require physical presence like answering e-mails, listening to web-casts etc.

Days when they are in the office are structured by meetings, spontaneous or planned, organized with a calendar tool. Time between meetings and on-site visits are filled with discussions with colleagues and contact to customers and potential customers by phone and e-mail.

At about 12 a.m., the sales consultants and their marketing colleagues go to lunch together.

B.3 Personas in the target group

See Tabel "Personas Infoman"

B.4 Interaction among staff

B.4.1 Scheduled meetings

There are several scheduled meetings which structure the workweek and are held in meeting rooms for the most part.

At the *monthly INFOMAN meetings*, all INFOMAN employees and the CEO are present. The meetings take an hour and typically two topics like highlights of projects are presented. The *monthly sales meetings* and *review meetings* may take longer than that. Sales consultants and their marketing colleagues participate in them. Review meetings usually take place a week after the occasion (e.g. a fair). Topics in these are personal view on the event and business opportunities which arouse from as well as reports about the employees' contacts with the potential customers afterwards. The meetings are organized by the team leader,

whose assistant writes minutes during the session into his/her laptop. These are shared via e-mail after being revised. Business consultants use sharepoint to save their meetingminutes.

Individual performance reviews are held annually, in some cases biannually or quarterly. In those meetings, the employee's work achievements are discussed and objective agreements and wage for the next term are negotiated. The objective agreement becomes the next performance review's basis.

Project/ task-based scheduled meetings (example: planning of a fair (sales) or a project (business)). In some cases, scheduling those can be done in the short term, e.g. when the colleagues get into a conversation on the hallway and decide to enlarge upon it, they may look for a free meeting room.

Meetings with external partners happen, when there is the need to talk about the used or offered software (e.g. new releases), preliminary discussion for events like fairs are held, advertisement campaign are to be planed or events are reviewed. Business consultants also provide feedback for new software versions.

Lunchtime: usually five to ten people of sales and marketing go to lunch together and talk about work related stuff as well as personal events.

Once a month, there is a *team leader meeting with the CEO*. Every two weeks, there are *team leader meetings*, which were scheduled weekly in the past.

Besides these, there are some *individual meetings* as off-site colleagues are seldom approachable at the company's hallway and others may not have the time for spontaneous discussions or need to prepare themselves for these.

On-site customer visits and post-processing could not be observed.

B.4.2 Unscheduled meetings

A lot of interaction takes place on the hallway and the offices. Employees talk about the work, ask for help and information about certain customers. Since most of the time all office doors are open and most people share their office or at least have a window in the door in it, there is a culture of spontaneous "break into" the offices for small questions and talks.

Much of the talks on the hallway occur at the coffee machine, at the copying machine/printer and on the way to and from them.

B.5 Support for daily work: documents / data and other helping means

- *Lead Documentation*: On a fair every talk with a visitor at the booth is documented on a lead document. This is a form with several fields that should hold information about the potential customer, e.g. the size of the company or which kind of product they are interested in. This documentation is afterwards talked about in a sales meeting and typed into the CRM (see below). If the customer seems interested and the sales consultant responsible for the lead thinks it may be worth to deepen the contact, it may lead to a contract. The lead documentation is in some cases also shared with other companies with whom they shared their booth and that have another target group.
- *Additional Notes*: in a personal notebook that did not fit the lead documentation or for quick documentation when no electronic device is at hand.
- If INFOMAN responds to a request for proposal, they have to document it in a web based system hosted by their partner where they have to fill in which requests they

are responding to. This documentation is merely for the partner to get an overview about which requests for proposals exists and which of their partners are responding to them.

- The central document management system (*Sharepoint*) provides *forums* for professional discussion about technical stuff. The participation in forums might also be considered for annual staff reviews. Forums are also used to make questions and answers more sustainable. E.g. when somebody sent a question by e-mail to colleagues and did not get any quick response they also post it on the forum where answers are more likely and in-depth or link to existing solutions and the corresponding documentation. The forums are used by business consultant who also store their *meeting minutes* in Sharepoint.
- *Meeting Minutes* of sales meetings are sent around by e-mail by the assistant.
- *Customer-Relationship-Management (CRM)* serves as a workflow management system. Relevant information obtained from any interaction with the customer or the potential customer or with others about those and their project or interests are put into the CRM. This includes contact information, a company profile, e-mail correspondence etc. It is also used to assign activities to staff, e.g. call a customer again if he/she was not reachable.
- *Documentation of projects and additional information*: for each project a project page is created including a wiki, a glossary etc. on a SharePoint server. Additional Information is stored in Office documents or result documents, in emails, in customer documents, in outlook dates etc.
- *Documentation of experiences with customers*: process maps or process descriptions of the customer are used to describe things, which worked well or topics the customer is interested in.
- *Best practice range*: for example: a colleague suggests an improvement for a customer process. If this improvement is a real benefit it will be integrated in the best practice range of the customer processes.

The system is accessible by laptop and partly by smartphone.

- *Webcasts* with chat, offered by the partner. This is used to stay informed about technological developments and news. It is used individually, for example after work in the evening as well as in scheduled learning meetings where several consultants meet and discuss it afterwards.
- *Websites* of customers to learn something about their profile and services as well as a website specialized on giving additional information about (possible) customers.
- *Presentation slides of finished projects* are saved on the file server as a post-project documentation. For creating them, a structured template is used.
- *SharePoint library for presentations in sales*: each sales person creates his/her own presentation. Each sales person owns his/her own project experiences including certain functionalities and knows how the customers work. For new colleagues it is not easy to get these materials and therefore a SharePoint-Library for sales presentations was established
- *A file server* is used to exchange any kind of data.
- *Digital advertising material* (PDF files) on the file server is used by the sales consultants when they write e-mails to potential customers. Most of these materials are provided by INFOMAN's partner company. The consultants choose the digital brochures individually to gear to the potential customers' interests and not "irritate" him/her with info, he/she doesn't need.

- In some cases, the consultant creates *presentation slides* for potential customers. This might happen, if the consultant doesn't see the existing brochures as fitting enough.
- Some *old e-mails* are read again. When an e-mail holds important information about a potential or existing customer, they are copied to the corresponding CRM entry. The copied e-mail becomes part of the preparation for interaction with the potential or existing customer.

Another reason for reading old e-mails is looking for a wording the consultant wants to reuse. For doing so he/she uses Outlook. On one observed case, the consultant tried to remember the date of the mail he was looking for and swiftly scrolled through several e-mails around the assumed date. Still looking for the e-mail, he then tried the search function and found it moments later.

- *Individual note taking*: Different forms of individual note taking were observed or talked about by the interviewees. They can be differentiated into computer based ways and pen and paper using ways (notebook, post-it notes). The following software solutions are used by at least one employee: OneNote, Excel, a tool to post notes on the desktop. At on-site visits, sales consultants take notes during interactions with (potential) customers when info is presented that is new to them using pen and paper.

While making a phone call, one consultant wrote down notes which he came back to later in the call.

- The Outlook calendar is used to coordinate meetings and other events.
- *Client acquisition via telephone*: within Outlook appointments and telephone calls are organized, additionally color-coding help to organize the events. An evaluation about who might be an interested party, whom did I call, which activities are completed is currently under development.
- Some offices have a wall calendar which is used for overview of larger timeslots, e.g. when fairs are or to manage holidays
- Every consultant has a Microsoft Windows based *smartphone* and a *laptop*.
- *Staff user profile*: on the intranet Sharepoint server each colleague of Infoman could create a user profile about his/herself including his/her qualifications. The persons are directly searchable. Ideas, tools and resources are available, but necessity, consequences and discipline to use it and to keep it up to date are still missing.
- *Individual documentation of customer questions*: one consultant prepared a list of more than one-hundred questions within an Excel sheet, to prepare herself for customer meetings, or to better understand the current situation of customers.
- *Exchange of information between employees*: software platforms, wikis or other collaboration possibilities like mobile phones, chat or the SharePoint portal

B.6 Current status, problems and motivation of reflection

At the stroke unit, there is already a culture acknowledging the advantages of reflecting work. This can be taken from the statements of interviewees and from observation we made during meetings (see above).

B.6.1 Current status of reflection

- *Description of personal views in meetings* after a happening: In a meeting we attended, the moderator asked the employees to express their views on a fair that took place some days ago. The reflection was based on experience where one consultant describes a meeting with a customer or a competitor and the others gave

input about their experiences and knowledge they have about those. In this, they made a difference between technical or business knowledge and knowledge about persons and behaviour. They went on with experience exchange about the usage of the demonstration appliance.

- *Talks during lunch* which cover professional stories as well as personal stuff.
- *Discussions on the hallway* about projects, potential customers and how to approach them. These discussions are mostly triggered by a) a current event or b) dependent on the person met.
- Individual reflection e.g. directly after a telephone call with a customer based on what happened. On the one hand about the customer and the potential project with the customer (if INFOMAN wants the project at all; what has to be done there; what the customer may want) and on the other about the approach he has chosen, the course of the conversation. This guides possible future contacts and if the customer is afterwards contacted by a colleague, they exchange the knowledge verbally.
- In complicated projects they (business consultants) reflect about whether they have chosen the right solution for a customer individually at first and may discuss it in the group afterwards.
- After meetings with external partners, they talk about the meeting and exchange their appraisal of the meeting they had.
- Annual/quarterly staff reviews with the supervisor. They set up goals and talk about if they were achieved at the next staff review.
- The consultants acknowledge reflection about their work as a good thing, but it was said that their daily work does not allow them enough time to do it regularly.

C. Description of work at NBN

This document is meant to be a description of the work AS IS done in the Neurologische Klinik Bad Neustadt (NBN). The document is the result of joint work done by MIRROR partners active in user studies (March, April 2011) at NBN (FZI, DFKI, RUB, KC).

Version	Editor(s)	Affiliation	Content
1	Martin Degeling, Michael Prilla	RUB	Initial Structure and Content based on observation and interview study done by RUB
2	Christine Kunzmann, Andreas Schmidt, Lars Müller, Verónica Rivera Pelayo	FZI	Revised and augmented the content based on analysis of observation data and interviews conducted by FZI
3	Silke Balzert, Thomas Kleinert	DFKI	Management Interviews (financial and medical management, QM, HR, advanced education)
4	Michael Prilla	RUB	Integration of changes and consolidation of first draft.
5	Angela Fessel	KC	Insertion of documents / data and other helping means found during the evaluation of the user studies

C.1 NBN

NBN is a hospital located in Bad Neustadt, Bavarian, Germany, and specialized in caring for patients suffering from neurological problems such as epilepsies or strokes. As a consequence, it has a wealth of different wards and specialities. To focus research on reflection at NBN, the stroke unit was chosen to be the target group for the MIRROR project. In this unit, patients being brought to NBN with an acute stroke are being cared for, if they do not have to be sent to intensive care. While this ward provides a good opportunity to observe the work of medical personnel in practice and find out about their reflection practices and needs, findings from our research on this unit cannot be generalized. This means that our results can neither be conveyed directly to other units of NBN or to other hospitals. Interviews and observations were carried out during early shift and late shift (depending on the study: while FZI observed both shifts, RUB only observed the early shift), so that information about night shift only stems from staff's reports and sensor data. However, due to its good structure and performance in care, the stroke unit is oftentimes used as a role model both at NBN and other hospitals when it comes to transferring good practice to other wards. To open the perspective for NBN as an organisation, interviews with the financial, medical and quality management, with human resources and the internal advanced education department were held. Therefore, we are convinced that there is a substantial amount of overlap in the practices of the stroke unit and other parts of NBN, which will allow for generalization of our findings and later development activities.

C.1.1 Partners at the testbed

Partner	Research Step	Time	Methods applied
All	Initial workshop	September 2010	
RUB	Work analysis	March 2011	Observation: Ethnographic notes, observation scheme
RUB	Work description and collaborative reflection analysis	March 2011	Interview: Guidelines for job description, (collaborative) reflection
FZI	Work analysis	March 2011	Observation: Ethnographic notes, observation scheme
FZI	Work description and collaborative reflection analysis	March 2011	Interview: Guidelines for job description, (collaborative) reflection
FZI	Sensor data collection	March 2011	Sensor data analysis and interview: Feedback about remembering experiences
DFKI	Work analysis	March 2011	Interview: Management Interviews
KNOW	Discussion of potential tools for reflective support	April 2011	Focus groups (nurses, therapists, physicians)
KMRC	Current situation of (individual) reflection	April 2011	Reflection Interviews

C.2 Work environment and routines

When entering the hallway on the left there is the ward station which is the central point for organising the work on the ward. Here drugs are stored and monitors constantly show the status of patients' heart rate and other vital signs. In the back of the ward station the physicians have a small separate room equipped with computers. On the other side of the hallway the recreation room is located with a small kitchen and tables with chairs for the staff's breaks.

Along the hallway there are 16 beds for patients available in the stroke unit. The beds are spread over eight rooms with two beds in each room. The rooms are along on hallway with four rooms on the left and four rooms on the right side. Each two rooms are connected with sliding doors. Staff members refer to these entities of two rooms with 4 beds as stations. There are four stations.

C.2.1 Physicians' work

The number of staff members present in the stroke unit depends on the shift. During the morning shift, the busiest one, at least 2 physicians are constantly on duty. Each physician is

responsible for 4 rooms and up to 8 patients though during our studies not all beds were occupied.

The morning shift is highly structured by meetings, ward rounds and doing diagnostics. The job of the physicians is to monitor the conditions of the patients in close cooperation with the nurses. Whilst the physicians are responsible for the diagnoses to be carried out and the decisions about the right medical treatment of patients the nurses do the daily tasks of assistance, care, washing and drug application. Every change in the status of patients as well as changes in treatment or examinations are written down in a protocol and serve as a basis of the work of nurses. In addition, some further documentation for patients leaving or join the station as well as the coordination of examinations and accounting purposes has to be done by the physicians in the KIS ("KrankenhausInformationssystem", hospital information system).

The early shift of the physicians starts between seven and half past seven a.m. with a handover between a physician and a representative from the night shift, either the nurses responsible for the patients the physician medicates or the physician from the night shift (see Table 1. Since the nurses start their shift at six a.m., they already had their handover and woke the patients up and have information about patient's status they share with the physician. In addition, the documentation at the end of the beds (called the "curve") holds notices about changes in status and medication. The length of the first handover depends on the physician, the number of shifts they had the days before and the number of new patients since the last shift. At eight a.m. there is a daily meeting of all physicians of the hospital that serves as a mixture of handover and informational meetings since physicians of the night shift are still on duty and can report on any particular events. The meeting is sometimes also used to present interesting case studies of patients or organizational stuff like shift plans.

Table 1: General structure of physician's early shift

Time	Activity
Before 8 a.m.	Shift handover
8:00 – 9:00	Daily physician's meeting
Between 9:00 – 11:00	Ward round with medical director
11:00 – 16:00	Diagnosis, documentation and new patients

At a varying point during the rest of the morning, mostly between nine and eleven a.m., the assistant medical director visits every patient during a ward round where decisions with a larger scope are discussed since the assistant physicians are still in training to become professionals in neurology. During the ward round decisions are made about when the patient might leave the hospital or whether more examinations have to be conducted. The medical director joins the ward round if private patients are present or if exceptional cases require his presence.

Table 2: General structure of physician's late shift

Time	Activity
12.30	Shift handover
	Consultation with patients' relatives
	Individual round to check patients and to document the results
22:00	End of shift

During the late shift, physicians take their time for consultation with patients' relatives. If there is anything special with some patient, physicians are called by the nurses when needed. The rest of the time, they use for writing reports, preparations for presentations, and informal learning using the Internet. Besides the routine work with patients in the hospital, physicians and nurses are always prepared for urgent admissions of stroke patients. These are usually announced short time before arrival and on physicians as well as on nurse are in charge for emergency patients and carry a special mobile phone (DECT) with them to be reachable. For stroke patients, there is only a short time window (4,5h) after the stroke in which the physicians have to decide whether the patients is given the 'lysis', a special medication which has the best recovery expectations, or not. Therefore, the examination and analysis of emergency committals has to be carried out very fast and everybody has to work hand in hand.

There are three kinds of physicians.

- The assistant physicians are relatively new to the ward. They are working towards becoming medical specialists in neurology as part of their further education. They also switch between wards for educational purposes. At the beginning (when they enter a new ward), they have a mentor for a few weeks. Then they gradually get more responsibility, one patient, two patients etc. The time frame depends on the capabilities of the physician.
- Ward physicians are more experienced physicians ("Oberarzt"), either experienced assistant physicians or medical specialists for neurology and responsible for treatment on the ward.
- The assistant medical director ("Leitender Oberarzt") is a specialist in neurology and guides the daily ward round. He is consulted when ward physicians are uncertain about the diagnosis and treatment of special cases. He is also responsible for the treatment of private patients (delegated by the chief physician).
- The chief physician is also a specialist in neurology and is responsible for the whole institute. He directly treats private patients, if not delegated to the assistant medical director.

C.2.2 Nurses' work

The work of nurses in the stroke unit is divided into three shifts comprising early, late and night shifts. While during early and late shifts, usually about six to eight nurses are on duty, in the night there are only up to four. During each shift, the nurses are responsible for patients in several rooms as well as for supplementary tasks such as filling up medicals and material in the patients' rooms. In the morning and late shifts, each nurse usually is responsible for patients in two rooms– the rooms are connected by a sliding door, thus easing the work in two of them. Nurses are sometimes assisted by another nurse. In addition, one nurse per

shift is responsible for the emergency ward and carries around a telephone to be informed about people being moved to this ward.

The shifts of nurses have an intended overlap, which is sometimes even extended by nurses. For example, the morning shift ends at 2 p.m., while the late shift starts at 1.30, giving the nurses the possibility to do handovers and have informal information exchange about patients and other things in the ward. Sometimes, morning shift nurses even stay until 2:30 p.m. for communicating to others from the morning and late shift. The same intended overlap of half an hour applies to the late and night shifts. Additionally, nurses change between shifts both on weekly and daily basis.

The early shift of nurses is structured by the day structure of patients, including tasks such as waking them up and serving them meals, and physicians' needs such as the ward round. Other influences they have to react on are unforeseen incidents such as emergencies and external influences such as therapists entering working with patients or patients being collected for external examination. Thus, their day is structured by certain milestones, as Table 3 shows, but the details of organizing their work are left to their own planning and responsibility. This, for example, also effects the documentation they are supposed to do during the day, as they have to find time slots for this during the day – on busy days they do it just before their shift ends.

Table 3: Day structure of nurses (early shift).

Time	Activity	
6:00	Shift handover with night shift	Documentation of patient's data, physiological data such as blood pressure and the like (captures by devices in the room) or blood sugar (to be measures by the nurse), medication given, and incidents during the day
After :00 – 9(:30)	Waking patients and getting them ready for the day (washing, mobilizing etc.); giving them medication, serving them breakfast	
9(:30) – 9:30(10)	Break (half an hour)	
9(:30) – 14:30	Servicing / caring for patients; performing other tasks, including special responsibilities	

About 10:00	Assisting the ward round in nurses' room (if not on break)	
About 12:00	Serving lunch	
13:30-14:00	Shift handover with nurses from next shift (1 nurse from morning shift for all, each nurse for their rooms)	

Table 4: Day structure of nurses (late shift)

Time	Activity	
13:30-14:00	Shift handover with early shift	Documentation of patient's data, physiological data such as blood pressure and the like (captures by devices in the room) or blood sugar (to be measures by the nurse), medication given, and incidents during the day
About 17:30	Serving dinner	
18:30-20:00	Washing and Bedding	
21:30-22:00	Handover with night shift	
22:00	End of late shift	

The responsibility of nurses is to ensure medical treatment of patients as well as assuring their physical and mental well-being. In the eyes of the nurses, this is their most important and challenging responsibility, as they reported in our interviews. The tasks they perform in order to fulfil these responsibilities are manifold and include the implementation of directives e.g. for medication given by physicians, the organization of patients' days including their transport to examinations and the documentation of both care given and physiological data measured during the day. For this, the nurses told us that they are using a multitude of standard procedures they learned in nursing school as well as standards stemming from the hospital's quality standards. Surprisingly, despite all these standards and the dependence on others' directives, there is a lot of freedom in the organization of daily tasks for nurses – in the interviews their estimates were up to 50% of tasks on a usual day to be in their responsibility.

Nurses do most of their work alone and care for all patients in their rooms. There are only a few deviations from that. In some cases such as heavy patients or special tasks, they ask another nurse to help them doing it. In other cases, nurses perform certain tasks for patients

of others, if they have received special training on certain treatment such as mobilizing a patient or other capabilities.

C.2.3 Therapists' work

Since there was no observation dedicated to this group and only one interview with a therapist – there are 18 (Partgroup) working in the hospital - the following information is rather incomplete and based on the interview and interaction observed between staff groups.

The therapists are not bound to a specific ward in the hospital in contrast to the other groups since they do therapy with patients in predefined timeslots and according to their profession. There are therapists specialized on different disciplines and body parts that get effected by a stroke e.g. swallowing, speaking, or motoric problems. Their work is to help the patients regain abilities they lost as a consequence of the stroke. Only few patients and especially those who got the lysis recover fast from the stroke. Most patients need a few month of rehabilitation therapy in the hospital to be able again to live on their own. A lot of them never recover fully. The therapy in the stroke unit is the earliest stage of therapy since it starts even the next day after a stroke. Since most patients do not recover quickly and are heavily affected by the stroke it is the aim of the therapist to give hope and even show slight improvements from day to day since a therapy needs the willing of the patient to work out.

Table 5: General day structure of therapists (over all Groups)

Time (approx.)	Activity	
7 a.m. - 7:30	Organizing with other therapists; Day plan	
7:30 a.m. – 2. p.m.	Doing therapy with patients on different units; Sometimes meetings with physicians are in this time.	Documenting of therapies done.
3:30 p.m. - 4 p.m.	Time for documentation in the therapists' room.	

The therapists organize themselves at the beginning of each day. In difference to physicians and nurses they do not work in shifts but daily on workdays between 7 a.m. and 4 p.m. They split the patients according to their needed therapies and organize the day with a computer program (“Magrathea”) and print out a timetable that guides them through the day. A dedicated handover is not needed every day but after weekends or holidays when more than one therapists of the same profession worked with a patient.

During the day they visit the patients at their beds and spend 15 to 30 minutes which depends on the number of patients they are responsible for dependent to the therapy they need. A therapist for tongue and swallow problems for example works most of the time during breakfast and lunch hours helping and guiding patients to learn eating on their own. Fifteen minutes is the minimum of time for a therapy session required by legislation, from the therapists' view, more time is always better so they organize their workload with other therapists to get larger timeslots for each patient. After the therapy sessions they write short notices in the Curve about the process of the patient and current diagnosis. Due to the short timeslot they spend with the patient they also have to rely on observations the nurses make of the progress *“Because they observe the patient in other phases. [...] I need feedback and*

say ‘Okay, can you say the nurses from the evening shift to look if this and that works.’” Just to get feedback.’” [N1]¹.

The organization of therapy sessions is not from the beginning organized with the other staff groups. The therapists organize them together with the nurses and a timetable for each patient and therapy sessions is kept in the Curve. But since there are unplanable events like new patients arriving timetables shift a lot. This results in conflicts and requires a flexibility in day planning e.g. when a ward round starts late and a therapist already started a session with a patient when the ward round group of physicians arrives.

Besides the first half an hour of a work day they use to organize themselves they have another 30 minutes at the end of the day to document what type of therapy they did with which patient and which changes they recognized. This work is carried out in the therapists’ room. Since all therapists work in the same timeslots they meet during this time and also exchange information about patients there.

For the accounting relevant part of the documentation they have a barcode based system in the ward station where they scan the type of therapy they did according to the patient – for each type of therapeutic activity, they have a barcode. Thus, after sticking barcodes to a patient’s record, they can use a scanner to easily document therapy done with the patient. The documentation of patients’ progress is shorter on the stroke unit than on other units due to the fact that patients only stay there for few days before they change to one of the long term rehabilitation units. Long descriptions are only needed if the patient changes the hospital. The short progress information is also used by the physicians to decide about handling of a patient (e.g. if and what they can eat themselves) and steps for rehabilitation.

A strong collaboration between therapists and physicians is also needed to determine the level of diagnosis. *“If somebody is bad at breathing you don’t know whether they choked on something and suffer from pneumonia or whether it is accumulated from the heart. Then you say: “Okay, I need an X-Ray” to the physicians who then do that.”*[N1]

The type of therapy that is done with the patient is highly regulated by legislation, based on what is allowed, and will be payed by the insurance company the physicians prescribe therapy forms. The way these therapies are carried out are described in the clinic internal quality management handbook. To stay informed about new developments and updates in the handbook there is a weekly therapists’ meeting on Friday. Like other staff, therapists also have to react on sudden changes and new patients arriving in the hospital.

Table 6 Number of staff present during the day

Shift	Workers present
Morning	2 (assistant) physicians, 1 medical specialist (assistant medical director), 1 medical director, 6-8 nurses
Afternoon	1 physician, 6-8 nurses
Night	1 physician, up to 4 nurses

C.2.4 Human Resources

¹ Interviewees will be named by an „N“ für NBN and consecutive numbers to ensure privacy.

The human resources (HR) management for NBN and therefore for the stroke unit (SU) as well is affiliated in the corporate HR department. In total there are seven hospitals managed by this HR department and they are split up onto two personnel officers.

The personnel development as one of the main functions of the HR department is coordinated in close cooperation with the ward managers in the hospitals. The HR department generates plans for educational offerings and communicates these to the employees. After the educational program the certificates of the employees are archived in their personnel records. The personnel records are paper based.

The HR department mainly documents quantitative issues of advanced personnel education. The wards choose themselves who participates in which further education program and HR only manages registration issues and documents the participation of the employee in the program. As a result HR has an overview whether or not the quantitative targets for advanced education were reached.

Apart from programs for key qualifications like needed for the SU, another big issue is the training of employees so they can function as practical leaders in certain topics. The choosing and education of these employees follows the mechanisms described above. Some further education programs have a value which is calculated into additional funding for the employee as an incentive system.

As ways of transportation for information to the employees there is an intranet established. The NBN-Intranet is not the first choice for HR to transport information because HR is technically not part of NBN. Information is given to ward leaders who give it into their departments in formal or informal meetings. There is a mailing system established but most employees do not have regular access to their mail accounts during every day work (1/3 of staff has an email address available).

The processes of the HR department are not documented since they do not fall under the quality management (QM) of NBN and do not have a corporate wide QM available. Employees have started to do informal documentations of their work processes and make these available for new employees to get involved.

Appraisal interviews on a regular basis are held in the departments of the hospitals and therefore in NBN as well. The HR department does in general not take part in these interviews but documents when all interviews were held. After each interview the ward management informs the HR department of the completed interview.

The time registration system lists work times and overtime of the employees and automatically alerts the HR department if the numbers exceed legal or internal agreements. In addition a digital duty roster is generated that keeps the working effort and the workload for employees balanced. For this roster externally bought software ("Breitenbach") is used in all seven hospitals.

C.2.5 Quality Management

Quality Management (QM) transfers the guidelines that come with the certification of NBN into process descriptions and work instructions. NBN is ISO-certified (9001:2008), IQMP-Reha-certified and the SU has a special CENTRUM certification by Stiftung Deutsche Schlaganfallhilfe (SDSH)/Deutsche Schlaganfall Gesellschaft. The results of this transfer are instructions for work processes on the one hand and documents, descriptions and checklists for certain purposes on the other hand. The centralized collection of this data is the QM handbook which is available in the intranet.

The process documentation in the QM handbook is sorted by occupation groups and not by process, which is being changed now (2011) for a better overview.

QM generates process models in MS Visio and annotates additional process information. Furthermore tables and textual descriptions are part of the QM handbook. In the current restructuring of the QM handbook documents are integrated into the process models for easier access and the QM handbook is connected to the intranet.

There is no connection between the Healthcare Information System (IMED1) and the QM handbook. Where data and documents for single patients are stored in IMED1, the QM handbook contains information on patient groups.

Since the main purpose of the QM handbook is providing a centralized platform for up to date documents and checklists, these files are available and can be printed out from the QM handbook. There is no feedback-mechanism for the documents integrated. Information on the usability of the documents etc. cannot flow back to QM.

Employees can address suggestions directly to the QM department. There is a suggestion system established and the employees can also give their suggestions to their superior. In the annual employee interviews and in questionnaires that are handed out every two years, effort is taken to identify possible process improvements.

The QM also briefs the auditors of the annual ISO 9001 system audit. The auditors are then provided with a professional expert and a co-auditor. The protocol of that audit is then handed to the management.

The QM handbook is implemented in a specialized software solution and there are plans for a corporate-wide software system for QM handbooks with integrated document management.

C.2.6 Advanced Education

The Advanced Education (AE) department (“Innerbetriebliche Fortbildung - IBF”) is responsible for any education programs concerning nurses and carers. The further education of the physicians and therapists is not managed in this department.

After establishing the SU at NBN there is the need for further education for nurses and carers if they want to work in the SU. NBN has established the AE department mainly to offer these educational programs in house. The program for the SU was developed together with the “Deutsche Schlaganfallgesellschaft” (German stroke association) and is offered to internal and external participants now. AE manages registrations for participants and lecturers.

In addition to the SU education program there are also further educations on several other topics. Furthermore the AE department helps managing the induction of new employees in all wards.

The identification of need for further education happens informal. When needs are identified, courses are being scheduled and the ward management is being informed. The employees are then sent to the courses by their superior.

AE periodically invites the lecturers for so called “practical days” where they visit the participants of the courses again and help them again in transporting the new learned techniques into their everyday work.

Every nurse and carer has a yellow “advanced education book” where all courses that the employee participated in are documented. These books are the basis for any analysis on further education in the wards.

The freshly trained participants of the offered courses are supposed to function as a knowledge basis for all the co-workers in their immediate surroundings.

The employees and the ward management communicate wishes and needs for special education programs or scheduling wishes to AE.

There are no e-learning systems established yet.

C.3 Personas in the target group

See Appendix developed together with FZI and DFKI

C.4 Interaction among staff

During the day, people in the stroke unit interact and collaborate intensively, both in spontaneous encounters and (more or less) scheduled meetings. Among these interactions, there are situations in which only one group of people is involved and others, in which members of at least two groups are involved. Mainly, there is interaction among physicians and nurses, but also between these two groups and therapists, who are not bound to the stroke unit and have their own daily schedule oriented towards therapy needs of patients. In addition, observations of work on the stroke unit have revealed that the work of physicians and nurses is highly dependent on self-directed task performance by both groups. In this section, we will briefly describe interaction types and situations we could observe.

C.4.1 Interaction among physicians

- *Handover between shifts of physicians:* based on a handover paper which is a one-sided printed page with a table on it where every patient is listed by name. The handover is in a first step conducted together with the nurses that are responsible for the patient and based on information written down in the "curve" where the physicians have to write down every information and change of medical interest (see below). In a second step the responsible physicians of the previous shift are asked for any additional information or personal appraisals of what happened and what should be observed.
 - *Physicians meeting:* Every day at eight a.m., all physicians meet in the large meeting room of the clinic. The meeting is divided into different parts with a changing audience. At the beginning most physicians of the clinic are present. This slot is used to speak about general concerns or news and to briefly present what happened at night in each unit/station. Sometimes there is also a case presentation by one physician about a patient with special illness or treatment. The second slot is only for the medical staff of the stroke and intensive care unit, who work closely together. Here the currently relevant cases and patients are discussed. In the end there is a short handover between the night shift and the morning shift where changes in the status of every patient during the last hours in the stroke unit are discussed.
- *Radiology meeting:* Three times a week several physicians (about 20) meet in a small meeting room that is equipped with a large screen computer connected to the clinic internal network. The computer is used to show the results of examinations with imaging apparatuses (CCT, MRT, etc.). The meeting is facilitated by the senior physician responsible for radiology. He goes over the list of all patients and asks if the responsible physician is attending the meeting to get additional information like the status of the patient when she was taken to the hospital. They talk about the diagnoses the responsible physicians made and what else the senior radiology expert sees in the images.
- *Spontaneous interaction:* Especially when they are working with the documentation and sitting together in the doctor's room, they talk about their daily practices, work processes and pending/unfinished duties, as well as diagnoses of patients.

C.4.2 Interaction among nurses

- *Spontaneous interaction:* During the day, there are many spontaneous and job-related interactions among nurses, which serve different goals such as mutual assurance of care

given to certain patients, talking about cases and incidents happened, asking others for help or information on certain tasks or issues and discussion problems with work. Usually, these interactions are short and happen if nurses meet in the hallway, the ward office or in a room. In other cases, nurses intentionally contact others if they know that they have been involved in special tasks or incidents.

- *Discussion during breaks:* There is one break per shift where nurses eat something and exchange in the nurse's room. Nurses start to discuss a broad range of topics ranging from small talk to work processes. Nurses often use these informal meetings to talk about their problems during the day and about other employees.
- *Handover between shifts of nurses in rooms:* Between two shifts, the nurse(s) being responsible for a room briefly meet in this room. During this meeting, the nurse from the passing shift reports on each patient's case history and their day, while the other listens and asks questions. These talks are closely related to the curve (see below) available at the bed of each patient. During our observations, nurses reported that it is their duty to hand over all relevant information and oftentimes they ask themselves whether they have forgotten to mention relevant information.
- *Handover between shifts of nurses in general:* Besides the handover done in the patient rooms, there is a general handover happening in the overlapping time between shifts. For this, one nurse from the passing shift sits down with the arriving shift and tells them things they need to know for the day. Usually, the head nurse is responsible for this and keeps track of things to be handed over. Topics we could observe in these meetings include tasks to be carried out such as filling up linens in the rooms, orders from physicians such as calling them when certain tasks have to be done and the allocation of rooms, including a short statement on each patient on the ward.
- *Nurses' ward meeting:* Once per month nurses from the morning and late shifts meet in the break room to discuss current topics vibrant in the ward. This meeting is done in between the morning and late shift, so that all nurses from the morning shift and the half of the late shift can participate – the other half takes care of the patients meanwhile. They are joined by some nurses from the night shift, some part-time nurses and (sometimes) by a representative from the hospital's work council. The meeting is run by the nurse(s) responsible for the ward, who have asked the others for topics in advance and add some topics they want to discuss. During the meeting, these topics are discussed iteratively. Topics we were able to observe comprise decisions to be made such as whether the ward wants to create their own ward manual, announcements such as changes in personnel and day structures, organizational issues such as how to cope with laundry or how to deal with visitors on the ward, staff needs such as training in using the internal telephone messaging system to report emergencies as well as coordination issues such as the timing for breaks during the days. During the meeting, one nurse keeps minutes, which are afterwards distributed to others on paper and / or via email (for those who have an email address). During the meetings, it is striking that the head nurse running the meeting seems to be the main address for problem solving: while all nurses engage in discussion, the implementation of solutions proposed is left to the head nurse(s).

C.4.3 Interaction among therapists (on and off the ward)

- *Daily Therapists meeting:* Every morning the therapists meet to organize who visits which patient that day. This meeting is also used to exchange information about patients.
- *Weekly "further training"-meeting:* Every Friday the therapists of the hospital meet and exchange information about changes in the quality management handbook or new equipment is explained. This meeting is protocolled hand written and the protocol is visible in the therapists' room for those who were not able to attend the meeting.

- *Therapy pre- and post-processing*: Besides the daily meeting in the morning all therapists document the status of the patients in the afternoon before quitting time. This time, about 30 minutes, is also used to discuss about patients and problems during the day.

C.4.4 Interaction among different groups

- *Ward meeting*: Once in a month on Wednesday at 2 p.m. there is a meeting for all people working on the stroke unit ward including office, nursing and medical staff as well as therapists. In total, this results in a usual attendance of 20 to 30 people. The meeting is announced with a bulletin in the break room, and everybody can note down topics they want to discuss on this bulletin. The meeting is facilitated by the head nurse and a senior physician. During the meetings, topics concerning the work at the ward are discussed, which comprise announcements and orders as well as topics of collaboration between the professional groups and issues already discussed in one of the group-internal meetings. Everything discussed in this meeting is documented by the head nurse. In general, the discussion culture is very open and everybody is taken for serious when they pose a problem or comment on certain issues. However, the meeting is dominated by the senior physician and head nurse, who not only host the meeting but also are the final instances to decide and implement solutions discussed.
- *Therapeutic meeting*: is a rather short meeting on a regular basis with a short talk about every patient. It is held in the ward office ("Schwesternstützpunkt"). There the therapists responsible for the patients on the stroke unit explain to all the physicians' status and progress of every patient and what they examined as sicknesses that have to be cured in further rehabs.
- *Breaks*: During the breaks e.g. in the early shift, some physicians and the medical directors join the nurses in the recreation room. This time is used to talk about private issues and to reflect on issues concerning the ward.

C.5 Support for daily work: documents / data and other helping means

- *The (curve) folder residing at the end of each patient's bed*: The central document for every patient is the *curve*. A folder lying at the foot of the patient's bed with all available information in it. On the front there is a paper with basic information, name, age etc. in the inside the nurses document vital sign like blood pressure and fevers, the physicians note down treatments and drug application rates. The curve folder also contains a multitude of forms e.g. for physicians to write down their diagnosis, for nurses to document the day of the patient and for therapists to document therapy done and announce additional appointments for therapy. This makes the curve the central document for daily treatment of patients and for the coordination between the different professional groups. For example, we often saw nurses flipping through the curve folder to stay informed about the patient's development or to notice appointments for therapy in order to include them in the planning of their day. Additionally, the curve folder is an important enabler of work, as e.g. nurses are not allowed to give patients drugs without a physician writing down a prescription in the curve.
- *Computers*: There are several application for computers in the ward, but computer usage and accessibility varies between the professional groups:
 - *Monitors in the ward office*: There are two monitors in the ward office, which give an overview of the current status of patients by showing vital signs of up to eight patients and audio signals triggered by anomalies and errors in data capturing by the devices the patients are connected to. These monitors are used to ensure quick help in emergencies and thus, they are constantly observed by the nurses.
 - *KIS (hospital information system)*: In addition to the monitors showing patients current status, there are additional computers in the ward office offering access to the hospital

information system. This system holds information on a patient not available from the curve folder. In the system, physicians and nurses can access different data from a dashboard screen with names of all patients and their location in the ward. In addition, the system provides templates such as the so called “letters”, which have to be written every time a patient is relocated in the hospital as well as when they leave the hospital (“Entlassbrief”). The letters are composed semi-automatically by the system and aggregate a patient’s status at the time of the writing, medication given, diagnoses of illnesses, proposed therapies etc. For nurses, the system provides background information on a patient such as how many times they have been in the hospital so far. Additionally, they use part of the hospital information system e.g. for digital documentation of wound care. In our observations, the system just played a minor role in the daily medical work of nurses and physicians, but was used for administrative purposes.

- *Coordination of examinations:* Many facilities and medical equipment at NBN such as the magnetic resonance tomography or CCT scanner are located at different laboratories across the hospital campus or shared among wards. Thus, using them needs coordination and scheduling. The KIS is also the frontend for this coordination, and it is used by nurses and physicians to access to timetables of shared equipment and examination rooms. In the timetables they can see when the appliances are already in use and when a patient can get an examination.
- *Physicians’ computers:* In the physicians’ room, which is located just behind the ward office, there are five computers connected to the internet. Four of them are for the use of KIS (see below). They do not belong to a single physician but every physician has a login ID and a password to get access to the computers. The fifth computer is a special equipped one with a larger screen and better performance. It is used to view the images of CT and MRT to analyse them and look for the cause of a stroke. Besides this usage, physicians also use the computers for research on cases and personal training purposes.
- *E-Mail:* The physicians, some of the nurses and (at least some) therapists have personal e-mail addresses which are used for asynchronous and not time critical communication like arrangements of meetings or information exchange. For example, changes in the quality management handbook are communicated via e-mail to physicians and nurses.
- *Quality management handbook:* Although it is also computer-based and accessible via NBN’s intranet, the quality management handbook has a specific role in the stroke unit. In general, it contains advice and help for all tasks to be done in the hospital, including criteria of doing them on a certain level of quality NBN guarantees to their patients (and to their insurance companies) as well as DIN EN ISO and other certificates. While the management seems to imply that this handbook is read and used frequently, our observations and the statements of nurses differ from that. In particular, they told us that in order to do their work properly, they cannot lookup everything in the handbook, but have to have it “*in my head*” [N3]. In addition, they told us that in rare and special cases, they look up things in the handbook in order to ensure they do things right. Then, some nurses told us, they print the respective information out and take it with them in order to have the information available for their work. The handbook also provides forms staff of the ward needs to document their work or to request e.g. transportation services and enables staff to print these forms.
- *Intranet:* Like the QM handbook, the intranet contains information for all employees. In addition to general information from the different departments in NBN, the Advanced Education (AE) department publishes information on their courses via intranet/Email. Not

only information on upcoming education schedules but also information material like presentations and pictures from held courses.

- *Bulletin boards*: In the break room and in the ward office, there are pin boards serving as public information points for the ward. On these boards, announcements of meetings are done and can be commented, initiatives and orders from management are displayed and private stuff such as a birthday list are put up.
- *Mobile phones (in-house)*: Every physician has a *mobile phone* for internal usage inside the hospital. These phones are based on DECT standards and have a four digit phone number listed on an electronic phonebook in the intranet. Thus, each physician can be reached via them. In addition to the personal phones there is one emergency phone for a physician and one for a nurse being responsible for the emergency ward in her shift, which is used to inform them about emergency committals which are usually announced some minutes before the patient arrives. In emergency cases there is a code to report the emergency, resulting in all physicians and an emergency team if nurses being called to the emergency ward.
- For paper based communication physicians have mail boxes on the ground floor next to the reception.
- *Lysis protocol*: for each stroke patient, the assistant physician has to fill in this protocol, including reasoning, why or why not the patient was medicated with lysis. This protocol can be seen as feedback (a) for the supervisor to find out how the assistant doctor thinks about the patient's treatment and (b) for the assistant doctor to reflect on how long she needs to provide the patient with lyses.
- *Medical specialist training documentation* ("Facharztausbildung-Dokumentation"): assistant doctors document their patient cases themselves within a paper-based book to control their training progress e.g. copying written documents about medical examination conducted, writing down information of simple and quick treatments or information about the patient.
- *Evaluation sheet*: for an appraisal interview the interviewee has to fill in an evaluation sheet. Feedback and further information about their work is given during the interview with a supervisor
- *Protocols of conversations with relatives*: Conversations with relatives about the patients or about the treatment of patients are documented as well. (NBN Interview)

C.6 Current status, problems and motivation of reflection

At the stroke unit, there is already a culture acknowledging the advantages of reflecting work. This can be taken from the statements of interviewees and from observation we made during meetings (see above).

C.6.1 Current status of reflection

The physicians reflect regularly alone and together with others since it is a useful method to make right analysis and decide about the best treatment for each patient based on what they decided before or as a reflective kind of problem solving e.g. on physician describes the beginning of a shift: "*I just ask: What happened? What's up? She [the nurse] tells me what happened yesterday or during the night and I reflect, based on this I do something with the patient for example. It is just our work.*" [N2]. Since the assistant physicians are still on a learning track to become specialists they discuss many situations and decisions with colleagues and the assistant medical director. But even more specialized staff is required to change behaviour according to new developments in medical science. Since the already know most standard procedures very well they are focussed on special cases where standard treatments are not applicable.

For physicians, reflection may take place in various situations: Individually in front of the KIS, where information about all patients triggers thought about the right treatment, or collaboratively in discussions during scheduled meetings and ward rounds. The assistant physicians for example always visit their patients before the ward round and plan what the next step should be. Afterwards they have to explain larger steps to the assistant medical director and, if she does not agree, have to reflect about why they took the wrong decision.

Furthermore each patient that is uncommon causes reflection, e.g. because she or he is much younger than the usual stroke patients or the treatment with the lysis was extraordinary successful or the healing is in a good or bad way other than with the perceived average. In this case the staff of the ward talks a lot about patients and exchanges information about the status on the hallway. Afterwards the case is also discussed in the meetings and the participants describe how they behaved and reflect about what could have done better.

Like for physicians, nurses also have a practice of concurrent reflection during the day and aimed at improving their work and the care for patients. There is a multitude of situations during the day when they talk to each other e.g. to mutually ensure proper treatment of patients. This is usually done by groups of two nurses standing in front of a patient's bed as telling each other what they did. Such situations both happen spontaneously during the day and pre-scheduled during the shift handovers. In these situations, mostly episodic information is exchanged and there is not practice of sustaining ideas or results stemming from these situations.

In their meetings, nurses also reflect problems that came up in the ward and good practice in their daily work (see the description of meetings above for details). In these meetings, they discuss issues such as changes in their work, possible solutions to their problems and the reasons for their (good or bad) performance in specific tasks. For these meeting, the minutes kept are the only documentation and it is left to the head nurse to further work with the meeting results and e.g. give them to the hospital's management.

On the level of exchange between the different professional groups working in the ward, the ward meeting is of special importance. During planned meetings like the monthly ward meeting where every staff member can and should participate there is a very open atmosphere for reflection and everyone *"Are there – any problems or something like that. Every problem we talk about together"*[N2].

Reflection on an organisational level is currently limited by the available information. Financial management has information extracted from the hospital information system and an established SAP ERM system (SAP IS-H). Much of the information needed for decision-makers is informal and provided directly without IS support.

C.6.2 Motivation for reflection

From the motivational perspective the main goal is to give the patients a good treatment so the healing process is fast and visible *"when we do a lysis to patient and on the next day he has no neurological deficits you can say: Good day. Good job – we did it. When we see the effects of our work. I have to say it that way"* [WGA08]. In addition especially the assistant physicians have a huge interest in the domain specific knowledge which is on the one hand related to the medical field and on the other based on experience e.g. how to apply a catheter. They need this knowledge and experience to do their job well and to be able to apply for the degree of a medical specialist in their field.

In this context, another motivating factor can be found in the nurses' ambition to be able to plan their day and the care to be given to patients. This became obvious when the nurses described their daily work and problems in this in our interviews: *"A good day is when you*

are able to plan your procedures, without incidents. [...] So that nothing happens in between [...] such as diagnostic, relocations, emergencies. Then it can happen quickly that things get over your head." [N3]. During the observations, we found that such situations also result in certain patterns showing the stress level of nurses such as doing documentation right before their shift ends instead of during the day, because there was not enough time for it during the day. The motivation to structure their day is closely connected to their wish of caring for people, as they told us they regard a structured day and enough time as enablers or rather prerequisites for good care.

C.6.3 Problems for reflection

One problem of reflection in the stroke unit, which was reported by the nurses often, is time for documenting both results of talking to others and individual thoughts. In their view, there is too much documentation to be done anyway, so they do not want to do any more documentation than necessary. This is also shown by the observation that among the nurses, nobody uses a notebook to write things down. This is different for physicians, but they use notebooks to write down medical observations and also do not document out ideas and reflection results. However, they also document patients' days for handovers, so there might be potential in doing purposeful documentation tasks. This way, oftentimes episodic information on more comprehensive procedures are missing when reflection sessions are held.

REGISTERED NURSING HOME ASSOCIATION (RNHA)

Current Work with Technical Partners at end of Year 1

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Introduction

There are 2 main purposes of this 'composite' document from the RNHA, although alone it is not an official project deliverable:

1. To provide a perspective from the Test-bed side. As will be shown, this perspective can be useful in highlighting common themes and interests of partners, as well as provide a focus on the real business needs of a vital sector in all European countries. The customer perspective is an essential role in any technology development project.
2. To help improve coordination between technical partners, and thereby help to address issues of integration in the project. It is very easy for individual groups to focus on their own research objectives and fail to see commonalities and mutual benefits. By providing a focus on a testbed and its business requirements in this project, the various contributions of the individual partners can be seen in greater context.

This document contains summaries of the work of each of our main active partners in the first year of MIRROR. For the most, these summaries have been written by the partner themselves.

The RNHA Setting

The National Context

The majority of English care/nursing homes are privately owned and managed. There has been a deliberate shift of such homes from local authority control to private sector control. For the Government this has immediately thrown up the challenge of ensuring that these small businesses pursue more than bottom line profits, which could theoretically be at the expense of quality of care of service users (i.e. residents in this context).

There are three main 'official' or 'government' players plus other important stakeholders concerned with the quality of care provided and the training of those carers providing that care.

The three main 'official' bodies are:

1) **The Care Quality Commission.** The Care Quality Commission (CQC) is the body charged with ensuring that good standards prevail in the sector. It has a number of weapons in its armoury. Until recently, these included the 'Quality Rating Assessment', buttressed by compulsory Annual Quality Assurance (self) Assessments (AQAAAs) and further underpinned by detailed regulatory powers. The Quality Rating Assessment awards stars to homes, with Excellent homes achieving 3 stars, Good 2 stars and Adequate only 1 star. Poor homes get no stars and should get squeezed out.

(See <http://www.cqc.org.uk/> While the 'headlining' Star Rating has recently been dropped by the government, essentially the same methodology is still used in practice.)

2) **Skills for Care and Development.** 'Skills for Care is the 'industry-led' body which translates the national minimum standards for care set by the Government Department of Health into national occupational standards. See <http://www.skillsforcare.org.uk/home/home.aspx>

These national occupational standards are used to inform the sector's national vocational qualifications (NVQs). A high percentage of care home assistants are expected to attain NVQ level 2, with the more senior staff expected to attain NVQ 3.

3) **The Social Care Institute for Excellence.** The Social Care Institute for Excellence (SCIE) is a largely research based organisation. It is a charitable company and is largely funded by the Department of Health. SCIE's remit is to identify good practices based on firm evidence and to encourage the spread of good practices. See <http://www.scie.org.uk/>

The work of SCIE has been of relevance. During the past two years SCIE have developed Social Care TV – an online repository of high quality videos across the range of social care. See dementia video material

<http://www.scie.org.uk/socialcaretv/topic.asp?guid=6ddc31cf-a355-46cf-9fce-2685b51272d3>

SCIE have also commissioned two major surveys on the state of ICT and ICT readiness in the sector. The sector has historically been a 'late adopter' of technology, and the surveys reveal that belatedly there is now some movement. See

<http://www.scie.org.uk/publications/consultation/readiness.asp>

In 2010 SCIE sought to inject a £12m stimulus by launching the Get Connected project which provides grants of up to £20,000 for equipment and associated training in Care Homes to help care staff get access to the increasing and increasingly good quality training resources available through internet, and help get residents access the internet, as an essential social and therapeutic tool. See <http://www.scie.org.uk/workforce/getconnected/index.asp>

(It is ironic that the 'dementia life box' demonstrated by Ian Turner, Chairman of the RNHA, at the Kick Off meeting is not eligible for Get Connected funding, as it is not internet-based and falls outside of the scope of that project.)

RNHA and other Association Stakeholders

In addition to the agencies listed above, care homes tend to coalesce into associations or clusters of similar organisations, often based on geographical location or type of Care Home. Such associations provide a channel of dialogue with Government and a 'strength in numbers' when it comes to disputes and negotiations. They form important pressure groups in the sector, and will often provide important input to policy developments.

The RNHA, with some 1200 members, (<http://www.rnha.co.uk>) is the relevant association for Nursing Homes and it is within busy functioning individual care homes that the research has taken place.

Malcolm Rose and Kevin Pudney form the RNHA team providing the interface and working with research partners on collaborations, guided by Ian Turner, Chairman of the RNHA.

The Care Home context

In round numbers, there are some 20,000 residential care homes in England, looking after some 1 million residents. Generally there are 2 sorts of homes – Residential Care Homes, and Nursing Homes. Nursing Homes provide the same personal social care services as residential care homes, and also offer 24-hour qualified nursing care. Nursing care may need to be considered – for example, if the person with dementia is very confused and frail, has difficulties walking, has other illnesses or disabilities, or is doubly incontinent. But in most operational ways, the 2 sorts of home work in similar ways.

For a range of interesting information on dementia see the Alzheimers Disease Society website. See <http://alzheimers.org.uk/> It is sobering to reflect that as little as 40 years ago the phenomenon of dementia amongst elderly people was almost a secret – no one wished to admit that there might be ‘mental problems’ in the family. Now there are some 100 forms of dementia recognised, many triggered by physical or chemical changes. Certain expensive drugs have been found to help slow onset but ways of assisting those with enduring dementia are still in their infancy. Likewise staff training (as described at the Kick Off meeting) has begun to be better at ‘managing’ the sufferer but equally has far to go in terms of ‘engaging’ the sufferer.

A Typical Care Home

A typical care home is likely to have around 40 to 50 residents.

The typical admission age for nursing home care is now in the 80s, and has gradually increased over time in line with rising longevity. (The proportion of the population suffering dementia doubles for every 5 years of aging.) Residents will come into nursing care from other residential care, or from their own homes. It is estimated some 2/3rds of residents will have some form of dementia, in varying degrees.

Some 2/3rds of residents are women.

The main policy approach in residential care today is that of ‘personalisation’ i.e. fitting services to the needs of the individual resident, rather than fitting the resident into inflexible existing services. (For example, “when would you like your breakfast?” v ‘Breakfast is at 8:00-9:00am’). Reflection is central to the care of dementia sufferer, and in their own lifestyle activities, when short-term memory, typically, is badly affected. Information is the key – capturing, processing, and providing it in ways to improve both the care and quality of life for this specific, but large and growing, group of people.

The Work Environment

Most Care Homes are purpose-built, modern buildings, to satisfy current building standards for separate bedrooms and sufficient toilets/bathrooms. (Older buildings have increasingly been too expensive to adapt for access and standard facilities.) Reception and the administrative Office are usually close to the entrance, and the rest of the building will be mainly residents’ private rooms, with residents lounges available. A kitchen and dining area will be prominent, and a garden is often available.

Staff will often be on their feet most of their shift, moving from resident to resident, task to task. Staff will have access to a general staff room, but not individual rooms or desks or computers. Mobility is the nature of the job. It is difficult to find peace, as all around you are both colleagues and residents. There is little 'spare' space in a Care Home. A space could be a bedroom, and a bedroom is income – between €450 to €800 a week, depending on the needs of a resident and quality of care given.

Work is organised in shifts. Night-shift staff tend to be a separate group, although still in need of training, induction, communications, etc. Staff work all manner of shifts, depending on their personal circumstances. Management's task is to provide sufficient staff cover for the residents' needs at all times – ratios are laid down by regulation.

Staffing

A typical care home is likely to have around 40 staff. The overwhelming proportion of staff, particularly carers, are women. Many will be part-time.

Staff will have supervisors. Generally there will be a hierarchy of staffing.

- Care Home Manager
- Registered Nurses and Senior Care Staff
- Care Assistants
- Auxiliary Staff (Kitchen Staff, Maintenance, Administration)

As the residential home is a '24/365' operation, the staff will typically be on 'shifts', including night shifts, which vary according to the needs of the home, and the needs of the staff. Providing rotas for staff is a constant problem for managers, exacerbated by a high turnover – around 20-25% a year is not unusual.

Our previous research at one, typical, nursing home in December 2008, provided the characteristics of 38 staff in some detail. There is no reason to suppose that this staff profile is significantly different from other Nursing Homes.

Almost all the respondents were 'hands-on' care staff; three quarters were social care staff, and almost a quarter in a nursing role. The vast majority (86%) had no supervisory responsibilities, and the bulk of respondents (84%) were women. Although a small group, the male carers were educated to a higher level than the average female respondents.

Of those who indicated an educational level, some 43% were educated to the minimum 16 years old, a further quarter had A-levels, and 14% were graduates. Only 27% indicated having professional qualifications.

Although the average age of all respondents was almost 40 years, that single figure hid a considerable variation, shown in this graph.

The average carer had worked at the Care Home for nearly 5

years (4.7), and worked in Social Care for nearly 6½ years. Some 62% had only worked at that Care Home in their social care career.

Again these single figures hide much variation, shown in the graph below, looking at the length of time respondents have worked at that Care Home.

In fact the largest group of respondents had been recruited within the last year, although almost a third has worked there for than 5 years.

These figures demonstrate the significant turnover rate in social care - but many of those who decide to stay for more than 5 years do see it as a long-term career.

One of the key reasons for the high turnover is simply the levels of pay in the sector, often at the 'minimum wage' levels, or just above for the standard unqualified carer - and then reinforced with little financial incentive to seek qualifications with little pay differential, traditionally, between the levels of qualifications in social care.

Despite the poor pay, staff are expected to undertake a range of courses (or somehow learn the skills) covering everything from health & safety to dementia awareness. The table below shows the mandatory skills-set required by role, most to be learned in the first 12 weeks of induction, and many to be refreshed annually.

List of 'Mandatory Training Courses' by Care Home Role

COURSES	Care Asst	Snr. Care Asst	Nurse	Managemt	Kitchen	Domestic	Admin	Activity Coord.
Safe Handling	1 & 3	3	1 & 3	3	1 & 3	1 & 3	1 & 3	1 & 3
Fire Safety	1 & 3	3	1 & 3	2	1 & 3	1 & 3	1 & 3	1 & 3
Adult Safeguarding	1 & 3	3	1 & 3	3	1 & 3	1 & 3	1 & 3	1 & 3
Infection Control	1 & 3	1	1	3	1 & 3	1		1 & 3
Basic Food Hygiene	1	1	1		1 & 2	1 & 3		1
First Aid	1	2	1	2				1
Philosophy of Care	1	1	1					1
Health & Safety	1	1	1		1	1	1	1
Communications Skills	1	1	1					1
Personal Care	1	1	1					1
Skills for Care'	1	1						
Induction Workbook								
Dementia Awareness	2	2	2		2	2	2	2
Mental Capacity	2	2	2	2			2	
Nutrition	1	1	1	2	1			
End of Life Care	1	1	1	2				
No. of Courses	15	15	14	8	8	7	6	11

Where 1= Mandatory training at Induction 2= Other Mandatory 3= Annual Refresher

The 'training industry' for residential care is large and growing!

However the training methods remain, for the large part, traditional. Most training and skill acquisition is delivered and learned through observation/learning on the job, through supervision, and face-to-face classroom training, using 'traditional' training methods of Powerpoint-assisted talks, small-class discussions, and some video/DVD demonstration on key professional practices.

In our PROLIX work we asked about e-learning. It is fair to say that on the issues of IT and computer-based learning, the respondents were divided. To the question 'Do you consider e-learning useful for your own work-based training?', the average score was 2.5. This slightly positive average hides considerable variation, as shown in the graph below:

Whilst the majority did see e-learning as useful for their own training, a significant minority were yet to be convinced. This seemed unrelated to their assessment of their own competency using computers, and also unrelated to age. Certainly learning on one's own was not as popular as group training, and group training with a trainer and without a computer was preferred far more than computer-based training without a trainer!

Many professional multimedia e-learning products are now available in social care – though most are essentially videos, repackaged for digital (DVD) and internet delivery - as the core skills remain largely constant. There are many providers now, both from the public sector e.g. SCIE, and commercial providers e.g. <http://www.embrace-learning.co.uk>

IT 'Readiness' in the sector

'IT readiness' – the capacity to embrace the digital revolution – is very much a key topic in the social care sector. For various reasons, social care in general, and residential care in particular, has lagged behind much of the economy in use of ICT. The various reasons are relevant when looking to engage the sector today:

- The core business skills are personal. They are person to person, largely one-to-one relationships, and simply engaging in social interaction with a resident is part of the 'task'. Staff would often say "I came into care work to talk to people, not computers". That comment is not heard as much, (and computers are not what they used to be), but the essential truth is that these staff are 'people-centred', and haven't seen much evidence, so far, that machines can help them in their job.
- The senior staff group, including much of management, are typically older women who have risen through the care ranks, and have had very little, if any, exposure to ICT in their day to day work. They often struggle to engage with the management issues related to the introduction of ICT.
- ICT has been used primarily as an administrative tool, and then to provide basic information about residents, in pre-formatted reports required by the regulators.

Electronic communication with all Care Homes is still an aspiration for the regulators. The Care Home's administrative worker is likely to be the main user.

- Care workers have not used ICT as part of their caring work, except perhaps for e-learning/training on one or two topics, and recording case notes.
- Residents have very rarely been users of ICT in care homes.

IT 'Readiness' in a typical Care Home

Recent research on behalf of SCiE suggests that the overwhelming proportion of Care Homes, probably over 90%, will now have computers and be connected to the internet for email and access to professional reference material.

However, a typical Care Home will have only a handful of computers, which will be mainly fixed desktop PCs. The administrative worker will use one for business communications, email, and internal administration. The Care Home manager will have one or access to one, for email and administration. It is likely that other 'workstations' will be communal PC workstations for the input of 'professional' data. Internet access will almost certainly be blocked from these workstations. (Most, though not all, of the UK is well-served with broadband connections.)

Most Care Homes will run a professional 'client-server' database where resident and staff data is held, operational changes and case notes are recorded, and care plans are developed and consulted. These are often seen as inflexible, slow, and input-hungry, with very little useful output for staff – helping to give ICT a bad name for care staff.

Apart from administration, some key roles lend themselves to the use of ICT in a Care Home. Training activity is increasingly being linked to ICT in its delivery, recording, and evaluation. Marketing the Care Home business may be assisted with a web-site for the Home, and an informative DVD. 'Activity Coordinators', who work with and stimulate residents, is another area where the power of imaginative ICT use is starting to take off. The 'Dementia Life' box shown at Saarbrücken is such an example of this work.

As with all organisations, there will often be an amateur 'techie' in a Care Home. These people can be very useful, particularly for providing on-site user-support, but also can be seen as threatening to senior, and less knowledgeable, staff.

User-support is typically variable from Home to Home. For many, too few business processes are run that depend on ICT to warrant specialist ICT support – but this is rapidly changing.

At least as important to the MIRROR project, is the resident. Currently residents have little or no access to ICT facilities. Increasingly in Europe it is recognised that access to the internet (and the applications in the cloud) is, practically, a human right, and has the capacity to enhance their quality of life. Email, Skype and webcams, Facebook, community and interest groups, family trees, various 'reminisce' activities, photos, favourite music and media, Wii games, etc. etc. All are seen as valuable resources. What can be done with 'new technology'?

A typical staff member and User Personas

Social care staff have typically been agnostic about technology. Unfortunately many have seen it as controlling them - rather than the other way round. The computer has required data, and lots of typing, but didn't do much for them. However, although resistant at the start, social care staff have accepted ICT as necessary some time ago. A survey some 15 years ago in a large social work department found only 7% of staff resistant to using 'new technology'. Even that small group appears to have disappeared.

Recent surveys, supported by our small group work with Nursing Homes, now suggest that the typical staff member in a Care Home uses ICT and accesses the internet regularly – though from their own home. Although many did not see themselves as 'computer users' they accepted readily that they used Face-book and shopped on-line. Age alone did not appear to be a factor in usage. Older staff, grandmothers in many cases, used email and Skype to keep in contact with family members abroad.

Whereas 15 years ago, the staff needed help and persuasion to use technology, now they see their working environment as 'behind the times' - ICT-poor, manual records, slow old systems, poor or no internet access, etc – compared to home broadband and, for some younger staff, smart-phones. It is likely that most staff communications in a Care Home are still done by notice-board, rather than email. Possibly for the first time, the staff group are more ready than the management and owners for help from technology.

But, and it is conditional, it has to be genuinely useful and helpful.

A selection of 'typical' staff members as Users of MIRROR Apps are shown as personas in the document '**RNHA Storyboard Personas.docx**', stored in Google Docs.

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1zVyFzy5goEAq-m22bCf7zU3rapOxVXXSzjJZEm-NwuE/edit?hl=en_US&authkey=CJCsiuQI#

Challenges for MIRROR Research

Taking all the above factors into account, the RNHA Testbed provides a set of unique challenges for MIRROR researchers. But it also offers some attractive features – size, transferability of methodology, willingness to engage, and not least, a genuine opportunity to indirectly improve the quality of life of potentially millions of European citizens.

Key challenges have been considered by researchers, including :

- It is a Residential Home – i.e. someone's home

First and foremost, it should be remembered that Care Homes are peoples' homes. Change is often unwelcome to residents, and new faces and new situations can be challenging. It is important therefore that any research activity undertaken 'on-site' is organised as sensitively as possible and disruption minimised.

The RNHA team have experience of working and researching in Care Homes, looking at the application of technology for learning with real users, and feel confident that with the

right approaches, similar positive working relationships have been made. It is requested therefore that all approaches by MIRROR partners are made via the RNHA team.

- Staff attitudes to research and technology

A typical care worker is a busy woman, often a mother and housewife. She is poorly paid, tends to be under-pressure, and practical. 'Research' and 'computers' will not be an attraction for most staff. Suggesting staff groups to discuss such topics 'after work' (i.e. in their own time) will be unlikely to get any positive responses. However, many staff now recognise that technology can have its positive uses, and small group discussions can stimulate various 'good ideas' for beneficial applications.

- The outcomes from MIRROR should be Useful and Easy to Use

Not just theoretical models, or unstable prototypes. Mobile 'Apps' seem to be better suited to the work of care staff in their fast-moving mobile work, than say, fixed PC links to the internet and then further complex applications. Indeed our PROLIX work finished with attempts to produce short, simple, YouTube-type videos available on-line addressing key practical skills. The content was accepted, but the method of delivery was too slow and complex. Mobile apps perhaps can provide a better solution.

The Business Needs addressed by MIRROR

Introduction

At the Kick Off Meeting RNHA set out some very concrete examples of business need which were enthusiastically endorsed by Consortium partners. These centred on the use of reflective learning apps with the objective of improving:

- a) the improvement of the skills of the care worker in assisting the person with dementia to have as good a quality of life as possible, and if possible
- b) the quality of life of the person with dementia in a care/nursing home context.

This then was the very specific focus that we looked to MIRROR partners to help us with.

Whilst it might have seemed a relatively narrow focus, it was clear from those present at the Kick Off meeting that nearly everyone knew of an aged relative suffering from the onset of one of the many forms of dementia that will almost inevitably affect each of us, should we survive to old age. All the demographic projections anticipate that most of us Europeans will 'enjoy' a much longer life than our forebears so that successes in this area could be of both immense strategic value as well as helping us to actually enjoy great old age.

To be more concrete, we formulated 5 specific areas of development, or business needs, which we felt could be addressed by an 'app', to be used by carers. These have remained a constant focus throughout our first year.

These were:

1. Life History Application. This would provide basic details of a resident, accessible by a mobile device by a carer. This would replace or supplement the current physical Life History book of each resident.
2. Simple Training. This application could present information in a multimedia form about common tasks, which could be called up and viewed on a mobile device. The outputs would last seconds or minutes at the most – key essentials – not ‘training videos’.
3. Complex Training scenarios, explored using Serious Games.
4. Challenging Behaviour App. An application to assist carers dealing with episodes of ‘challenging behaviour’ (i.e. unexpected disruptive behaviour). This covers a wide variety of behaviours, and is certainly not unique to the social care sector.
5. Rummage Box. An application, to be mediated by Care Staff or used by Residents themselves, which allows the user to browse through multimedia ‘memories’ of their past (personal, cultural, or generational memories), for therapeutic and entertainment value.

The Development of Storyboards

One of the first collaborative events of the project was held at City University, billed as Creative Workshops. Over two days the various project partners explained their situation, needs, and what they could offer to the project. Highly productive, the outcome of these workshops were the Testbed Storyboards, which set out the operational problems which could be addressed by solutions from MIRROR. This early Storyboard listed our 5 business needs, linked to the partners and their ‘products’ which seemed to provide part of the solution to our needs.

The RNHA Creativity Workshop Storyboard: (RNHA Storyboard.docx), is available at:

https://docs.google.com/leaf?id=0B4DLAdlxAPYGYWM1MWFkZTQtMTRmNS00YzY4LWlZyWEtOGNkY2Q3NTIwYzk5&hl=en_US

This document was the start of a process which over the following months elaborated these business needs into more detailed User Requirements, each addressing a business need, and again using the Storyboard method. These can be viewed in Google Docs, on the links below:

Life History Storyboard :

https://docs.google.com/leaf?id=0B14s8eTfwMj-MGYyMTc2NmMtMzQwNS00Njk2LTk2YWQ0tNjQ0OTA1OWY4YjA5&hl=en_US&authkey=CPCu2qAE

Simple Training Storyboard :

<https://docs.google.com/leaf?id=0B14s8eTfwMj-ZWIzZDcyNTEtZmUxZS00YmUzLTk3YmEtMmU4M2IzYmJkYjBj&sort=name&layout=list&num=50>

Serious Games Storyboard :

https://docs.google.com/leaf?id=0B14s8eTfwMj-OGVmNzkyYTMtYTBjOC00ZTYwLTgxNWItOTRjNDNhNzE2MTlj&hl=en_US&authkey=COvZ5N0G

Challenging Behaviour Storyboard :

https://docs.google.com/leaf?id=0B14s8eTfwMj-MWRIM2U1NzQtNzQ5Ny00M2FmLTk2ZTMtNTFhMzVhMjRhZWl2&hl=en_US&authkey=CMn05dQN

Rummage Box Storyboard :

https://docs.google.com/leaf?id=0B14s8eTfwMj-Y2U3YjI5OGQtOGZjMC00Y2ZiLTk3MjctNDZmMGJiMzEwZTc1&hl=en_US&authkey=CJjjw8kM

Partners Involved

As the first Storyboard from the Creativity Workshops demonstrates, a number of technical partners were identified who were potentially matched with our business requirements at that time, and showed the areas of possible collaboration.

Over time these proposals were refined, and at the end of Year 1, a number of specific activities have now taken place involving 6 Technical partners.

Summary Table of Partners and Activities at RNHA Testsites

Partner	RNHA Testsites	Work Type	Current Status
KMRC	All (n=7)	4 Questionnaire Surveys and Diaries for Staff and Managers	Data submitted by 92 individuals
KNOW	All Data	Analysis from Documentation	
City University	Risby	Field test for Carers communications Carers App developed	Publication of early positive results
Imaginary	All, for testing	Serious Game ('Think Better Care') for Managers and staff	Field test of early versions focusing on complex dialogues
RUB	Risby	Data Collection & Observation	Collected.
NTNU	Palm Court RNHA HQ	Reflection research with Carers Life History App development using NTNU Students	Collected Prototype developed.

A summary of these activities are shown below.

Brief Description of Work by Technical Partners

KMRC

KMRC had the first impact on the RNHA Test sites with 4 type of questionnaire.

In total 88 returns were made from 7 different homes.

Questionnaire Type	Testsites responding
IT Checklist	3 (Wren Hall, Castle Froma, Kineton Manor Nursing Home)
Manager Questionnaire	7 (Kineton Manor Nursing Home, Castel Froma, Compton House, Marillac Care Home, Willows Care Home, Wren Hall Nursing Home, Beachcomber Care Home)
Reflection Diary	1 (Marillac Care Home) 6 (Kineton Manor Nursing Home)
Staff Survey (Short version)	28 (Kineton Manor Nursing Home) 43 (Wren Hall Nursing Home)

Due to the specific nature of the RNHA test-bed - a lower level of education and concerns about the level of literacy – as well as considerable time constraints on working carers - a shortened version of the staff survey with easier language was used. The modifications were recommended by the RNHA test-bed and probably led to an increased response rate. Indeed, RNHA returns comprise the majority of all project returns. While the level of detail and accuracy in which the key aspects can be captured is lower, these aspects can still be compared to the other test-beds.

It is intended that the data collected will be analysed and presented to the participating Care Homes in autumn.

KNOW

Early comments on the tools and data collected is reported by The Know Centre, as follows:

Tools and Reflective Practices

We analyzed the following data to find out which work tools that capture data potentially useful for reflection, and which reflective practices already exist at RNHA care homes

- Reflection Diaries provided by KMRC
- Reflection Interviews conducted and provided by NTNU

At RHNA there exist a lot of tools with corresponding data, which could be useful to support reflection. These tools will be divided into three categories:

Tools keeping patients information:

- **Resident's documentation:** documentation of residents about their behaviour:
Documentation of residents about their behaviour: Carers document everything about residents. Any things that the nurse needs to know about is told them verbally and is put into the care system. If anyone's got a break or broken skin or what they eat, if they're toileting, if they're incontinent, if they've been to toilet. The carers document the resident's mood of the day. E.g. if residents were in a bad mood then there can be reflected if they haven't been to the toilet for a few days... Conversations with the residents. Fluid watch charts to make sure that they're drinking and that they're passing urine and stuff. Documentation of eating.

Tools for knowledge sharing with colleagues:

- **Resident's notes:** notes made about residents after finishing the work with the residents are inserted in the computer:
Hand over notes: notes about residents to give over to the next shift. "E.g. why I use the handover notes because of once I've sort of helped a resident with their personal care, I can then write down anything I think is important and then hand it over".
- **Handover notes:** notes about residents to give over to the next shift:
Notes made by hand (e.g. handover notes) are usually transferred into a computer manually! Usually directly after the residents are done.
- **Daily Workplan:** to coordinate work at RNHA care homes.

Tools keeping personal/individual information:

- **Personal Diary:**
"Yeah I used to have my diary when I started, which helped me to remember sort of the time phrase of sort of what to try and stick to. On a night shift I was asking just about catheters because I wanted to know sort of what it... not what it does, how it is attached and stuff and the night nurse explained it all to me. She actually write it, like drew a picture of it and then she gave it to me to take home."

The following reflective practice was found at RNHA:

Scheduled reflective practices:

- **Supervision:** nurses and carers reflect with a supervisor about their job:
Nurses and carers reflect with a supervisor about their job, the problems with residents and other topics. Meetings with supervisor: *"... it is like a folder and it's all kept confidential and it would say what you were talking about last time. If you have any problems with care work and then you can discuss that sort of the next time you have supervision. Use the folder and looking back into what you talked about last time."*

City University London

City University London has collaborated significantly with RNHA on a number of developments, using MIRROR and additional resources to explore creative problem solving approaches and other mutually beneficial activity satisfying research goals whilst contributing to genuine business solutions

The collaboration has included the following:

- Running a Creativity Workshop which allowed technical partners to better understand the needs of the application partners, and application partners to gain a sense of the possible solutions available through the technical partners. City provided valuable facilitative help with the first 'storyboards' incorporating the 5 business needs of RNHA.
- Working with the group of technical partners and RNHA to explore the acceptability of technology (digital pens, sensors, tablet devices etc) which would be acceptable to carers in the conspicuously 'technologically-challenged' care sector
- Providing template guidance for the development of second generation of storyboards, exploring the detail of User Requirements
- Preparing and field testing the use of mobile devices using a modified Twitter at Risby for data capture and reflection. The positive results of this test will be reported as both a conference delivery (see below) and an academic paper, shortly.
- The development of a prototype 'Carer App' to assist carers reflect on instances of 'challenging behaviour', by reporting, and then comparing similar examples of challenging behaviour from a repository, and invited to reflect.
- Formation and leadership of a 'Challenging Behaviour' working group, recognising that 'challenging behaviour' is a feature of many aspects of human interaction - not just nursing care – and that creative thinking may help inform solutions when looking at the wider picture.

The field testing of the mobile devices at Risby proved an exceptional success and has already been written up as a short paper 'Supporting Reflection and Creative Thinking by Carers of Older People with Dementia' and delivered by the RNHA Chairman and City University London at the Pervasive Care Conference in Dublin in May 2011.

Some of the detail and scope of their series of usage trials with new MIRROR technologies and tools to explore their feasibility, is reported below, followed by a description of the development of the Twitter trial and Carer App.

Usage Trials

(1) trial usage of selected creativity techniques; involving four care staff, one activity coordinator and one nurse for one day using creativity techniques to resolve recognized and emerging care problems. The data included creative outcomes and interview feedback on creativity techniques in the care home environment. Results are reported in an MSc thesis produced at City University London

(2) trial usage of Twitter for recording resident observations, through text recognition and speech recognition on mobile devices; involving one week of usage of 3 mobile devices with Twitter in real care work to make resident observations by up to 8 care staff. Some 48 tweets containing 150 'bits' of information were communicated, including status reports, tasks done, residents mood and professional issues.

(3) trial usage of new creativity support app called CARER to handle challenging resident behaviour, on mobile devices; involving sporadic use and exploration of the Carer application over one week on 3 mobile devices distributed to 10 care staff during their shift work. A small number of challenging behaviour queries were entered into the Carer app

(4) debriefing session for effectiveness and problems associated with (2) and (3) involving one two-hour session with one nurse who acted as coordinator of research activities during trial week, with interview notes and feedback in audio and transcribed form.

Recording Practices

As part of the initial articulation of business needs, the RNHA stressed that recording of resident information was vital both for the well-being of the resident and the protection of the staff. Should there be a breakdown in care and an Inspector be called in, only documented evidence is taken into account. Also slow, barely perceptible changes in resident health can fail to be recorded or be recorded in such an insubstantial a way as to be useless.

The rest of this note describes the City University approach to tackling these issues, and the rapid progress made at Risby.

Current practice

Staff carry a small notebook and pen to record care activities and resident well-being during the day. At the end of shift there is handover and at Risby (though this is not universal at all care homes) the information is keyed into a computer. There are very few computers for this purpose so staff have to queue and are unable to spend as much time as they would wish. As a result information is often incomplete and does not provide a basis on which to reflect on symptoms, diagnoses and possible improvements to the care of an individual resident.

New approach

City University London therefore decided to investigate whether mobile hand held devices could replace the paper and pen and lead to timely and more useful records being created, especially by the carers of people with dementia, in their words.

In MIRROR we conjecture that mobile devices can be adapted to support the same tasks but in situ during resident care shifts, thereby reducing the distance between the care tasks and the documentation of these tasks. These mobile devices can also increase the bandwidth of communication between care staff by enabling them to communicate directly more effectively during a shift and gain access to shared good care practices. In particular we have designed prototype mobile apps to encourage two specific improvements to the care process:

(i) more reflective observations about residents by care staff, and;

(ii) more contextualized support for care staff to aid them with the diagnosis and response to difficult situations.'

In addition to stimulating reflection whilst capturing data, City University London also sought to deploy the mobile devices so that they could bring more contextualised support to the carer to help them diagnose and respond to difficult situations. To achieve this a store of 'case studies' of good practices began to be assembled. The intention being that the carer could quickly look up a similar problem and reflect quickly on whether the solution to that similar problem would work in this instance.

Unlike with some complicated projects the issues of semantics and ontologies can be neatly side-stepped by the use of natural language to describe the problem and natural language parsing and matching technologies is used to select suitable comparator cases.

More Reflective Observations

In the feasibility test more reflective observations by care staff are assisted through the use of micro-blogging – in essence each member of care staff micro-blogs each observation in real-time using Twitter. Twitter restricts each blog to a maximum length of 144 characters, thereby requiring the person who is blogging to reflect on the content and structure of each blog to ensure that it is complete and coherent, rather than provide a less structured monologue.

Each member of care staff is guided to write an observation in three parts: (i) the room number of the resident as his or her unique identifier; (ii) the observation made, and; (iii) his or her own reflection, encouraged by the prompt – what does this mean?

Care staff enter these observations directly in situ using the mobile device and Twitter app shown on the left-hand side of Figure 1.

In MIRROR the app is implemented on an Apple iPod Touch locked to provide only the capabilities needed by care staff during a shift. The iPod Touch was chosen to be portable by care staff during a shift: it is only 4.4 inches tall, 2.3 inches wide, 0.28 inches wide and weighs only 100 grams.

Unlike regular tweets that can be followed by members of the public, each observation is posted to a locked account that can only be accessed by the other devices being used by care staff and the shift supervisor. Each tweet can also be encrypted to ensure complete resident anonymity. Unlike the current process with paper notes, each observation is shared in real-time as shown on the right-hand side of Figure 1, thereby increasing communication between the care staff in the residential home and directing support to residents quickly.

The Apple iPod touch devices rely on keypads for data entry. Recognising the diversity of care workers and their variable skills at entering data via a keypad, City University London also installed voice recognition software (Dragon speak)

Figure 1

Finding similar instances

To help carers quickly find similar instances City University London made use of query expansion and term disambiguation because descriptions of the problem written by the carer could easily be incomplete or ambiguous. A major part of the 'clockwork' is delivered by the on-line lexicon WordNet coupled with a 2-step query matching.

The outcome, what is important to RNHA, is a ranked list of the top three matched case studies.

Further work on this extremely promising strategy will be carried out during summer 2011.

Imaginary and the 'Think Better Care' serious game

At the first General Assembly in Milan (November 2010) it was agreed between i-maginary and RNHA that an exemplar serious game should be produced that would enable care staff to see what a serious game could look like and how it might help them experiment with and reflect on care choices made in a totally risk-free environment.

The RNHA team have been working with i-maginary since and by the end of April the first serious game - 'Think Better Care' - based on complex dialogues in a fictitious care home, was ready for limited testing with selected managers from the group of RNHA volunteer test-sites.

A couple of the pages in the game are shown below:

The screens present a series of challenging situations for the carer to deal with.

The user chooses from a multiple choice of options to respond.

Following a self assessment, below, the user is provided with feedback graphics to assist them reflect on their choices.

Variable	1	2	3	4	5
Resident Satisfaction I think the resident was completely satisfied with the answers I gave and my behaviour:	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Quality of Response I answered the resident's questions and demands fully and honestly.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Sensitivity of Response I adjusted my response according to resident behaviour:	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Time management I managed my time well, balancing care for each resident against my other tasks.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

After initial positive feedback, this is now being widened to other staff.

The game can be found at : : <http://service.i-maginary.eu/rnha/login.jsp>

Using the Username= **mirror-rnha** and Password= **rnha1**

The imaginary developers describe their game,:

Carers are often hard pressed and 'have their work cut out' in order to accomplish all the tasks they have been allotted. Sometimes though, the achievement of tasks can be at the expense of the feelings of the resident. There is a world of difference between putting someone in clothes and helping them choose what they will wear and helping them to get dressed where they find it difficult – perhaps doing up that awkward button, say.

Putting it bluntly there can be a trade-off between getting through the jobs and being kind and caring to the resident, the service user. The more dependent the old person is, i.e. the less competent and slower, the more the tensions between getting through the task and providing quality care become exacerbated. Frustrations can lead to misery for both the carer and the cared for.

Our game has been devised to allow the carer to experiment in the risk-free environment of a serious game. It starts by offering the player the choice to select one of three shifts. Each shift then has a typical range of tasks that have to be performed by the carer. For example in the morning the resident may need help in getting up, going to the toilet or in having breakfast. Later the resident may, or may not wish to join in leisure activities and so on.

During a normal shift at work a carer can be presented with a number of unexpected dilemmas when dealing with an elderly person who may not be behaving rationally. There is only one chance for the carer to get it right, but simply experimenting whilst at work could lead to unacceptable risks and the potential to cause upset and harm to both the carer and the elderly resident.

Hence in this game, certain scenarios are introduced where the carer has to choose between alternatives. The intention is that each alternative presented should force the carer to think carefully and to reflect on which of the answers best meet the complex balance that has to be achieved. A balance between own needs, the needs of the resident, and the business needs of the home, usually represented by time and tasks completed.

The intention is that such a game can help the carer, when confronted with similar dilemmas during an actual work shift, to make better choices. Not only that but the aggregate scores achieved are presented back to the player- offering some pointers to ways to improve future performance in general.

It is important to note that this game has a further purpose, and that is to introduce a range of technologically lagging small businesses – the care homes – to the novel concept of serious games. It is hoped that this game will demonstrate the potential for more sophisticated games in the future to augment the training offerings for new staff as well as to refresh the skills of existing staff.

To this end the game will be tested amongst a group of care home test sites. Feedback will be gathered from carers who use the game through questionnaires. Such feedback will be used to improve the game for subsequent releases. It is hoped that the jury will try the game and base their judgement on what has been achieved so far.

Our game does not approach the very serious issue of care training through trivial attempts to 'entertain'. In contrast with much existing training material which is often dull and uninspired, the game offers fascinating and sometimes edgy scenarios. Sometimes there is no 'right' answer but some answers are better than others. The purpose is to get the player to reflect. We consider that the material will be more than sufficient to engage carers as it is, and hope not to be proved wrong when real carers try it out in our test-sites.

The ambition is to help the carer to reflect on what choices might mean in the risk-free game world so that better choices can be made in the care home. We want to reduce those painful learning situations "I wish I had not done that" or "I wish I had not said that" and the concomitant distress occasioned amongst the elderly service users.

Think Better Care contains different elements to help the reflective and learning process:

- players can check their behaviour during the game experience and reflect on it via the feedback
- thanks to the self-evaluation processes, users are stimulated to reflect on their actions and reactions during the game
- seeing the thoughts of counterparts provides players with extra insights into different points of view
- the mood map data allows users to reflect on the ways in which mood can affect performance
- final reports help users to reflect on the whole experience they had during the game.

Currently RNHA are demonstrating the game to Care Home managers, and encouraging a range of staff to try out the game and provide feedback.

Initial responses are positive, and users are keen to provide suggestions for improvement and extend the range of difficult scenarios. These will be noted and used to guide developments.

It is worth noting that this is another aspect of tackling 'challenging behaviour', and again demonstrates commonality, highlighting the fact that such situations occur in a wide range of working environments, and that this methodology too has a wide applicability.

RUB

Description of work at RNHA

RNHA and RUB have been in regular communication since the Creativity Workshops suggested that a closer relationship may be mutually beneficial. RUB had interesting ideas for the usage of technology, and RNHA provided a valuable testing ground. Their initial research involved detailed analysis of the business processes by observation and interview. This is reported extensively below:

This part of the document is meant to be a description of the work AS IS done in care homes associated with the Registered Nursing Home Association (RNHA). The document is the result of joint work done by MIRROR research partners active in user studies at NBN (RUB, NTNU) and RNHA representatives.

Version	Editor(s)	Affiliation	Content
1	Martin Degeling, Michael Prilla	RUB	Initial Structure and Content based on observation and interview study done by RUB

Reflection in Care Homes – RNHA Insights

The Registered Nursing Home Association (RNHA) connects more than 1200 privately owned care homes throughout Great Britain. In the average care home, there are about 40 residents and a total of 70 people on staff. While there is a great variety of reasons to live in a care home, the work in MIRROR is focused to the ever increasing group of elderly people suffering from dementia. In order to focus the user studies on typical homes and residents of this group, the sites were chosen carefully. In particular, we visited one home with about 60 people on staff and about 40 residents.

It has to be mentioned that research considering the user studies at RNHA was done in one particular care home, and thus provides insights into work at care homes, but cannot be taken as applicable for every care home member of RNHA. Additionally, most of the research was done with staff from the morning and afternoon shift, so that information about the night shift only stems from people's reports.

Description of work conducted in the testbed

In the care homes visited, there are mostly people living who suffer from dementia or similar diseases. In the homes, these people are referred to as "residents" or "service users", so in the following, we will use both phrases.

Work in the care home observed is divided into three shifts with a different number people working on the shifts (see Table 1). In the morning shift, there are more people than in other shifts, as residents need to be woken and dressed, including washing, bathing as well as having breakfast and lunch. As some residents have constraints concerning their mobility, this can take a lot of time and needs additional staff and hands.

Table 1: Shift structure at a care home.

Shift	Time	Workers present
Morning	8 (7)1 a.m. – 2 (1) p.m.	1 nurse, 6-7 carers, entertainer, manager
Afternoon	2 (1) p.m. – 10 (9) a.m.	1 nurse, 4-5 carers, entertainer, manager
Night	10 p.m. – 8 a.m.	1 nurse, 2-3 carers

The day in the care home visited is semi-structured in terms of both allocation of care to people and its timely structure (see Table 2 for a brief outline of the day structure). In this home, carers get a list of five people every morning. During the shift, this will be the group they are especially responsible for. This group may change daily, but at least on a regular basis to avoid one carer caring for the same people all the time – however, some carers are excluded for a particular resident if they do not get on well together.

A sample day in the morning shift can be as follows: In the morning, carers wake their group of people up, assist them in leaving the bed, wash and dress them and take them to the day room, where they get breakfast. Alternatively, one carer per day is given a group of two people and after these have been served, this carer supports the making of breakfast and lunch. After breakfast, the carers are joined by an entertainer, who plays games with residents, paints with them and does other daytime activities. During the morning and after lunch, which is served at 1 p.m., carers engage in these activities, too. Additionally, they assist the residents in e.g. going to the toilet and care for their well-being in general. In the afternoon, entertainment and other care activities continue, until residents are brought to bed.

Every shift at the care home begins with a handover meeting in order to ensure every carer present knows about the state of their residents. The day might also be interrupted by some of the other meetings described below. Additionally, the carers may have to interrupt themselves from doing their work in order to get the documentation done.

Table 2: Day structure at a care home.

Time	Activity	
8 a.m. – 10 a.m.	Waking residents and getting them ready for the day.	Docu ment ation (care)
10 a.m. – 1 p.m.	Daytime activities and documentation	
1 p.m. – 2 p.m.	Lunch	
2 p.m. – 6 p.m.	Daytime activities, excursions, doctor’s visits etc. and documentation	
6 p.m. – ...	Dinner and taking residents to bed	
10 p.m. – 8 a.m.	Observations of residents’ sleep, assistance during the night	

All carers in the home receive regular training and supervision, the frequency depending on their knowledge and time. Training is done personally, in full day lectures and is usually about care activities. New employees receive more training and before they are allowed to care for people on their own, they shadow a senior carer for two weeks. According to the junior staff we spoke to, this prepares them well for their job. In addition, all carers reported that they do not need special skills and do not need to comply to complex standards in order to do their job properly. In terms of supervision, there are regular talks with the manager or a

¹Although shifts are pretty regular, people are allowed to shift time according to their needs.

senior carer (depending on the person receiving supervision), in which they talk about their performance, things they want to learn and problems as well as good practice during the last weeks and months.

Work in care homes has some special characteristics in terms of collaboration and teamwork. Most important, people working in care homes are on a great variety of working hours per week. While some work five to six days a week, some others may only come in once a week. As a consequence, there is a core of people forming the different shifts every day, and another group of carers who join different shifts. In their cooperation, there are hardly any rules or standard procedures: Besides the assignment of a group of residents to each carer and the structure shown in Table 2, the day is structured according to routine and spontaneous needs. The only constraints we could see is that residents are never left alone in their day room and that for all medical issues, the nurse has to be involved.

Personas in the target group

At the observed sites, just as in many other care homes in the RNHA, employees (including carers, nurses and managers) are predominately female

Mandy: Senior carer, experienced and at the age of 47. Has been doing the job for 9 years, including a pause for having her babies. Most of the time, she works in the same shift and is in about five or six times a week. Every day, she receives an update about what happened in the night shift by a nurse. She documents all of her tasks properly and regularly, but does not take notes on a daily basis. Thus, her experiences mainly reside in her memory. She also reads minutes from staff meetings, but does not remember everything from them. Mandy uses a computer at home, but is rather reluctant to use any IT system, as she thinks she does not know how to do it. In her work, she is responsible for guiding younger colleagues, using her experience to find solutions for problems and she runs meetings among staff, caring for their well-being. Also, during the day, colleagues approach her if there is a problem. If someone is sad in trouble, cares for them and gives them a hug. Before her job at the care home, she has done home caring. Her main motivations for doing the job are to make the residents happy and to share her experiences with younger carers. Additionally, she likes to train younger colleagues and to give them a comfortable feeling in their daily work. Mandy sometimes thinks about what happened during the day, including problems occurred and things that went well. She also talks about that to some colleagues, who she thinks are trustworthy and experienced. She is interested in reflecting about residents, but also sometimes tries to help when organizational problems need to be solved. She is a mother of two children at 12 and 15 years. Therefore, at home she has only little time to reflect her work. She also does not compare herself or her performance to other, as she thinks that everybody does their work well and has their own way of doing it.

Danielle: Junior carer, one year of experience in care, at the age of 25. Danielle is new to the care job, and has started it one year ago, as her aunt is also doing this job in the same home. She works three times a week, mostly in the same shift, as it fits her lifestyle. Therefore, Julia has to give her an update about what happened if she has not been in for a couple of days. On some days, she has not enough time to complete all the documentation work and thus, the manager sometimes allows her to skip some input into the care system. She has used a diary to write things done in the first months of her work, but stopped doing that now. Sometimes, she does not know how to do something. Then, she asks a senior carer to show her how to do it, but does not keep notes on that. Danielle likes using

technology such as mobile phones and services such as Twitter and Facebook, but is not allowed to do so during her daily work. In her daily work, she is responsible for waking residents, making them ready for the day, getting them meals and caring for their well-being throughout the day. This also is her main motivation for working at the care home, as she wants to see people smiling. Sometimes, she is affected emotionally by disturbing interactions with residents and needs to be helped. In meetings, she talks about these feelings and others help her to overcome them. Also, she sometimes feels uncomfortable when others speak about their problem and starts to giggle during the meetings. But she always tries to provide help for problems with residents. In her day, she also often thinks about things she has done and whether they went well or not. This is her main motivation for reflection and she would like to know more about she does her work. Sometimes, she also compares herself to others and talks to them about her work, preferring senior staff as a communication partner. She does not care so much to think about work organization, as she thinks everything works well – however, in meetings she agrees if someone comes with a problem.

Julia: Dayshift nurse, at the age of 32. She has been doing the job as a registered nurse for some time now. During the day, she is responsible for the medical treatment of residents. Additionally, she keeps track of carers' documentation of what happened to the residents in order to see if they are well or not. Additionally, she runs a handover meeting with the late shift nurse and the late shift carers every day, telling them about the residents' day and about special events such as appointments at the doctor's or incidents happened. During this meetings, she and the nurse are the only people to take personal notes. She has her own office, but most of the time, she is on her feet somewhere in the home. Therefore, carers often look for her.

Interaction among staff

There are several occasions for interaction during the day. The majority of these interactions is spontaneous and very brief and e.g. consists of a short talk about a resident. There are also (semi-) formal and scheduled interaction occasion such as meetings and breaks, in which there is more time to exchange thoughts and experiences. In the following, we summarize such occasions.

Spontaneous encounters: Whenever a carer feels they need to contact another carer, they communication is started spontaneously. Additionally, carers meet in the hallway or day room of a care home and use these occasions for a brief talk. Talks can be triggered by a problem with residents, a question how to do a certain tasks or the need to support another carer in a particular task such as lifting a resident. Sometimes, there is also a private reason such as feeling sad.

Daily breaks: According to staff members, during their daily breaks, they sit together and talk about their work with other carers. Is has to mentioned that they do this in the residents' day room instead of going to their staff room. As staff reported, in the breaks there is more time to talk about problems and other encounters with residents during the day.

Handover meeting: Between every two shifts in a care home, there is a so called handover meeting. This is done to inform the nurse and the carers on the particular shift about the day/night of each resident. In addition, carers who are not working very day are informed about the recent development of the residents they are responsible for in their shifts. During the meeting, the nurse from the past shift iterates through a list of the residents, talks about

their status and assigns tasks to carers. For this, the lists given to the carers in the beginning of each shift and the notes carers made on these residents are used. The communication in the handover is primarily between the two nurses participating. Carers are informed, too, but neither take notes nor actively engage into the communication besides short questions. A typical handover meeting lasts about 15 minutes.

Reflective meeting: In some care homes, so called reflective meetings are run. In home of the homes observed, such meetings used to be run once every two weeks and have been reduced to be run on demand. Staff (especially juniors) mentioned that they were happy for this decision. The meetings are run either by a senior carer or by the home manager. Participation (at least in the home visited) is voluntary, but in practice most carers participate. In the meeting, the facilitator mentions some of the problems she has collected from carers and also asks the carers present whether they have anything to discuss such as problems or positive encounters. In the course of the meeting, each issue is briefly introduced by the facilitator or a carer and discussed. Most carers engage in these discussions, especially if they are related to residents or a carer's feelings at work. Reflective meetings can last from ten to 30 minutes, depending on the amount of issues discussed.

Staff meetings: In staff meetings, the manager gathers all (except some to continue care) members of the staff. In the home visited, such meetings are run irregularly whenever the manager thinks she needs a meeting. Reasons for meetings can be found in changes to be applied in daily work or major problems to be solved. In contrast to the reflective meetings, participation is obligatory. In the meetings, staff may also bring in problems, but meetings are mainly used to announce and explain changes in procedures and work in general.

Support for daily work: documents / data and other helping means

Although work in care homes is not organized restrictively, there are plenty of different documents and tools a carer has to use or may use during the day. This is mainly due to three reasons. First, work needs to be given a certain frame, which is reflected by a list of residents to be taken care about and a shared (paper) calendar for the residents' appointments. Second, care homes have to document care given in order to scrutinize their work and get paid. This is shown by various sheets for task documentation and a computer tool used to gather all this information. Third, in order to provide good care, homes have to have good knowledge of their residents and how to treat them. This is implemented by a binder used as a care plan for each resident and another binder representing information about the resident's past. In the following, we will shortly describe the most documents and tools used as support for daily work.

Group sheet: At the beginning of shift, a carer is given a sheet with a list of residents she has to particularly take care of during the day. On this sheet, not only the names are imprinted, but there is also enough room to make notes on the resident. During the day, carers use this room to write down everything they need has to be document for the resident. There notes are then used as an archive of residents' status and for the handover meetings. As we were told by the carers, they also use the archive of notes to inform themselves about the last days and weeks of a resident.

Calendar at the nurses' office: The nurses keep a calendar in their office, in which they note appointments such as doctor's visits of the residents. If there is any special advice for a resident, it is attached to the day it is due in the calendar. The calendar can be viewed by all management, care and nursing staff and is mainly about medical issues.

Shift plan: In order to get an overview who is on shift and when they arrive, there is a handwritten shift plan at the pin board in the nurses' office.

Documentation of tasks: For all tasks such as giving residents meals and drinks, talking them to the toilet, bathing or washing and the like, the carers need to do documentation of special sheets. In addition, they have to document observations such as incidents or problems, the bed turning during the night and other behaviour of the residents. For all this documentation, there are special sheets, which are either carried around by the carers or lie in the residents' rooms. This documentation is used primarily for verification of care given and assessments, but – as also the case for the notes on residents – is also used by carers to get information how well a patient is (e.g. if a resident is angry, they look up if it may be caused by not being to the toilet for a longer time). All this documentation is done with pen and paper and later it has to be put into the E.C.S. by carers.

E.C.S. (Elderly Care System): At one of the homes we visited, the manager and carers used a tool called Elderly Care System (ECS), which is a commercial tool not present in all care homes. In the particular home, the tool is used to keep a digital record of care given and additional information on residents. It is accessible via computers in the care home and carers need to transfer all their paper-based documentation into it manually. It contains all information about residents, ranging from personal data such as weight to accounting data and it can also be used to create various report based on the documentation. However, for the care plans, Microsoft Word is used, as apparently this is easier and more reliable. As we were told, the system also lacks proper functionality for documenting incidents and other important issues of residents, as it only allows free text documentation of such. As a result, such documentation is short and unstructured, lacking important details such as solutions to problems or follow-up events. Originally, the system was chosen due to its ease of use and usability, but it also has limitations in the length of input to some text boxes. Access control is done by fingerprint sensors, so only authorized staff can have a look into the system.

Care plan: In the manager's office, there is a paper-based binder used as a care plan for each resident. In this plan, there is short personal information on a resident, a short history of care given, descriptions of problems occurred and instructions for care to be given regularly (every day, week etc.). The level of granularity is very high: The plan includes detailed information about how to wake the resident up, what she likes to do and eat, as well as information about how to approach and talk to her. The plan is produced by the manager and updated every three months as part of a regular assessment of each resident. In addition, it may be updated due to unforeseen events. This care plan needs to be known by staff caring for a resident and, according to staff's reports, helps them to understand residents.

Life history: For each resident, the care home strives to produce a paper-based life history binder. It contains information about a resident's family, past jobs and hobbies, pets, occupancies and other details of their live that staff happens to find out or is provided with by relatives and friends of the resident. Additionally, it contains pictures illustrating this history. This history, in addition, is developed in cooperation with the residents. It can be used by carers to inform themselves about a resident and e.g. derive topics for chatter with them: "it tells me what they used to do when they were younger what jobs they were in. And then that helps me sort of communicate with them"(BJT09, I. ...).

The center of information provision, sharing and sustainment can be seen in the group sheet each carer is handed out in the beginning of their shifts. In this sheet, each carer notes that is

happening during the day, including details on residents and care given. Carers told us that it is this information they need for their daily work and that they come back to it in order to see how well the residents are: “To see if somebody is being feeling unwell that day, or you know like that” (NLJ08, l. ...). The central role of these sheets is mirrored by handover meetings, in which the care sheets of the current shift are used for briefings of the respective next shift of carers.

However, while some information is already available digitally in the E.C.S., most (documentation) work is done on paper, and then later transferred into a computer (mostly into the E.C.S. system). This is inefficient and time consuming for the carers and may cause carers to document more briefly than they would if there was not need to transfer their documentation to the system. Additionally, it also causes problems of lacking contextual availability of relevant data. In the care homes, the life history and care plans are central documents to be informed about a resident and to spread information about them. Both are used mainly on paper and composed mostly by manually transferring data e.g. from the E.C.S. Therefore, items in the care plan are not synchronized with the life history and vice versa. Also, comments cannot be linked directly to that and there is no mechanism how to directly propose additions and changes to the care plan. Moreover, care insights are documented in the personal care plan of resident and not shared besides this, meaning that if there is a solution working well for a characteristic of one resident, it will not be known automatically if another resident also shows this characteristic. These problems have been known to knowledge management and learning as well.

Therefore, we propose to have most documentation available as digital data and related or synchronize central documents. For these documents, besides interaction with the E.C.S., there should be lightweight access for carers e.g. by tags for searching and touchpads for commenting on. This can support the continuous documentation of relevant information and work data, the building of collaboratively shared knowledge as well as a culture of reflection and mutual support, in which knowledge is easily accessible and activities of participating are rewarded (by e.g. management) and rewarding (e.g. by finding ways to work better and to care better for certain residents).

Current status, problems and motivation of reflection

Reflection is happening daily in care homes. There are scheduled occasions of reflection such as team meetings and short reflective session as well as spontaneous encounters of reflection, when carers and nurses e.g. reflect on an incident or on a resident’s wellbeing. Reflection is being done on different levels, depending on the actors reflecting, the occasion of reflection and the topic reflected about. Additionally, the environment of a care home poses special constraints for reflective practice, especially if reflection is done by more than one individual. In the following, we give an overview of existing reflection practice and analyse it due to support needed and possibilities to integrate the MIRROR reflection tools.

A typical type of reflection, which happens multiple times in the daily work of carers and nurses, can be found in spontaneous communicative interactions among staff. These reflective encounters are usually triggered by a problem, an incident or a good experience in daily work, but also to discuss individual reflection results. Topics we have been reported include

- Problems with residents suffering from dementia, e.g. how to cope with typical behaviour such as a patient always asking to go home or having to tell residents the same thing every day
- The state residents are in and their development, e.g. asking themselves why a resident has not felt good for a couple of days or telling others something new about them and their life history
- Securing the floor by e.g. putting things away, which have been picked up and left by residents, also avoiding such situations
- Ensuring that their way of doing things is appropriate, e.g. how they treat certain residents
- Personal problems related to work or influencing the ability to work, e.g. “if you come into work feeling low or something” (J, ...)
- Incidents happened during the day such as aggressive behaviour of a resident, arguments or fights between residents or residents falling down

There are two situations of reflecting these topics concurrently, off meetings and spontaneously.

First, there are many situations in which two or more carers work together or meet in the hallway or day room of the home. Thus, the combination in the reflection group is more or less random. In their reflection practice, they usually discuss issues related to concrete tasks and try to help each other by reflecting their practice.

Second, there are situations in which carers explicitly address a particular colleague, mostly because of personal relations, trust in this colleague and her capability to listen as well as experience of the addressed other. In such situations, more information and details are shared. Additionally, the expectation of finding a solution or understanding a particular issue better are much higher. In particular, carers reported to us that they address senior staff members because they wanted them to provide concrete and quick help in situations they did not know how to get on with. Additionally, from carers' description of these two different ways of spontaneous reflection, it becomes obvious that reflection with random colleagues is mainly done for relief and reassurance, while reflection with explicitly chosen partners is very much oriented towards results and exploring the background of issues. Thus, this second type of reflection usually leads to changes on a broader scope, while the first kind mainly serves the purpose of the carer initiating the reflective interaction.

There are also pre-scheduled occasions of reflection, which in the care homes can be found in the staff meetings, the reflective meetings and the handover sessions.

Typical topics of reflection for these occasions we found in

- The development of residents and care planning for them, based on the notes (other) carers provided about them (mainly done in handover meetings).
- Organizational and legal changes making changes in daily work necessary
- Making cooperation and work structures more convenient and efficient for carers and residents, e.g. changing the way toilet groups are formed or postponing lunch to give residents more time for contemplation in the morning
- Secondary process organization such as provision with sanitary pads and washing clothes in time
- Personal problems either concerning care provision for a resident or emotional problems in dealing with certain people (mainly done in reflective meetings)

In contrast to spontaneous reflection, dedicating time and having different people sit down for reflection offers the possibility to go deeper into details and understand things better. As one carer told us, this helped the group of carers understand some managerial decisions better: “I think after a while some people, some colleagues probably thought; no it would be a bad idea. But then everyone just agreed when they saw the benefits it had for everyone” (BJT09, I. ...).

Concerning motivation for reflective communication and interaction, a rather homogeneous picture can be drawn. For most carers, there are two primary goals in their work, namely the well-being of residents, including good care and making them happy (Interviewer: “What does make a day successful for you?”, Carer: “If I made somebody happy and comfortable”, NLJ08, I. ...), and their personal well-being as a result of doing their job properly and thus knowing that they do something helpful and valuable (“I thought it went, it went well. Because there was no violence or anything between the two [...]. I was able to [...] sort of calm [them] down.”, J ...). While these motivational aspects can be found for all carers, for non-junior staff, a third dimension of reflection can be seen. Both experienced and senior carers repeatedly reported that they always try to be a help for younger colleagues, supporting them in their daily work and helping them to improve daily: “we’ll take them aside and discuss it and hopefully deal with it”. While this can partly be attributed to a broader ambition of providing good care, it also shows a sense of responsibility for these carers, which differentiates them from younger carers, who are struggling to become good carers and thus facing different problems.

In this context, there is also a difference between junior carers and more experienced staff. When asked, junior carers deliberately report that they often compare themselves to others and they use this as a learning mechanism: “I sometimes compare sort of my strengths and weaknesses to other members”, “[...] if that was to help then it could be done” (BJT09, ... and ...). More experienced carers, in contrast, report that they do not compare themselves to others, as they have found their way of working and think that differences in individual work do not count in a large amount: “Cause I learn something everyday, that’s... at this job you learn something from the service users usually and your nurse in charge.” (NLJ08, I. ...).

Figure 1: Levels of reflection in a care home, including relations between the levels.

By analysing the carers' description of their daily work and reflection practice, one can derive different levels of reflection and reflection topics, which are interrelated to each other. Figure 1 gives an overview of these topics. In the figure, we differentiate between task- and incident-related topics and more comprehensive reflection topics. For the first group, topics mentioned above such as problems with residents (behaviour), securing the floor (good care) and feeling bad as a result of work (emotional problems) can serve as examples. For the latter group, examples can be found in discussing the development of residents and potential reasons for it (care-related) as well as postponing lunch (organizational) are illustrating examples.

Figure 2: Levels of reflection in a care home, including relations between the levels.

In practice, it seems that people are more aware of reflection done for task-related topics such as discussing a particular incident and why it might have happened: “we [...] do it on breaks really. We can sort of reflect on, if someone needs help or, if like we're doing well” (BJT09, ...). Considering more comprehensive topics, they are interested in these as well (“[...] if you find out something interesting about them, then you can talk about it. Just to let everyone sort of know”, (BJT09, I. ...)), but engage much less in these. This could also be observed in reflective meetings, where carers are very active in providing solutions for concrete cases, but more reluctant when it comes to proposing solutions for organizations issues. This may be attributed to lacking experience on this level, low perception of self-efficacy in engaging in such topics or a feeling to be forced into reflection rather than a feeling comfort with this, as one carer reported when asked about this kind reflection in meetings: “Usually I have to talk about [this], yeah” (BJT09, ...). Additionally, younger carers seem to me more open to be addresses and supported by senior carers than speaking freely about their problems in front of other carers: “[I] don't really attend many of the reflective groups because I find out what I need to by the staff” (BJT09, ...). However, we could also observe junior staff to speak up in meetings, telling other about problems. Summing this up, our insights show that for collaborative reflection, there is a need to provide different tools or access to the MIRROR appsphere for different kinds of carers.

Handover meetings are run daily between the shifts. As they are short, there is not much room for reflection. Additionally, they are run by one nurse and topics are mainly addressing

the nurse of the next shift. However, the topics are mainly influenced by the notes carers provide about the residents' days. In scheduled meetings besides the regular handovers, these topics are either brought up by senior staff such as senior carers or managers or other carers are explicitly asked to talk about what they think needs to be changed. In practice, we were told that meetings and topics in these meetings are prepared by the senior or manager facilitating these meetings. In addition, team meetings are only run when a senior or manager feels there is a need to run them. Taken together, reflection topics are mostly brought up by senior and management staff. The influence of other staff is reduced to telling senior staff about an issue and asking them to bring it up or prepare to talk about it in meeting. There is no existing process of having carers initiate a meeting, and such behaviour is also not part of the culture in the home observed.

Senior staff and management are the centre of reflection in care homes. They are running and determining meetings of reflection, and they are central communication and reflection partner for all carers we talked. While these carers told us that they like to work and briefly chat with all of their colleagues, they stated that for problems or things that need to be changes, they address a senior: "I prefer to talk to senior carers" (BJT09, I. ...). According to the carers, this is due to their experience in life and work as well as because they are in charge of solving issues in a home: "Well, the seniors are always there, so mostly the girls go up to the senior and say 'Oh I've got a problem' or 'Come and discuss this'. And so we'll take them aside and discuss it and hopefully deal with it" (NLJ08, I. ...). This fact needs to be taken into account when support is provide, as is shows the communication structure in a care home. Additionally, it implies that for collaborative reflection, experience, seniority and competence play an important role. If this is a general finding, it can offer new possibilities for composing reflection groups.

An important problem carers repeatedly reported is a lack of time for purposeful reflection, be it individual or collaborative: "[...] you don't have time to think during the day really" (NLJ08, I. ...). This is a typical problem for secondary processes such as knowledge sharing and reflection. Stemming from this, there is a lack of proper documentation of reflection results besides formal meeting minutes. Concurrent documentation is not done, as hardly any carer takes notes. This oftentimes hinders the transfer of valuable results and knowledge among staff. This problem can also be seen for the documentation of impressions the carers get from residents during their daily work (Group sheet): Although carers are willing to document all of these impressions, they feel they are lacking time for it and, in addition, they do not know which information may be relevant – another typical problem known from knowledge management. Thus, information such as the context of problems or follow-up observations on residents' reaction to solutions is hardly provided. As a manager told us in the user studies, this lack of context in the descriptions hinders their understanding and re-usage by both other carers and senior or managerial staff, who would like to derive topics for reflection meetings from such documentation.

NTNU

Work with the NTNU has been on two fronts, primarily with on-site research at the Palm Court Nursing Home, with some software development work as part of a student project.

Short description of the Palm Court

The Palm Court is a small UK nursing home in South England specializing in dementia care. The home has 39 residents and a total of 48 staff. At any time there is a RGN on duty. On the dayshifts, one of the two managers will be at work and in charge. In addition, the owner of the home is present on a daily basis and is generally actively involved in the running of the home. The majority of staff are not native English speakers have a background from e.g. India and the Far East.

In the home there are three wards (called 'houses') each of which gets assigned teams of carers on a day-to-day basis. In each team one of the carers has the role of team leader with particular responsibilities for coordination and reporting. In addition, there are senior carers with responsibilities for the care staff across the wards.

The home is located in a residential area in a couple of early 1900 century buildings that have been connected by a smaller building and extended with more buildings towards the garden. As a consequence, the interior layout of the home is a mix of old-fashioned and modern, with a couple of staircases.

The work of the carers is structured into three shifts. The carers work two types of days: short days (until the afternoon handover) and long days (until the evening handover).

There are two lounges where the residents spend most of their daytime, the residents of two of the wards sharing the biggest lounge. A third living room serves as dining room as well as space for meetings with relatives etc. Further, there is a beautiful garden designed to provide various stimulus to the residents

For the residents, when they have been given assistance to get washed and dressed and get seated in the lounge, the main morning events are breakfast, medication round and activities. The latter is adapted to the preferences and abilities of each resident; it could for instance be chatting with the staff, going for a walk to the garden or playing a word game with a carer in the lounge. During the morning the residents are also served tea and fruit. Lunch is at 12 pm, with some residents going to the dining room and some staying in the lounge. After lunch the residents again spend their time in the lounge before supper..

The morning handover meeting at 07 am lasts about 30 minutes. The meeting takes place in the biggest lounge in the presence of the residents who are already up and dressed. In the first part of the meeting the manager goes through the list of residents, commenting on their condition and, wherever there is something to be noted, goes into detail on recent changes and events as well as special considerations or actions that need to be taken by the staff. The second part of the meeting is allocated to presentation, explanation and discussion of key issues of dementia care and in particular the care model/philosophy deployed in the home. Also the mission statement of the home is repeated (e.g. by having one of the carers say it aloud). It is mostly the manager who is speaking in the morning meeting, but some feedback and input is also provided by the staff. The manager assigns teams of carers to the

wards. Immediately after the meeting, there is a quick session among the carers in which a more detailed allocation of residents and tasks to single carers is made.

In addition to the morning meetings there is a bi-weekly lecture by the care home owner, who has an academic background in nursing and a strong focus on learning and on-the-job-training as well as the chosen model of dementia care. The systematic attention to learning/training and the dementia care model guides the activity within the care home, but also play an important role externally towards relatives of current and prospective residents. The topics addressed in the lecture will be repeated and elaborated in subsequent morning meetings.

A third type of scheduled meeting in which reflection may take place is the evaluation meeting that each staff member has with the manager every three months, focusing on the work performance of the staff member.

The IT infrastructure at the Palm Court can be considered limited. Only the owner and the administrative assistant have computers and use them in their work. The information processing and sharing by the manager, nurses and carers is totally paper based (leaving out the calling system). There is no internet connection (wireless or otherwise) in the common areas and resident rooms. The owner sometimes helps residents communicate with relatives via Internet and the PC in his office.

One characterizing feature of the home is that the owner strongly promotes a particular model/philosophy of dementia care: the Personhood Model of Care (the Kitwood Model); the picture below is taken from the Palm Court website. An outline of the model and implications in the form of lists of do's and don'ts are displayed in posters in and outside the manager's office. The model is important as a guidance to the practices in the home but also as part of the marketing of the home towards relatives of prospective and current residents.

Figure 3: *The Personhood Model of Care, originating in Kitwood, T. (1997): Dementia Reconsidered. The person comes first. Open University Press.*

Picture taken from the Palm Court website:

http://www.palmcourtnursinghome.co.uk/assets/40/Palm_Court/PERSON_CENTRED_CARE_%28Autosaved%29.pdf

Data collection

The data collection performed by NTNU started with an initial, short visit in late March 2011 by Birgit Krogstie and Simone Mora, who had a meeting with the owner in his office and a got a guided tour of the home.

A couple of weeks later, in mid April 2011, Birgit Krogstie returned to the home for two days of observation of the work of the Palm Court staff. This included informal communication with many staff members and three semi-structured interviews with carers. Data were collected as hand written notes, complemented by photos of environment and artifacts (not persons).

For the interviews, the selection of carers was made to include one carer who was new, one with a bit more experience, and one senior carer. The time provided for the interviews was 90 minutes for the senior carer and 60 minutes for each of the two others. The work description and individual reflection questionnaires (see MIRROR deliverable D1.1) were used to guide the interviews, but they were not used rigidly as the interviewer tried to exploit the flow of the conversation to cover the topics of interest.

Reflection at the Palm Court

Findings on reflection and practices relevant to reflection in the care home are reported in MIRROR deliverables 4.1 and 6.1. Some key observations include:

The fact that residents and staff spend most of their daytime together in the lounge provides good occasions for mutual awareness about the care work among the carers (keeping updated on the general situation and each other's work) as well as learning from observation and from asking others. The awareness of the current situation also makes it easier to achieve the there-and-then re-organizing of work needed when something happens requiring extra resources. Not only being constantly aware of the residents' needs but also judge when it is necessary to ask for help from other staff seems to be a key competence for carers. Generally there appears to be a strong – and necessary – culture for helping each other out in the home, and this includes helping out in other areas than your own work area if necessary, e.g. carers helping out in the kitchen or with the laundry if someone is on sick leave.

In the lounge, by speaking aloud to the residents in the lounge (e.g. during feeding or medication), often in a very lively way, the staff achieves communication with the residents and also includes the rest of the room (carers and residents) in what happens, providing not only awareness for the other carers about the ongoing work but also inclusion of the residents into ongoing activity. There is a lot of joking among the staff and with the residents, contributing to a positive atmosphere and a sense that (maybe paradoxically!) everyone is taken seriously.

Issues of concern to carers, leading to needs for reflection, are – not unexpectedly – typically about the well-being of single residents and how to provide the best possible care for them, in line with the Personhood Model, e.g. in handling challenging behavior. There is a strong consciousness that getting to know the single resident is essential to provide the best possible care. The handling of difficult situations is being learnt by new carers and taught by senior ones through day-to-day work and observation of others' work and there-and-then communication. In addition, the care records (found in the resident lounges) are used to

check recent developments and events, and the care plan used to check resident life history and preferences, in order to understand the status and situation of the resident and choose the appropriate action.

The motivation for going into the care profession and do a good job there is influenced by the background of the carer. For instance, having a close relative with dementia may contribute to insights about what dementia is about and the wish to work with it professionally. The cultural background of the carers affect their thinking about care, and for a new carer from a different country reflection on work involves comparison between attitudes and practices in the carer's home country and those in the UK.

To new carers, gaining mastery of the job is primarily about mastering the care situations as outlined above, but additionally it is about being able to account for and articulate the care philosophy of the home, e.g. the Personhood Model and the Mission statement. A carer should be ready to explain the key ideas and concepts to management, to relatives of residents or to a visiting Inspector.

To more senior carers, issues of staff coordination and competence become more prominent and a source of challenges and need for reflection. Also, more senior carers seem – based on their experience - more conscious about the need to weigh against each other different concerns that sometimes conflict, e.g. when the consent of a resident conflicts with the need for a bath.

Currently, some carers make notes during the work day, e.g. in a note book that they carry with them. New carers in their first two weeks get a book for making notes about things to remember. Additionally, individual carers have their own practices of writing down things to remember or and/or reflect, whether in brief lists or in a diary form. This writing may be done on paper and/or on a private computer.

The morning meetings led by the manager provide an occasion for staff to share experiences in a more formal setting. It also provides an occasion to link experiences to more general issues/concepts (e.g. in the Personhood Model). The most important thing about the second part of the morning meeting seems to be linking theory to practice - to the actual care of the individual residents at the Palm Court -and give a reminding 'pep-talk' about the nature and purpose of care. To have key ideas about care explained by the manager in the meeting – often as repetition and elaboration of the material presented in the previous bi-weekly lecture, and sometimes supported by the drawing of diagrams - is seen as a positive and relevant thing by the carers. It may be that the typical non-academic and non-native English background of the carers adds to the value of the explanation. Further, the bi-weekly staff lecture is conducted in the evening, which means that the carers' attention at that point may be lower than they would have wanted, and a repetition of key issues in the morning meetings may ensure that everyone is catching up.

While the carers are involved in communication in the morning handover meetings, the amount of two-way communication varies, e.g. depending on the time available; there are not always 15+15 minutes to be used for the handover, and it is necessary to go through the list of residents. Time for two-way exchanges of experiences and concerns in the morning meeting appears to be an important resource for collaborative reflection within the current practices at the Palm Court.

Life History Application development

The RNHA has also acted as a 'customer' in the specification of an application to be designed and built by a group of IT students of the NTNU. The Life History application to run on an iPad was chosen, and for 6 months the group of 'IT2901' students have been working with RNHA to develop a working prototype of the application. It has been a valuable experience for the students, and has provided some basic technical research to build on in the MIRROR project.

The prototype Life History application can be seen at: <http://ror.kartoffelmos.net>

(username: "pudney", password: "postword").

It is best seen on an iPad, and using the Google Chrome browser.

The students final report is available for technical details along with the source code for use within the project, if technical partners wish to build on this work.

RNHA Test sites

Initially 9 Nursing Homes were included as likely active research sites. All were volunteers from the RNHA membership following a request for expressions of interest from the chairman. Since that time there has been some limited turnover, with 2 Homes falling out due to pressure of work, and 2 more replacements found.

The current list is shown below.

Table of RNHA Test sites

Testsite Name	Contact person	Technical Partner involved	Current Status
Palm Court, East Sussex BN21 2ND www.palmcourtnursinghome.co.uk	Taleb Durgahee	NTNU Onsite KMRC user studies City University	Active with further research
The Marillac Essex CM13 3BL www.marillac.co.uk	Wendy Chen	KMRC user studies NTNU	Active with further research
Risby Suffolk IP28 6RS www.thepartnershipincare.co.uk	Ian Turner	City University RUB Onsite	Active with further research
Kineton Manor Warwickshire CV35 0JT (Website under revamp)	Paula du Rand	KMRC user studies i-maginary City (CB episodes)	Active with further research
Castel Froma Warwickshire CV32 6LL www.castelfroma.co.uk	Helen Finlay	KMRC user studies RUB? FZI?	Active (new research planned)
Wren Hall Nottinghamshire NG16 6AB www.wrenhall.com	Anita Astle	KMRC user studies	Active (to be visited)
Lindfield Christian Care Home West Sussex RH16 2JZ (no website)	Jennifer Herring	KMRC user studies	Inactive for present
Highfield Private Care Home, Essex CB11 4AQ www.highfieldprivatecarehome.co.uk	Angie Silva	i-maginary City (CB episodes)	New (new research planned)
Park View/Ranc Care Essex IG2 7HU www.ranccare.co.uk	Salome Erasmus	City PhD research	New (to be visited)

We are currently visiting each of these homes demonstrating and discussing the work of the project, with a view to gauging the direction and extent of their interest in further participation. Most agree to basic testing of applications as a minimum. The information gained on these visits over the next two to three weeks can help match appropriate testing sites with the appropriate technical partner in future research.

Conclusions after Year 1

One of the primary reasons for producing this document was to facilitate integration within the project. It can be easy for individual partners to pursue their own work without realising the shared interests. By reporting these early findings and impressions, partners can see common themes and interests emerging, for example, the importance of communication. Similarly the focus on the detailed work processes is common to most of the technical partners. Insights gained from one will be relevant to others. And again, the recently-formed Challenging Behaviour working group, composed of a subset of the project, will help to focus all relevant knowledge from various perspectives on this common theme.

In many ways we are ahead of our anticipated schedule, with real applications at a testing phase, and a good range of data collected by on-site visits and off-site documentation. And with real tangible products to demonstrate, it makes our job as a test-bed easier when maintaining interest from the very busy Care Homes themselves.

These Care Homes are providing a challenging but willing testing ground for the technical innovations from the technical partners. As the table above of the Test Sites shows, there is a recognition in the sector that technology has a place in learning and improving performance, even in the most person-centred of businesses - nursing and social care.

This first year has seen a very active response to the RNHA articulated requirements by a range of the technical partners. That the project is achieving mutual benefits so early in the project is very encouraging, and we feel confident that much more can be achieved over the next three years.

Malcolm Rose and Kevin Pudney

RNHA

11th June 2011

MIRROR

STAFF SURVEY

Thank you for participating in this survey.

The MIRROR project tries to develop tools to help employees to learn from their past work-related experiences. The data will be held and used on an anonymous basis, with no mention of your name, but we will refer to your organisation. Findings will only be reported to third parties anonymously and in summarised form.

If you have any questions regarding this questionnaire, kindly contact:

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Information about your person:

First we would like to ask you for some information about yourself:

Age: _____ years

Gender: male female

Position/Job description: _____

Years in current position: _____ years

Years in current workgroup/team (if applicable): _____ years

Years in similar position (including in other places): _____ years

Name of Care Home/Nursing Home: _____

Participant Code:

Kindly write down your participant code. This code consists of the first letter of your place of birth, the first letter of your own first name, the first letter of the first name of your mother, and your own day of birth.

Example: For a person who was born in **L**ondon (first place) called **A**nja (second place) whose mother's first name is **H**ilde (third place), and who was born on the **04**th of February (fourth and fifth place) the code is: **L A H 0 4**.

Your Participant-Code: _____

Note: In the following tables, please check the box that applies to you in each row. For example, **if you agree** to the statement “Sometimes I feel the need to think over what I have been doing and consider alternative ways of doing it” then check the box in the “agree” column.

Reflection					
Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements:	strongly disagree	disagree	neutral	agree	strongly agree
	Sometimes I feel the need to think over what I have been doing and consider alternative ways of doing it	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Reflection

Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements:	<i>strongly disagree</i>	<i>disagree</i>	<i>neutral</i>	<i>agree</i>	<i>strongly agree</i>
Sometimes I feel the need to think over what I have been doing and consider alternative ways of doing it	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I have time to think about my work.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
In our organisation, we are encouraged to think how we do our work.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I frequently think about how I do my work.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I benefit from thinking about how I do my work.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
As a team, we work out what we can learn from past experiences.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
When we are successful as a team, we take the time to try to work out how we did it.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
When things don't work out as they should, we take the time as a team to try to find the cause of the problems.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
We regularly discuss whether the team is working as well as it could.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
If I think I have done my work badly, I discuss this with my supervisor.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
If I think I have done my work badly, I discuss this with colleagues.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I come up with ideas how things could be organised differently here.	<input type="checkbox"/>				

IT Attitudes & Usage Questionnaire

In this questionnaire, we would like to ask you about your attitudes to and usage of technology. Kindly answer the following questions as they apply to you.

	Know of?	Use or have used?
Personal Computer / PC	<input type="checkbox"/> yes <input type="checkbox"/> no	<input type="checkbox"/> yes <input type="checkbox"/> no
Smartphone	<input type="checkbox"/> yes <input type="checkbox"/> no	<input type="checkbox"/> yes <input type="checkbox"/> no
Laptop/Notebook/Netbook	<input type="checkbox"/> yes <input type="checkbox"/> no	<input type="checkbox"/> yes <input type="checkbox"/> no
iPad	<input type="checkbox"/> yes <input type="checkbox"/> no	<input type="checkbox"/> yes <input type="checkbox"/> no
Game Consoles	<input type="checkbox"/> yes <input type="checkbox"/> no	<input type="checkbox"/> yes <input type="checkbox"/> no
Serious Games	<input type="checkbox"/> yes <input type="checkbox"/> no	<input type="checkbox"/> yes <input type="checkbox"/> no

Please indicate your agreement with the following statements	<i>never tried it</i>	<i>strongly disagree</i>	<i>disagree</i>	<i>neutral</i>	<i>agree</i>	<i>strongly agree</i>
Note: A smartphone is a mobile phone that offers more advanced computing ability and connectivity than a contemporary basic feature phone (e.g., calendar, web browser, eMail-functions, e.g., an iPhone or Android phone).						
I am used to typing into a PC.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
I like typing into a PC.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
I am used to voice input or voice recording.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
I like using voice input or voice recording.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
I prefer to use paper instead of the PC.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
I like to use e-paper, e.g., electronic paper or diaries.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
I am used to typing into a smartphone.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
I like to type into a smartphone.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
I am used to wearing physiological sensors (e.g., to measure pulse, heart rate), e.g., as bracelets or chestbelts.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
I like to wear physiological sensors (e.g., to measure pulse, heart rate), e.g., as bracelets or chestbelts.	<input type="checkbox"/>					

Please indicate your agreement with the following statements	<i>strongly disagree</i>	<i>disagree</i>	<i>neutral</i>	<i>agree</i>	<i>strongly agree</i>
Whenever I use something that is computerized, I am afraid I will break it.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
At home, I often use a computer.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Usually, other people convince me to use a computer.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
It is hard for me to understand computers.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I have had bad experiences with computers.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I really enjoy using new personal computer software.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I give more computer advice to other people than I receive.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
There are many things that I can do easier and quicker using a computer.	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Which statement below best describes your level of understanding about how to use a personal computer? [Check one box only!]

- I don't know how to turn on a personal computer.
- I can turn on a PC, but I have trouble with almost everything else.
- I know the basics of how to use my PC, but not much more.
- I understand how to use most of my software, and have little trouble learning new software.
- I completely understand my PC software and hardware.

Smartphones

A smartphone is a mobile phone that offers more advanced computing ability and connectivity than a contemporary basic feature phone (e.g., calendar, web browser, eMail-functions, e.g., an iPhone or Android phone).

Do you use a smartphone in your spare time? yes no

If yes: Which one (e.g., iPhone, Android, Nokia, etc.)? _____

Which statement below best describes your level of understanding about how to use a smartphone? [Check one box only!]

- I do not have any experience with smartphones.
- I can make calls on a smartphone, but I have trouble with almost everything else.
- I know the basics of how to use a smartphone, but not much more.
- I understand how to use most of the software, and have little trouble learning new software.
- I completely understand smartphone software and hardware.

Privacy

Please indicate your agreement with the following statements	<i>strongly disagree</i>	<i>disagree</i>	<i>neutral</i>	<i>agree</i>	<i>strongly agree</i>
I regularly talk to my colleagues about personal things or my feelings.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I always wonder what happens with my personal information when asked for it at work.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I would share my notes and other personal information with my colleagues if they would also do that.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I would share my notes and other personal information with my colleagues if I knew it would help them.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
My team colleagues are trustworthy, as far as handling personal information about me is concerned.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I trust that my team colleagues would keep my best interests in mind when dealing with information about me and my work.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
My team colleagues are in general predictable and consistent regarding the usage of information about me and my work.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
If my superior asked why a problem occurred, I would speak freely even if I were partly to blame.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
My organisation is trustworthy in handling personal information about me.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
My organisation considers the impact of decisions on employee morale.	<input type="checkbox"/>				